

**The Scottish Art Scene:
shrinking resources, growing networks**

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ABSTRACT

The Scottish Art Scene: Shrinking resources, growing networks

This thesis examines specific challenges faced by mature Scottish visual artists in building and maintaining a career of sustainable practice during a time of austerity, Brexit and the Covid pandemic. Key components of this thesis will be teaching resources which include documentary-based interviews with nine mature Scottish visual artists, supported by the work of academic theorists which were useful in helping contextualize the relationship between these artists and the central social power structures of the Scottish 'art world'. It will also include a review of the Scottish government's developing cultural policy between 2015-20 and what impact it has on those artists lives.

In identifying the key milestones of their careers, the Scottish artists interviewed noted the significance of mentors and sponsors help in developing their careers and the fluid and inconsistent relationships they have had with the formal art market. They utilised diverse portfolios to generate income and used their reputations and cultural capital, both offline and online, in supporting themselves through grant funding, social media engagement, online sales or collective artists' mutual support networks. Those artists who were unwilling or unable to transfer their engagement with customers online really financially struggled during the pandemic. A number of female artists interviewed identified patterns of gender based discrimination that had impacted them during their careers.

Given the impact on funding for artists in Scotland in the post-Brexit era, the limited findings also identify the possibility of benefits to a more integrated Scottish government, Creative Scotland and Local Authority strategic approach in cultural and artistic support and the need for key data on cultural spend particularly at local authority level to be disaggregated to make it more accessible in decision making processes (Scottish Government, 2019).

It also highlights a need for the artists to expand their access to resources out with current limited funding routes and the potential value in looking further afield for additional funding support and new collaborative opportunities.

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The Scottish Art Scene: Shrinking Resources, Growing Networks

Introduction; Context of the research problem

At a time of massive impact and disruption of the global economy due to the Covid pandemic, which has created a funding crisis in the culture sector, particularly in the performance, music and film industries where lock-downs and social distancing have removed audiences and income overnight, we see it compounding the precarious temporal, and unsupported working conditions of thousands in the creative and cultural industries (Comunan & England 2020, Banks, 2020). The global Covid pandemic has had an impact on all economic sectors of Scotland, and in particular, visual artists who have had to adjusting to diminishing funding and support over the decades. My research will give some insights into the working lives of mature visual artists together with their evolving strategies and support networks being utilised within this context. It will also review the relevance of current cultural strategies developed by the Scottish government and its relationships with Creative Scotland and local authorities in supporting cultural practices.

This research examines the particular challenges faced by mature Scottish visual artists in making a living as art practitioners during a time of austerity, Brexit and the Covid pandemic. These artists have always struggled to make a living since the Thatcher austerity measures introduced in the 1980s, and as the UK government has progressively cut and privatized previously subsidized cultural provision (McRobbie, 2002, p519) the Covid pandemic has challenged their resourcefulness to the limit. It seems that these visual artists have been inoculated and have built up a resilience to the stresses of the pandemic that is borne out of their historically difficult working conditions prior to it, where they often created work in isolation, set with precarious lifestyles and little financial stability that has helped prepare and sustained them through the Covid lockdown. Their careers have always depended on them adjusting to a hazardous working environment created by the politics of the UK government's austerity years which have progressively cut and privatized previously subsidized cultural provision where it appears now only an instrumentalised, economic case for support would be considered, so their lives are always enmeshed in risk.

What strategies have they developed to navigate the networks of resources available which allow them to both emotionally and financially support their artistic practice and sustain a long-term career within the visual arts? How does the Scottish government, Creative Scotland and local authorities help support and sustain these artists' creative practice and what cultural support structures and policies have been put in place to ensure a viable cultural arts sector? Key academic theorists in this field are useful in helping contextualize this relationship between artists and the central social power structures of the Scottish 'artworld'.

As a Higher Education lecturer teaching art and design programmes for the last twenty years, I am particularly interested in developing teaching resources to support arts graduates build viable careers within the visual arts sector in Scotland. In particular, I'm interested in what challenges they will face and have to be overcome to survive and looking to identify what strategies have been developed by successful Scottish visual artists to sustain their practice. How have these visual artists navigated the networks of resources available which have allowed them to develop a sustainable career path within the visual arts sector, whilst looking to engage with local, national and international support networks?

The Research Question

The central research question of this thesis is ‘how do mature visual artists sustain their creative practice in Scotland and what are the dynamics of the Scottish ‘arts world’ and its relationship to government cultural policy?’

In addition to exploring key academic philosophers and sociologists’ writings on art and culture, I carried out a detailed literature review examining key Scottish cultural policy documentation. This exploration gave me a greater understanding of the nature of art and its relationship to audiences, what power structures sustain it, how artists survive economically and how does this fit within the broader cultural context in Scotland?

The following questions were explored with the interviewed artists:

How do we understand the art sector in Scotland?

Who are the key stake holders?

What are their relationships to one another?

What broad role does the state play in supporting the art sector?

What academic theories help explain the nature of artistic careers and success?

How do the academic theories relate to artists’ career paths in Scotland?

What are the key power dynamics between artists and stakeholders?

At a time of Covid and Brexit, do the academic theories highlight supporting pathways through this?

What is the scope and breadth of focus of current Scottish cultural policy?

Does government policy meet the needs of Scottish arts sector?

How significant is this to artistic success?

How does it reflect key ideas about art and power?

What personal experiences do artists have whilst navigating their career paths?

What do these experiences tell us about the impact of Scottish cultural policy?

What does their experiences tell us about the value of their networks?

What role does online and social media activity now help in their success?

How does gender influence artists success?

What is the short and long term implications for artists in Scotland in light of Brexit, and Covid?

Has government cultural policy been updated to help the art sector?

What are artists doing to help themselves?

What is it like to be a mature practicing visual artist working in Scotland and how do they financially survive in such a precarious career? In what way are their lives supported by the Scottish government’s cultural policy in pursuing their career in the visual arts? This research will develop an understanding of what strategies they are

utilising in sustaining an arts practice and what are the available support mechanisms in the Scottish art scene in 2020?

A visual map of funding flows was initially created to identify the relationships between the Scottish government's cultural policy, Creative Scotland, local authorities and the broader art community, looking at what organisational support was available and how does funding flow through the creative ecosystems to help these practicing artists.

Research was then carried out to develop an understanding of the personal lived experiences of nine mature Scottish artists and their relationship to governmental support available and to the larger system of supporting networks and stake holders who are involved in the Scottish 'artworld'.

This understanding was built utilising a theoretical academic framework that seeks to unpick the interactions between art and power driven by the political environment in Scotland which has a dynamic cultural and artistic ecosystem. There was also an associated focus on how online social media has impacted and possibly disrupted those artistic networks.

Scottish government's cultural policy

With specific regard to the political and economic environmental context, I explored and analysed the Scottish government's cultural policy set within a broader historical cultural context in my literature review, looking in detail at the last six years of its development (2015-2020) and what its future plans are in relation to supporting visual artists working in Scotland. This will be set within the current disconnection from Europe and its evolving situation, impacted by and responding to ongoing tense negotiations between the UK government and its EU counterparts. I have also referenced broader global trends and relationships to the Scottish art scene and its attempts to further position itself as an important international centre of the arts. Finally, the overarching impact of the pandemic on the creative arts sector through the eyes of the interviewees is discussed.

Practicing Artists Interviews

I've carried out a set of semi structured interviews looking at how Scottish visual artists generate and build resourcing networks which sustain their art practice. These chosen to be interviewed were spread across a range of practicing artists, most of whom are emblematic of the forty percent who know how to make a living primarily through their artistic practice. Its notable that sixty percent of artists in Scotland are unable to make a living wage from their work (Scottish Artists Union's Membership Survey Results, 2018).

Resourcing in the arts sector is not just about the financial necessities of making a living, but includes a wider range of potential support mechanisms such as those offered by governmental & public bodies, arts organizations, galleries, curatorial practice and their own creative communities support networks. There is also a need for the arts sector to develop graduate skills in reaching out and networking with other artists, partners, customers, collectors and engaging in ongoing dialogue with the receptive audiences of their work. This examination of resourcing is situated within an investigation of broader issues around the context of artists, their

patrons, curators, artistic networks and broader communities. The relationships and potential tensions between artists and those in power who may choose to support and fund them, contributes to the changes in arts practice as it is being progressively consumed in differing ways and being more broadly located within a global capitalist system of consumption. Aspiring artists will need an understanding of this alternate world which includes navigating and negotiating the social, political and economic environments that they will find themselves being in dialogue. (Bourdieu, 1995)

Academic contextual framework

My research is framed primarily by the theories of sociologists Pierre Bourdieu, Howard S. Becker, Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi and Gregg Sholette and their key themes and concepts will be summarised in the literature review, which will then be utilised and applied to the artists interviewed using textual analysis.

Relevant to the Scottish experience, Pierre Bourdieu's theories explore social capital and cultural capital, through which the artists interact with their own supporting organisations and with those in power. (Bourdieu, 1983, 1995, 1996, Bourdieu P, Johnston R & Krizman L.D (eds), 1994) Bourdieu states that "the art business, a trade in things that have no price belongs to a class of practices in which the logic of the pre-capitalist economy lives on." (Bourdieu P & Nice R., 1980) Bourdieu believed that there was an inherent paradox between art and capitalism where it simultaneously is spiritual and other worldly but is also a part of a financially driven global art market. Becker's ideas are similar but less detailed as he believes that art and artworks are produced through a wide range of artistic output, created through 'collective action' which would include the involvement of curators, critics, gallery owners, publishers and media who support the placing of that work within a cultural context and define its meaning and value (Becker. H.S., 1974, 1976, 1982). Csikszentmihalyi's creativity model has a systemic approach with parallel ideas to both Bourdieu and Becker utilising a tri-relational dynamic of interactions between the artists their environments and a cultural framework (Csikszentmihalyi, M., 1975,1990, 1997). There is also the complementary theorizing of the art world by Greg Sholette (2011) which recognises the non-institutional artists who are 'unofficial, autonomous and self-sufficient', working independently and who are disconnected from the official art world and make up the majority of artistic practitioners. He claims that the nature of art is a very personal and political practice, which has the ability to hold those in power to account and certainly sits out with the established financially driven global art market structures. (Sholette G, 2016, 2017) Simultaneously he also wants recognition of this groups' status as untarnished true bare art within that very same official art worlds.

How do these theoretical views of artists in the art world map over onto creative art practice in Scotland in 2020? How relevant are these models, considering Scotland's unique culture, its devolved parliament and its unique supporting networks for arts practice.

Historical context

'It is a wonderful result of the progress of human culture, that at this day there come to us from Scotland rules of taste in all the arts, from epic poetry to gardening.' (Voltaire, 1764)

The Scottish arts scene is vibrant and dynamic, making a significant economic, social and cultural contribution to the country. It is embedded within the social fabric of the nation, whether it is in its art galleries and museums, or through events such as Glasgow International and the Edinburgh Art festival or in urban artworks situated on tenement walls, public spaces and through artists' open studios.

Within a broader context, the creative industries in Scotland are its second fastest growing sector behind energy in the country and are seen as having a 'distinct competitive advantage' in the international market place. Music, design, film, TV, the games industry, textiles and crafts are thriving sub-sectors of the creative industries. It is claimed these jobs are more likely to be future proof as creative minds and businesses cannot be replaced by new technologies, automation or artificial intelligence. The Scottish government's 'Creative Learning Plan' delivered through Skills Development Scotland, the national skills agency, documents their vision of a creative nation which is curious, open minded, imaginative and has the flexibility of thinking that can thrive in a rapidly changing global environment (Scottish Government, 2020). However, there are downsides to the role of the cultural sector in Scotland which are never discussed, such as it embedding low pay, gig working, insecurity of employment and having discriminatory practices at its core, with little social protection for those who wish a career in the creative industries. This will be discussed in greater detail in a later chapter. (McRobbie 2002, Banks & O'Connor 2009, Banks 2020).

The Scottish Government does not need to promote a new vision and creative aspiration for Scotland, as it endeavours to revitalize and renew its focus on developing attributes which are already culturally embedded within the nation. Scotland has been preminent in its day, grounded in historical significance through the Scottish Enlightenment and rise of philosophical and intellectual thinking, where the power of the intellect was becoming more valued in relation to class-based status. This cultural landscape was supported by visual artists who included Henry Raeburn, David Allan, Alan Ramsay, Alexander Nasmyth and Gavin Hamilton whose works infused and complemented their philosophical peer group's activities. These artists challenged the traditional art world and this can be seen through their works of portraiture, urban landscapes, geography, everyday life and the reinterpretation of classical history. (Macdonald, M. 2007)

The impact of this creative force was felt not only in Europe but also had influence on the USA's founding fathers.

"the Scots shared the values of rationalism and humanism of Voltaire, Kant, Descartes and Rousseau, enriching it with their own very British empiricism. People and ideas passed back and forth between Great Britain, continental Europe and the American colonies." (British Council, 2016)

Its history holds within it a number of iconic artists, all having international impact such as the Scottish Colourists, the Glasgow Boys and the Spook School. More recently, others have joined them through the

contemporary arts scene in the 1980's such as the New Glasgow Boys: Peter Howson, Stephen Campbell, Ken Currie, Adrian Wiszniewski and their peers, Stephen Conroy, Joan Eardley, Elizabeth Blackadder, Eduardo Paolozzi, Alison Watt, Jack Vettriano, Peter Doig, John Byrne, and more recently Douglas Gordon, Martin Boyce, Simon Starling, Claire Barclay, Jim Lambie, Kay Pallister, Graham Fagan and Charlotte Prodger who recently exhibited at Scotland + Venice 2019 during the Venice Biennale. The list of Scottish based, internationally renowned artists is impressive for such a small nation.

“The arts are one of Scotland’s proudest assets and most successful exports”

(Hassan & Mitchel, 2013)

The Scotland + Venice project was developed as part of the Scottish Governments’ strategic vision to further develop Scotland’s international profile. It has created a platform to showcase new creative artwork from a range of leading Scottish artists in its pursuit of being seen as a dynamic centre of contemporary art production within a global context. It also opens up opportunities for the involvement of Scottish arts organisations and curators in increasing their profiles and helping gain experience which can open up opportunities in developing creative networks at an international level. Supporting roles also included places for students and recent graduates to be involved in its events management and in exposing them to the cutting edge works of leading international art practitioners and networks within the global art market.

The current Scottish art scene

There are approximately two thousand Higher Education students studying in creative arts and design courses in Scotland each year and its education system has an international reputation for producing cutting edge visual artists (Higher Education Statistics Authority, 2020). They graduate into a very complex arts environment often without the knowledge and tools to navigate the business and funding environments that allow them to fully develop their creative practice into a sustaining career. It is important that they create a deeper understanding of the varied structures of support available to them in all its complexity at local, national and at international levels. The majority will not succeed in having full time careers in the industry (Sholette 2011).

In a Creative Scotland's 'Report on the Consultation - Visual Arts Sector Review, October 2016' there were concerns raised around graduating students lacking the skillset to transition into a professional career and them having particular need of core business and financial skills. However, the quality of some of the top Scottish visual art students can be clearly seen through their impact on the UK's most prestigious contemporary arts competition, the Turner Prize, highlighting the depth of talent being produced through the Scottish education system. The internationally renowned Glasgow School of Art and its students have a long association with the Turner Prize and it has produced eight Turner Prize winners overall, and had a further ten artists nominated for the award. Five winners have been graduates of its celebrated Master of Fine Art programme.

“Scotland is becoming recognised as a centre of excellence for contemporary art with increasing national and international interest in the depth and range of work that is made and presented here.” (Creative Scotland, 2016)

This sits within the context of many Scottish artists being unable to fully support themselves in developing their creative practice and choosing or needing 'portfolio careers' where they have multiple jobs inside and out with the industry to support and fund their creative work, particularly if they are freelance or self-employed. The environment that most artists find themselves in requires a number of strategies to succeed. The pressures on public funding means it currently can only support a fraction of those who apply for support. Often their creative practice is voluntary, unpaid or they often create work for less than the living wage. Is there is a growing need to develop alternative funding routes through broader networks, collaborations, partnerships and new audiences out with Scotland? Although what appears to be a weakness of resourcing in support structures could actually be framed with a positive spin. This lack of pressure to meet funders strategic requirements and peripheral targets could give opportunities for artists to create their own deeply avant-garde personal work which does not have to sit within or meet more commercial constraints, targets and impact statements. (Creative Scotland, 2016)

As part of an arts sector review in 2016 by Creative Scotland in collaboration with the Scottish Contemporary Art Network (SCAN), the Scottish Artists Union (SAU), Engage Scotland and WASPS, a comprehensive exploration of the Scottish art scene was mapped out looking at the characteristics of that sector and strategic recommendations were made in response. (Creative Scotland, 2016)

A number of challenges and opportunities were identified whilst exploring the viability of growing the Scottish arts and cultural industry into a sustainable 'international centre of excellence'. They identified that the sector was inadequately funded and needed much more public and private support to grow, and believed that there was a need for long term strategic planning and development of connections, both at home and more importantly internationally.

Since then two further sector reports have been published by the Scottish government's Culture, Tourism, Europe and External Affairs Committee, the first published in December 2019 which looked into the future of arts funding and a document responding to it, 'A Culture Strategy for Scotland' was published in February 2020.

There is a recognition that Scottish artists are highly qualified, supportive, knowledgeable and outward looking. They are open to sharing and collaborating with their peers. Self-organized artist run ventures are seen as particularly important to the sector. They help form supportive, dynamic and cohesive groups and communities of artists offering collaborative opportunities, space for critical dialogue and help with networking.

The Creative Scotland report also was of the opinion that government funding should be utilized in supporting visual artistic work of 'quality' and that there were too many artists competing for the available supporting resources. They believed that much of the work was not of a high enough standard, although was no criteria given as to what that actually meant nor who specifically would make that decision. They believed that the 'quality of output' was much more important than quantity. They also have instrumentalised the art process by focusing specifically on the impact of the artwork. Who is given the responsibility to be the arbiter of defining what is creative art and who has been given the mandate to decide on the nature of what high art should be and whether artists are given government funded support? Equally important, where is the transparency around those funding decisions and who if anyone is held accountable for those choices? Definitions of quality and taste are deemed indicators of class and status and are utilised by those in power to sustain their privileges and the status quo. They are used as acts of symbolic violence.

"Partners and funders need to be more focussed on the quality and impacts of the work that the sector is generating rather than being overly prescriptive about the quantity of outputs and the pace of delivery"
(Creative Scotland, 2016)

There are historic precedents for this process going back to Socrates, who pledges in Plato's Book 'Ten of the Republic' (375 BC), a treatise on justice and the city state, regarding 'imitative poets and artists whose very labor deceives and seduces citizens through ruse and clever mimicry'. Only if the artists' work is in some way useful to the state will they be permitted citizenship of his republic, if not they will be kept at a distance.

Will government funded support of art production ever be allowed to be controversial, or anti-governmental or used where the artistic practice is pushing the boundaries of taste and decency? How does the bureaucracy and those serving it deal with these propositions of extreme art or with experimental artists who work on the margins or beyond that of their own comfort levels when financial decisions are being made? What of activist art which challenges and provokes the status quo, often being used as a tool against government repression?

Artists reflect the world back at us, and are in the business of provoking and disrupting contemporary cultural practice.

“I get censored four or five times a year': Paul McCarthy, art's virtuoso of vile, who is making a living out of his notoriety.“ (Frankel, 2020)

Gender balance of artists in Scotland

There are interesting statistics around gender balances in the Scottish art scene where sixty eight percent of artists working in the creative arts are women and only one third being men (Visual Arts in Scotland, 2015, p31). Of staff supported by Creative Scotland's regularly funded visual arts organisations, women make up approximately two thirds of employees and their role in management is fifty eight percent within the sector. Even though men are in the minority, their income is forty five percent more than their female counterparts, however women in full time employment earned fifty six percent more than their male counterparts. (Blanche, 2015)

Location of artists in Scotland

Half of the artist members of the Scottish Artists Union live in the central belt, with Glasgow at 30% and Edinburgh 20%. The highlands, Dumfries & Galloway, Fife, Aberdeenshire and the Borders all had approximately five percent each and much smaller numbers are dotted around Ayrshire, Perthshire, Dundee, the Outer Hebrides, Orkney and Shetland (Blanche, 2015, p3)

Methodology

Aims and Objectives

The overall aim of this research is to identify the supporting networks, successful strategies and business models of mature Scottish visual artists through which training material could be developed in helping support early career artists in their understanding of the relationship between artists and the political power structures in Scotland. It is important to understand the environment they will be working in, and responding to it through their personal relationship to the dominant culture, politics and capitalist ideologies that influence the paths and success of their careers.

To answer the key research problem, I have pursued three sequential and associated areas of study. That includes a combination of desk research and semi structured qualitative interviews

-Focused literature review of key art theorists exploring the nature of art and power

-Extensive desk research driven by a comprehensive literature review has allowed me to identify key theorists who philosophise about the nature of art and its relationship to power providing insights into the Scottish artistic experience and art world ecosystem. Of the extensive historic theorising around the nature of art several key theorists were identified as being most useful in understanding the nature of the Scottish art world. Bourdieu, Becker, Csikszentmihalyi, and Sholette explore the realities of art production set within the context of politics, culture, the global art market place and the capitalist system of consumption. Bourdieu in particular recognises and explains the relationships between the artists and those in power who control resources and opportunities, offering a theoretical framework to base this research around.

-A review of documents exploring the nature of culture, its use by the Scottish Government as a strategic tool and its ongoing development of its cultural policy

This research highlights the value of culture to a society and how it can be utilised by groups as a political device to achieve certain outcomes. It seeks to understand and map key relationships in the development of the Scottish government's evolving cultural policy proposals and their impact on the artistic community. It will also involve the textual analysis of various publicly available cultural policy texts, conversations and documentation over the last 6 years (2015-2020) looking into key stake holder interactions over that period and their connections to other cultural support organisations, followed by analysis and critique of the data collected. It will also examine the relationship between the Scottish government, Creative Scotland and local authorities in delivery of cultural objectives and their resourcing of support for visual artists.

-Series of nine visual artist interviews

One possible rationale for the choice of potential artist interviewees being chosen considers the differing types of visual artists working in Scotland through a lens specifically designed around the criteria of success and age.

- Superstar artists

- Successful internationally exhibiting artists
- Mature artists who have made a basic living through their practice, aged 35+.
- Young artists seeking a professional foothold (aged 25-35) before greater relationship responsibilities and need for more secure employment become the primary focus
- Young graduating artist sjust starting out on their career (22-25)

Although all artistic groupings defined above have interesting and unique positions, relationships and perspectives on the artworld, they are all worthy of research projects around their practice and indicators of success in their own right. Issues around the impact of class, sexism, racism, regions and migration impacting the artists success would also have been interesting routes to explore further, as would the role of activist art, particularly focussing on issues addressing global warming, destruction of the planet and the threats to society by global and national political structures and capitalism.

I have chosen to interview more mature visual artists (35 years +) who have sustained their art practice and made a basic artistic living throughout their careers. Their valuable life experiences and maturity of working in this area will likely bring novel ways of making a living, generating pathways to success and help in navigatating themselves through a creative career. This group was most easily contactable through arts organisations that are part of their supporting networks.

They will also be the most likely to have most experiences of applying for support and funding and will be likely to understand the strategies around success and the roots to failure in trying to access government, Creative Scotland or local authority support. Their experiences are likely to be most valuable to up and coming graduating visual artists looking to sustain themselves whilst developing an artistic career. These mature visual artists also will have had the greatest opportunities to develop the broadest networks of support and relationships with funding bodies, gallerists, patrons, customers and the broader institutional powers of the artworld and politics which is the essence of this thesis.

Young graduating artists and those in the early stages of their career are unlikely to be suitable candidates to understand the Scottish artworld and power structures, as they would have minimal relative expertise in having built strategies for sustainability, submission of funding applications, nor would they likely to have built up supporting-networks inside and outside of the art world that would be of support to them. Funders and arts institutions are looking for excellence, expertise and artistic longevity as precursors for membership of their societies, which is something young artists rarely can supply.

Those who are successfully established and internationally recognised visual artists and the even more successful superstars would certainly be an interesting group to study but their successes are unlikely to be easily replicated by arts graduates as there is only a small percentage of all artists who fit into that category and there are too many variables in understanding why they met that criteria. There may also be a need for the artist to be discovered by a powerful gallerist or mentor who would promote them and contribute to their success. It also would be more challenging to access their time as they have agents, business advisors and gatekeepers who keep them at arms-length from researchers and journalists unless it directly contributes to enhancing their profile.

Choice of artists

My initial interest was in Scottish visual artists who have been able to support themselves and be self-sustaining as practicing artists. In my communications with Troon art club, an email was sent out on my behalf to sixteen artists, looking for participants who would take part in my semi-structured interviews and four agreed to this. Another eight artists were invited through personal contacts. It became clear that my early assumptions around what artistic careers would be like were too simplistic and bore little relationship to the actual lives of many artists in Scotland and to those who were being interviewed. In particular it was challenging to find artists who have developed life-long full time careers without the need for alternative income streams.

A small group of interviewees were identified as having been able to make a living out of their arts practice. Several had started on a path of successful art market participation and then chosen to step back from it for a number of reasons, and others had alternative sources of income that supported them. Several received no income from their art practice at all and relied on other income streams.

The nine mature visual artists were interviewed and the recorded content was initially transcribed for this research project initially using Otter.ai. which is an AI based transcription service. A second stage of review was carried out to remove any transcription errors, which were many, as the system was not fully conversant with Scottish accents and in particular with accents from the West of Scotland. At its conclusion all data was wiped from Otter's servers.

Interview Method

Interviews with Scottish visual artists utilised an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) approach. This is a qualitative interview method which is a phenomenological and hermeneutic means of enquiry, working with a small number of chosen interviewees who can supply deep reflections of collective experience around the chosen research area (Smith 1996, Smith et al, 2009, Hefferon & Gil-Rodriguez, 2011). Since the production of art is a socially constructed experience, as will be discussed in the literature review, those interview participants are offering their personalised accounts located within their own cultural setting. They offer a homogeneous sampling of common reference points and a shared perspective.

“The participant’s ‘lived experience’ is coupled with a subjective and reflective process of interpretation, in which the analyst explicitly enters into the research process.” (Reid K, Flowers P, Larkins 2005)

Such is the small sample size, it is not possible to draw any firm conclusions with regard to the overall Scottish arts support network, but nevertheless this paper seeks to capture and map some initial key themes that could be valuable in understanding the development of cultural policy in Scotland. This research gives the opportunity to look in detail into a group of mature Scottish artists and gives an insight into the issues they have had to negotiate over their careers and in their daily lives. The research seeks to identify supporting arts institutions and organisations that have given a sense of support and community around the often isolating, creative

environment. It also explores these artists' views on the Scottish government's cultural policy and its support for their creative activities.

Bias

I acknowledge my preconceptions and cognitive bias brought into the exploration of this field where I had made a number of assumptions going into this project. I assumed that a number of artists had spent their lives in full time careers and those able to do this had been able to make a viable living. I also assumed that the Government's cultural policy would have a limited impact on artists' lives in Scotland and also believed that Creative Scotland's agenda was failing in its role as a supporting organisation for individual artists. Bonnar (2014) and Hassan & Mitchel (2013) discuss the key issues around that organisation's inception and the governments' failed attempts to create a common definition of 'culture' and strategic direction. I was also aware that I was learning progressively through this interview process and there was constant change in my perceptions of artistic careers and their relationships to power. This was particularly around that fluid nature of artists moving in and out of their full-time artistic practice due to personal circumstances. I also was progressively informed by the interview process itself and tuned in to collective issues that the interviewees progressively raised, such as the impact of gender bias and 'symbolic violence' on female artists.

“the researcher and the text he or she produces are part of their environment, part of the world, on which they have an impact and which influences them in turn.” (Hannula M, 2004, p168)

Ethics

Prior to the interview process taking place, a participants information sheet, topic guide and a standard UWS consent form were submitted to the UWS internal ethics committee for approval before proceeding.

These three documents were sent out to each interviewee explaining what the research project was about and supplying a list of questions that would be the basis of discussions prior to any agreement being made to support the interviewer. The participants were made aware that they could chose to withdraw from the research process at any point up until the final draft of this document concluding at the end of January 2021.

After the interviews had taken place, the conversations were transcribed and supplied to each participant offering them the opportunity to review the material and asking for any content they were not comfortable with to be deleted or anonymised and when they were happy with the transcript to return a signed copy of the approval documentation.

Participants were not anonymised in the study as their personal stories would have easily identified them to anyone interested. Due to the inclusion of filmed documentary excerpts where the participants discuss key issues on camera around common themes also makes the task of anonymising the participants problematic.

The Participants

All participants were contacted through my broad social network. The locations of the participants are spread across Scotland, from the north, south, east and west coast of the country, with participants located in Glasgow, Edinburgh, East Linton, Dundee, Tain, Lockerbie, Monkton and Irvine. The sample of participants is predominately middle aged and older, having experience of managing and understanding the Scottish art world. The gender of participants was seven females and two males and there was no interest or benefit in equalising this. They are collectively a homogenous group, although there was no attempt to find an ethnic mix within what is a relatively small cohort of participants. The chosen group of artists also occupy a range of positions and status in the art world.

The participants were invited to discuss their artistic careers focussing on several areas; their upbringing, artistic education and the broad range of external relationships with institutions, collaborators, funders, critics and buyers of their creative work. They were asked to discuss any government, Creative Scotland or local authority support and if they have been involved in developing any funding bids. The opportunity to discuss Brexit and Covid's impact on them was also included. Although they were given an information sheet of key questions, the interviews were open ended and lasted between forty minutes and one and a half hours.

Prior to any release of personal data obtained at the interview, participants were supplied with verbatim transcripts of their interviews for them to authorise its use and they could edit or delete content prior to analysis. A deadline for changes and authorisation of data release of content was agreed beforehand. (circa January 2021)

The intention was to interview artist practitioners who were making a living through their art practice and to explore how they are able to develop their career in relationship to their understanding of the networks, power structures, dominant hierarchies and capitalist ideologies that impact them and their artistic status within them.

The analysis of the transcripts looked for common themes, patterns of shared experience, novel ideas and useful advice. Once the data had been transcribed and analysed, comparisons with artists' relationships to the ideas of the key arts theorists were explored and successful career strategies and personal networks that these artists have utilised were identified. Groupings of similar strategies were pulled together and from that an analysis was carried out to see if they could be brought together cohesively into written content, visual maps and documentary footage for use by graduating art students, artists and policy makers in their understanding of the mature artists' working landscapes, their relationships and their survival strategies. This would be useful in preparing young artists more fully in understanding, supporting and managing their careers within the creative arts industry, focussing on their personal and business development in the broadest of senses.

Analysis

The transcripts were textually analysed for common 'themes' connecting the artists' relationships to key theoretical and philosophical positions of Bourdieu, Becker, Csikszentmihalyi and Sholette highlighted in the literature review, and their relationship to support networks, arts institutions and government cultural policy.

The analysis sheet below was used to identify the relationships between interviewees & theoretical key themes that are defined in the detailed analysis of the positions of the key theorists discussed in the literature review.

Pierre Bourdieu

Pure v bourgeoisie & subordinate

Habitus

Field

Symbolic goods

Signification v merchandise

Economic capital

Social Capital

Embodied state

Objectified state

Institutionalised state

Cultural capital

Symbolic violence

New v status quo

Avant-garde v consecrated

the cultural power system

the king maker - who can be called an artist

Support of the critic, and being worthy of legitimate discourse

heteronomous v autonomous principles

'high end' production v 'mass audience' appeal

bourgeois art v lowlier industrial art

large-scale production v niche output

Niche - consecrated and the avant-garde

Legitimacy

autonomous and self-sufficient

'bourgeois' taste

'mass audience'

Cultural workers solidarity with culturally dominated

Dealers' protégé

Artists

BG, AB, KD, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

KD, LR

BG, AB, KD, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, DR, SB, LR

BG, KD, KM, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, SB, LR

AB, KD, BE, DR, SB, LR

AB, SB, KD, KM, BE, DR, SB

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, DR, IS, SB

BG, AB, KD, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

AB, AB, KD, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

AB, KD, KM, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, DR, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, BE, DR, SB, LR

BG, AB, BE, DR, IS

SB, LR

Howard S Becker

artistic practice is through consensual negotiation

'collective action'

market driven consumable artifact built on the human interactions

guilds and academies

reputational value of artists directly equals financial value.

Who decides what the standards and rules of the art world are?

definition of art is challenged by new artists

model as a way of understanding the social relationships of art production

BG, KD, BE, DR, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

AB, AB, KD, BE, DR, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, SB, LR

AB, KD, BE, DR, SB, LR

AB, KD, KM, LR

AB

Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi

three dynamic and interactive elements

artist bringing creative skills and crafts

a clear domain of knowledge within a cultural context

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, DR, IS, SB, LR

BG, AB, KD, KM, BE, SB, LR

integrity judged by a group of authoritative experts	BG, AB, KD, KM, SB, LR
success of creative artists is often determined by chance events	BG, AB, DR, (IS), SB
symbolic nature of the domain identifying what is deemed elite art	BG, KD, DR, SB, LR
The new needs to be appropriately different to the old	LR
relationship between creativity and persuasion	KD, BE

Greg Sholette

'creative dark matter'	KM
stripping away outdated definitions of 'high art'	AB, LR
deep humanist acts of artistic cultural practice, defined as 'bare art'	BG, AB, KD, KM, SB, LR
High art's exceptional status, struggles to sustain that spiritual position	
art and culture progressively appropriated and embroiled in the political dark dealings of businesses and nation states	
divest cultural activities from inappropriate capitalist ventures	
unsuccessful artists propping up the small elite of successful artists	KM, DR
the uneconomic production and over supply of arts graduates	
development of digital communications technologies	BG, AB, KD, BE, DR, IS, LR
jobs to support their creative endeavors in a gig economy	AB, KM, DR, IS, LR
production process of digital communications technologies including network providers	
evolving production processes of the contemporary art world and those who control who is chosen and who are rejected	AB, KD, KM, LR

Thematic analysis was carried out on the transcriptions utilising the table of key theoretical concepts mentioned above which were cross referred to the texts whilst analysing the transcripts, looking to identify common relevant material against each identified concept systematically (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 77–101).

Utilising the transcriptions of the interviews, common themes were identified through the use of thematic analysis (Galvin 2015) and then edited into manageable coherent chunks. Once the themes were identified, the most interesting and useful interview material was extracted and made into video sequences and grouped into broader shared themes.

Video based elements

As part of the development of teaching material for graduating art students using visual clips to communicate impactful ideas, a group of short documentaries have been produced. These highlight key aspects of the lives and stories of the visual artists taken from the interview stage and the key findings of the research process have been captured through that audio-visual medium.

Challenges around interviewing over the internet included bandwidth and quality issues have been accepted due to issues of participant access due to the Covid Pandemic, since no face to face interviewing could take place for seven out of the nine participants.

The visual elements of the thesis, contain a series of eleven documentary clips which were produced, highlighting the findings of the research process. The themes of the documentaries aligned with three key areas of interest; successful navigation of funding resources, being discovered by artworld mentors and the use of symbolic violence against disempowered groups.

It has been broken down in this way to allow for those interested in accessing chunks of information as the total time of all the content is one hour thirty five minutes. This will be an effective tool for teaching the key messages taken from the interviews.

The researcher interviewed two of the artists initially in their art studios using an Apple I-Phone and the rest latterly on Zoom, when the Covid pandemic made personal visits unsafe. A number of technical problems with online interviewing occurred due to aspects of Zoom's recording processes whilst interviewing and with internet bandwidth challenges, primarily impacting video quality, and in one case bandwidth problems forced the interview to be switched half way through to solely audio. Editing of the material was a challenge, as using online content made it difficult at times to make smooth transitions between sections possible, and quality levels were often poor.

As mentioned earlier, as part of the interview pack, questions had been sent prior to the interview to the artists, so they understood the subjects to be discussed, but due to the informal approach to questioning, additional useful content was offered by them about their creative lives. After the early interviews, the responses to the questions and new themes explored informed new questions to be asked in the later interviews, developing in an iterative manner. Utilising the transcriptions of the artist interviews, the interviewer then took a thematic analytical approach (Galvin 2015) allowing common themes to be identified from the material being reviewed.

It was important to the researcher that the artists voices should be heard within a visual medium and that their personal stories were told. There is always the risk that artists will tell the stories they want to tell in front of the camera, reflecting how the participants want to be represented (Murthy 2008, p. 843). This has to be accepted as the interviewee will decide what they want to reveal and how they want to be perceived. There was no way to verify much of the content as it was often based on personal accounts.

“An ethnography cannot give us a glimpse of reality that resides beyond the story told within the ethnography; the story is all.” (Kent, T. 1993, p. 67)

Due to the nature of the interviews which were interactive discussions, it was difficult to denaturalize the videos whilst being edited due to overlapping conversations and difficulty in cutting pauses and repetitions out. Topics were open ended and themes not originally in the questionnaire were identified after the transcription process such as issues around symbolic violence, class and gender. Thematic analysis was carried out on the transcriptions utilising a table of key theoretical concepts which was cross referred to during the re-reading of the transcripts, identifying common relevant material against each concept systematically (Braun V. & Clarke V. 2006 pp. 77–101). This was solely carried out by the author.

The documentaries submitted are in three groupings of three to four topics with interview material relating to key themes: Csikszentmihalyi's theories connecting cultural mentors to artistic success, Bourdieu's theories around 'symbolic violence' and its relationship to gender-based issues and Scottish Government cultural policy and experiences of artists accessing funding and support networks. They are all of differing lengths as the artists involved often had differing experiences and issues were not common. Also, as the interviews were developing more time was offered in exploring some of these topics with later interviewees.

- Government cultural policy and experiences of artists accessing funding and support networks
 - Louise Ritchie - Funding & Support Networks 12:48 <https://youtu.be/avFIIsWUIKTI>
 - Wide ranging funding support from a variety of sources in Scotland
 - Alison Bell - Funding & Support Networks 25:09 <https://youtu.be/-gIsXC4Wqxs>
 - Wide ranging funding support from a variety of sources in Scotland
 - Kate Downie - Funding & Support Networks 13:03 <https://youtu.be/Dn1hdTtUoJM>
 - Funding support from a variety of sources in Scotland and abroad
 - Bryan Evans - Entrepreneurial approach avoiding engaging with funding & support networks 14:34 <https://youtu.be/TFONW4ckOiQ>
 - Independent path, choosing not to apply for any funding support from institutions

- Csikszentmihalyi's theories connecting cultural mentors to artistic success
 - David Reid – Mentor Opens Doors 15:47 <https://youtu.be/1oruj3yjf-0>
 - Mentoring support from local authority arts officers in taking first steps
 - Alison Bell – Mentor Opens Doors 3:42. <https://youtu.be/IvYdvgMZ3dU>
 - support from local authority arts officers expanding her horizons
 - Shona Barr – Mentor Opens Doors 5:47 <https://youtu.be/GwDyxZMDXqs>
 - Ongoing relationship and support from gallery owner
 - Inge Smith – Mentors Open Doors 8:16 <https://youtu.be/rI4YcmO7IK8>
 - Support from local authority arts officers to expand network

- Bourdieu's theories around 'symbolic violence' and its relationship to gender-based issues
 - Kate Downie – Symbolic Violence 3:09. <https://youtu.be/IB7oTmF4YEEY>
 - Systemic sexist policies towards working mothers
 - Karen Monaghan – Symbolic Violence 0:58. <https://youtu.be/oOdTTArTw7Y>
 - Educational institutions lay down rules disadvantaging women
 - Bella Green – Symbolic Violence 3:10. <https://youtu.be/EHmFxsDpneU>
 - Life experiences of subtle sexism in the art world

Future research

Future research could focus on the range of alternate sub-groups that could be of interest, such as the younger age group of artists in their late twenties and thirties, or in approaching highly successful Scottish artists, such as the New Glasgow Boys who graduated from GSA ,who were part of the authors cohort in 1982. Opportunities could be found to interview those artists who are members of the art institutions in Scotland with regard to how

useful these institutions are in supporting artists' careers and perhaps there would be value in looking at a more diverse ethnic group of artists and their experiences of living in Scotland could also prove illuminating.

Literature Review

Introduction

This literature review will be divided primarily into two parts; firstly, a theoretical review of literature looking at key philosophers and theoreticians explorations of dynamic relationships between power and art over the centuries, and secondly a focussed review of the Scottish government's developing cultural policy over the last six years, looking its relationship with Creative Scotland through which it engages directly with the cultural arts sector and also at Local Authority support for culture. The examination of cultural policy will be set within a review of the function of culture, what constitutes cultural activity and its relationship to politics and power. Culture can be interpreted as having an anthropological social meaning which focusses on the values, behaviours, practices and creative artifacts through which a society expresses itself.

It will conclude with an understanding of the relationship between these intellectual theories exploring and explaining this field of art and cultural production and seek to understand the how they relate to the practices embedded in the Scottish government and allied agencies' developing cultural arts policy. This material will underpin the focus of the interviews of the group of mature Scottish artists in this thesis.

“If power were never anything but repressive, if it never did anything but to say no, do you really think one would be brought to obey it? What makes power hold good, what makes it accepted, is simply the fact that it doesn't only weigh on us as a force that says no, but that it traverses and produces things, it induces pleasure, forms knowledge, produces discourse. It needs to be considered as a productive network which runs through the whole social body, much more than as a negative instance whose function is repression.”

(Foucault, 1980, p. 119)

In the examination of theoretical writing around the dynamics of art and its relationship to power, what is particularly apparent within the social networks of artistic and creative practitioners is that often there is a mystery around which artists are chosen to be gifted with success and stardom and why. Those vying for governmental funding support often are at a loss in understanding the criteria around success and what appears to be an opaque system of decision making on their funding bids. However, some artists who have been involved in supporting the process of allocating granting funding to applicants have developed a clearer understanding of the awarding system and what is needed to meet its requirements.

There are still notions of artists needing to suffer for their art and have lives submerged in poverty and turmoil to generate the powerful reflections that resonate with other's lives through their artwork. This conflicts with the vast sums of money that the global arts economy generates and the issues of art production being more than just an occupation and it having a spiritual dimension that can be damaged through its engagement with real world economics. There needs to be the illusion that the artist is totally detached from the money-making process and unsullied by its capitalistic corrupting ways. (Bourdieu, 1983)

“should grief and penury be built into art patronage, so the marketable wares created under those limiting circumstances are folded into the equation of the work's value in the marketplace in years and eras to

come. When all attention is withdrawn from artists, they have always been mad enough to do it anyway, so what's the fuss? Can't they depend on enlightened philanthropy when available – and look else-where when it isn't? Or can't they depend on the marketplace – which is to say design the art itself for the marketplace – and hope the target will not move before their work is completed? Or can't they rely on government support and trust to chance or the law of averages that their work will prove at least equal to the dollar value of the support? Such are a few of the questions, art advocacy raises”

(Morrison, 2019, p. 65)

The tension exists between the avant-garde artists who generate artworks independently of the market and who are constantly struggling to generate the financial resources to continue with their practice and with those artists who watch the market for signs of trends and patterns signifying what the flavours of the month will be. These entrepreneurial artists try to financially capitalize on that knowledge. Then there is the final group who are in tenure, employed through the state or having a benefactor's support, who have to balance their creative outputs with what their patrons require as a return on their investment of trust in their artistic skills and endeavours.

“All good art is political. There is none that isn't. And the ones that try hard not to be political are political by saying, we love the status quo” (Nance, K. 2008)

What are the theoretical contexts surrounding the nature of art, artistic production and supporting networks?

In order to identify relevant art theories addressing the artistic relationships and supporting networks, a broad literature review of key artistic philosophical and theoretical texts was carried out. Literature, seminal works and journal articles were sourced and through this an understanding of the changing focus and evolution over the decades around the theorising of art practice was gained.

Philosophical approaches to theorising around art

There appear to be four primary philosophical approaches to theorising around art, including its final apparent integration into the broader creative and cultural industries. The first philosophical theories look to explain the essence and concept of what art is through attempts at formulating definitions centring around taste and beauty. Secondly there are the theories proposing that artworks have the capacity to communicate meaning directly to their audience in some mysterious way. The third approach to arts understanding was that it is part of a social, hierarchical and historical construct which is contextually understood.

“the only way we can hope to reach a real knowledge of art, to go deeper into the specificity of the work of art, to know the mechanisms which produce the 'aesthetic effect', is precisely to spend a long time and pay the greatest attention to the 'basic principles of Marxism’”. (Althusser, 1966, p. 208)

Finally, the fourth approach has art politically subsumed into a cluster of creative activities called the ‘creative and cultural industries’ which the UK government embraced as a compelling narrative to promote economic growth in a post-industrial society and for it to make a contribution to the knowledge economy. For the last thirty years researchers and theorists have been trying to make meaning of arts relationship to broader cultural dynamics set within a neo-liberal agenda (McRobbie 2002, Banks & O’Connor 2009, Banks 2020). However, this is contested as even the Scottish Government has identified that Arts and Culture employment is distinct from the Creative Industries jobs market (CTEEAC, 2019, p. 52).

The aesthetics of art

Arts value to society has been debated by philosophers since Plato’s Republic, where he showed utter disregard for the production of artistic works due to their imitative nature. He believed that real objects in the world were the true reality and were available to be examined directly if you wished to gain any true knowledge from them.

Giorgio Vasary's writings of ‘The Lives of the Most Eminent Sculptors, Painters, and Architects’ in 1568 during the Italian Renaissance explored not only art history but the lives of local artists in Florence, Tuscany and Venice. He was also interested the artists’ creativity and working practices and their business relationships with their patrons and benefactors. He identified that talent was not enough for artists to thrive as they also needed to have perseverance to be successful. In a way this current research mirrors Vasary’s activities through an in-depth exploration of the working lives of artists and their supporting networks six hundred years later.

Building on this, art theorists since the writing of David Hume in the 1700's have progressively developed their understandings around the aura of the artist, the nature of art, its production, its relationship to those viewing it and its cultural context set within a historical canon of work. Some early seminal philosophers and theorists working in this field primarily focussed on defining the essence of the artwork itself, and around the creative production of works of significant beauty and aesthetics, viewed through the lens of a memetic and imitative response to the world, which is reflecting the beauty of the world back at society through its sculptures and paintings.

Hume's 18th century treatise 'Of the Standard of Taste' (1757) focusses specifically on the quality of the artwork and the inherent beauty and form within it that was clearly understood by those viewers who had the education, intellectual capacity and developed taste to appreciate it. Taste is a reoccurring theme in the understanding and appreciation of art where perceptions of what is defined as tasteful have changed over the centuries. Like style, taste appears mutable, but it is set within a historical background of elite culture, education and status, where there is a historical appreciation often grounded in the arts and culture of ancient Greece and the Italian Renaissance. This subject will be developed further later in the literature review.

Immanuel Kant's 'Critique of the Power of Judgment' in 1790 (1791) explored the aesthetics and judgement in art appreciation relating to the beautiful, the sublime and the genius of the artists who were imbued with messiah like qualities, who were the producers of works of beauty that had universal appreciation. He highlights the sublime, imaginative, creative genius that was embedded within each piece of artwork and believed that there was a collective inter-subjectivity around judgements of taste & beauty within an audience viewing these artefacts. He proposed that a specific type of disinterested pleasure was gained by an audience in their engagement with the beauty contained within an artwork which was centred on mass appreciation and universal feelings. Georg Hegel's 'Philosophy of Art' (1826) also reflected on truth and beauty within the arts, defining it as 'the beautiful ideal'. This ideal explored three stages of artistic development; symbolic, classical and Romantic art, which supported his elaboration of the primary definitions and historical categorisations of types of art.

With the dramatic changes during the European Reformation, religious beliefs became more personalised for many and the production of religious iconic works of art no longer were the primary focus of art output. Opportunities for artists to gain patronage from their historic religious benefactors in northern Europe were reduced. Some artists became more focussed on recording landscapes and aspects of secular communities in rural life such as in the Dutch Golden Age paintings which celebrated the increase in wealth of the Dutch and Flemish merchant classes.

Emotionalism: Audience reception of artworks

Art theory progressively became more interested in the exploration of relations between the artwork and its reception and interpretation by an audience and how the artwork communicated its meaning to them.

“Iconic art brings together social groupings within ritual, ceremonies & public displays, and with it social cohesion and personal security” (Dissanayake, 1988).

In Leo Tolstoy’s ‘Expression theory’, (1899) he explores how art directly transmits feelings that are received by the audience. Freud’s also believed that the artists convey their unconscious sublimated feelings, desires and emotions to the viewer through their artwork in his ‘Interpretation of Dreams’, (1900, 2010). Advanced ‘Expression’ theorists; such as RG Collingwood (1971), Benedetto Croce (1967) and Susanne Langer’s Representational Symbolism (1957), also explored how artists communicated their feelings, belief systems and ideas through their art. They believe the artwork conveyed symbolic images transmitted through the artists’ subjective realities to the audience viewing their work.

John Dewey’s ‘Cognitive theory’ (1934) proposed that the audience needs to be educated in art’s contextual and historic language to have appreciation for it and he believed that art was central to the understanding of any culture. This idea was taken further by Nelson Goodman (1969), who expanded on Dewey’s views, believing art was culturally situated and has the capacity to expand our understanding of the world and it having an ability to transform our perceptions. In Richard L. Anderson’s ‘Calliope’s Sisters’ (1990) ten differing cultures are compared and contrasted in their definition and appreciation of aesthetics and art, with non-western Euro-centric art having the most widely differing structural criteria in art production, understanding and context from the others.

Marxist theory explores political and cultural power structures and the institutional elites who have privileged positions within them. Within Marxist theory is the idea that art has a socio-economic function, but also has a philosophical aesthetic too (Graham G, 1997). Since art reflects a society and a time period, it is ideological because it is formed through imagination and not empirical enquiry, but in doing so it exposes truths about capitalism. Marxist theory bridges the social and aesthetic values of art and sees them as potential tools for radical political change. When imitative or abstract art is developed without social or political content it cannot be revolutionary as it represents things in a familiar way, thereby sustaining the status quo. Only jarring and disturbing types of art could open up new perceptions for its audience.

A structuralist model identifies Marx’s two complementary structures; the base structure which holds the economic and financial aspects of society and the superstructure containing the customs, culture entertainment and the arts which are responsive to the base structure. Art is forced to exchange its symbolic value for fiat currencies which ultimately are dependent on the economic system. Artists who wish to produce their own work, do not want to serve the needs of the market and do not want their art to be commoditised and a communist society would solve that problem (Eagleton 1990, p. 208). Good art, which contributes to the betterment of human kind, could only come from a communist state where all outdated and controlling institutions had been removed (Fischer E.P. 1963).

Critical and social theorists such as Lukács (1970), Gramsci (Litowitz, 2000) and those of the Neo-Marxist Frankfurt School looked to understand and expose the hidden class, political and power structures functioning within society. They explored how social groups use these structures to gain privilege and advantage over others

through an ideological dominance and identified how cultural and legal institutions support and legitimise those positions in society.

Among the Frankfurt School theorists, Adorno and Horkheimer examined mass culture and believed that the culture industries habituate the masses into accepting the dominant ideology.

“In reality, a cycle of manipulation and retroactive need is unifying the system ever more tightly. What is not mentioned is that the basis on which technology is gaining power over society is the power of those whose economic position in society is strongest.” (Adorno & Horkheimer, 2002, p. 42)

Art historian Heinrich Wölfflin’s ‘Classic Art’ (1899) and ‘Principles of Art History’ (1929) set a methodological framework for modernist art theorists by identifying the core attributes and fundamental categories embedded within works of art. His work identifying five pairs of concepts relating to the style and pictorial organisation in an artwork was designed to allow comparative analysis of art spanning any historical period. Aspects of linear structure, use of paint, 2&3D effects, lines of motion, coherence and clarity allowed for a thorough analysis of an artwork. He believed that contextual and cultural references about the work and information about the artists was of secondary importance in his critique (Ferne, 1995, p. 140-142).

Modernist art theorists such as Clive Bell, who was part of the British Bloomsbury group, believed that art had a universal resonance and language. Bell’s essay on aesthetics (1914) argued that artworks were carriers of meaning which elicit differing aesthetic emotions being generated by a type of artistic ‘significant form’ and believed that unique combinations of line and colour could evoke aesthetically moving, emotional feelings from artwork that everyone could experience. In Roger Fry’s theorising around ‘Formalism’ (1914), he also developed his work believed that colour, shape, line, form, space and texture were part of a universal language of two dimensional paintings.

The use of art in government propaganda

Michael Pearce (2022) in ‘The Art of Propaganda’ explores how American foreign policy objectives in the early 1940’s embodied art as a propaganda tool, initially through the Federal Art Projects, which were developed in response to the growing threat from Nazi Germany and Soviet Russia. It was decided that American art should be radically different to the totalitarian social avant-garde realist art of their adversaries. Their American art should represent itself as individualistic and free, including it ironically being ‘free’ from government intervention.

The German Nationalist Socialist and Soviet communist governments utilised visual culture as a way of promoting their ideals, and Lenin and Stalin were both supporters of proletariat art. The Nazis used an idealised figurative art as a vehicle for their extreme form of national proletarianism. Artwork that did not conform was defined as degenerative art and removed from public view. They also encompassed a range of cultural mediums in their communications strategy including theatre, staged performances, film, graphic design and fashion.

With the founding of the Peoples Republic of China in 1949, Mao Zedong also embraced culture as a propaganda tool of government and initially adopted the Soviets “social realism” art style promoting communist ideals until the Cultural Revolution, where artists were required to adopt an alternate style called “revolutionary romanticism”.

“In the world today all culture, all literature and art belong to definite classes and are geared to definite political lines. There is in fact no such thing as art for art's sake, art that stands above classes, art that is detached from or independent of politics. Proletarian literature and art are part of the whole proletarian revolutionary cause; they are, as Lenin said, cogs and wheels in the whole revolutionary machine.”

(Mao Zedong, 1942, p. 86)

The Americans in response promoted and supported the avant-garde of abstract and modern art ‘representing individualistic Western freedom’. The American press, in particular a German refugee Dr. Lion Feuchtwanger, who was a journalist, writer and playwright ridiculed totalitarian art as romantic kitsch. Clement Greenberg who was regarded as one of the most influential art historians and critics was a supporter of Feuchtwanger and developed his ideas in his seminal essay “Avant-garde and Kitsch’ (1939) where he espouses the differences between high and low populist art. He became an art critic for ‘The Nation’ where he championed the work of abstract expressionist, Jackson Pollock. American avant-garde artists continued to push the boundaries of artistic practice whilst the critics promoted the individual genius of these artists who were producing art exclusively for the elite bourgeois art market in the US. Greenberg defined Kitsch as being parasitic, a rehash and simulation of high culture, characterised by an insensitivity to its core values. Kitsch is utilised by class and those in power as a tool of fascism and embodied symbolic violence, in a form of entertainment that masks the propaganda within it.

Clement Greenberg also had advocated for artworks having universal properties that could be appreciated subjectively by everyone (Greenberg, 1961). He was a champion and promoter of the Abstract Expressionist movement where the artist was once again the genius at the centre of the work. No contextual or artistic references such as allegorical, literary or associative content were believed to be embodied in the artwork. There was also no figurative content, solely just two dimensional flat colours and a capturing of emotional depth where form was solely important. He believed that only the educated art specialists could really understand and interpret the quality of these artworks.

Harold Rosenberg (1952) was an advocate for ‘action painting’ where the canvas became a space of revolution and dialogue between the artists and their artwork. Rosenberg identified the changing face of art as it developed into which was increasingly becoming more focussed on abstract art literary theory than on the production of practice based abstract art.

Beyond Art: Reinhart and the death of art

Latterly the philosophical focus has become more about what the artistic voice was communicating, through both a visual and metaphoric language which located the artwork within a broader cultural and social context. It

is within this cultural and social context that greater insight into the symbiotic relationship between the artists, their culture and their environment could be found.

At the beginning of the 1960's the art world continued to change, moving away completely from the old order of modernist and memetic aesthetics, which became progressively outdated as new forms of artistic practice took over. Art philosophers struggled to theorise around the new directions that art was taking and it was challenging to categorise art that did not fit into the old aesthetic, memetic forms of art or of the modernist paradigms of flat, two dimensional, aesthetically pleasing, painterly work as defined by Clement Greenberg.

Arthur Danto's article 'The Artworld' (1964) attempted to theorise around the parameters of new art practices within the radically dynamic creative arts scene in New York during the late 50's and early 60's. His work had an influence on aesthetic philosophy as he introduced an important new theoretical element suggesting that there was a relationship between the institutional community surrounding art production and its social influence around the categories of what was acceptable and what could be introduced into the canon of art. His 'artworld' (1964) which was not clearly defined, acts as a collective of persons working on behalf of social institutions and authorised cultural gatekeepers who apply the historic, economic and cultural context to a piece of artwork to ascertain whether it is recognised as art or not. (Danto 1964, p. 34)

"To see something as art requires something the eye cannot decry - an atmosphere of artistic theory, a knowledge of the history of art: an artworld." (Danto 1964, p. 580)

George Dickie then responded to Danto's work and developed foundational ideas around the classification of art and its relationship to those institutions and the experts that bestow status upon it. In the 'Institutional Theory of Art' (G. Dickie, 1976) he further expands on the role of the interdependence of the inhabitants of the artworld; artists, gallerists, museum curators, critics, academics and art institutions in defining works of art. He believed that the artworld consisted of a number of differing subgroupings of artists and supporting infrastructures. His definition of what is art in a classificatory sense is conferred by an institution within the artworld as a 'candidate for appreciation'. He develops this further in 'The Art Circle' (1984) which refines his thinking.

"A work of art in the classificatory sense is (1) an artifact (2) a set of the aspects of which has had conferred upon it the status of candidate for appreciation by some person or person acting on behalf of a certain social institution (the artworld)" (G., Dickie, 1976, p. 21)

Dickie attempted to supply a framework (1984) which would define the status of art works through an institutional lens and although his ideas were appreciated by the theoretical community as a starting point, his proposals were seen as too generic and broad by other theorists such as Beardsley (1976), Cohen (1973) and Blizek (1974) who challenged and saw the limits of his premise, which cannot fully accommodate the multiple avenues that art can be conceived and defined as out with that model. His work was also in contrast to that of Morris Weitz in his 1956 essay, "The Role of Theory in Aesthetics" where it was proposed that there was no way to define art as it was an 'open concept'. Even Danto latterly disputed Dickie's definition of artwork meeting a special kind appreciation.

T. J. Diffey (1969) had a similar institutional perspective on the nature of the artworld, but used the term 'republic of art' to encompass the artworld of artists, the audience, critics and "anyone involved within the arts". Diffey also included value judgements around the quality of artwork and rejected the idea that bad art could actually be defined as a form of art. Danto (1997) latterly argued that the great master narratives defining traditional art had come to an end and that contemporary art was no longer encompassed by those types of narratives.

Howard Becker had similar views to Dickie's writing and developed these ideas further, believing that art is fundamentally social in character and is derived through consensual negotiation. He was particularly interested in the detail of artists' networks of relationships which support and add value to their art practice, in a similar way to collaborations within music production and in the film-making industries. He explores the myths and rational around what makes good art and the quality control set in place to support it. He believed that artworks are produced through a wide range of artistic outputs, and created through 'collective action' which included not only the artist but the involvement of curators, critics, gallery owners, publishers and the media who support the placing of that work within a cultural context and define its meaning and value. He also includes those who supply the materials that make the production of art possible, such as the paint, brushes and canvas suppliers (Becker. H.S., 1974, 1976, 1982).

Sociologist and philosopher, Pierre Bourdieu's work vastly develops these positions, analysing and exploring in much greater detail the relationship between art and taste in the dynamics of power hierarchies within French society, focussing on concepts of cultural, symbolic and social types of capital and their relationship to the broader issues of economic capital (1983). He also understood that economic and cultural elites controlled the definition of high art and gatekeepers controlled which artworks were valued, exhibited and which creative voices were allowed to be heard. He identified the interconnected relationship between the 'field of power' encompassing the economic, political, educational and intellectual fields and the field of cultural production (Hesmondhalgh, 2006, p27). 'Cultural violence' was a term coined by him to reference the abuse of social power that was used as a tool against the lower classes, also including women and minority groups, to exclude their voices and contributions (Bourdieu, 1983, 1995, 1996, Bourdieu et al, 1994). He stated that "the art business, a trade in things that have no price belongs to a class of practices in which the logic of the pre-capitalist economy lives on" and also believed that there was an inherent paradox between art and capitalism, where it is simultaneously spiritual and other worldly but also clearly part of the financially driven capitalist based global art market (Bourdieu P & Nice R., 1980).

Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi also developed a simple, elegant model of the development of creative artifacts which complements Bourdieu's (1977) thinking and modelling of art and cultural production. (Fulton J., Paton E. 2016). His model is made up of three dynamic and interactive elements: creative artistic skills and crafts, set within a clear cultural context, and judgement of appropriateness by a group of authoritative experts. These three subsystems correspond to the personal, the domain and field of his model and each has impact on the other (1975, 1990, 1997). The cultural gate keepers control what is acceptable art and Csikszentmihalyi, just like Bourdieu, uses religious metaphors to describe that process: ecclesiastical, having initiates, priestly castes and a language based on their esoteric knowledge about the metaphysics of the arts which are beyond the understanding of mere mortals and the working class. Even so, Csikszentmihalyi believes that the creative

artist's success is often determined by chance events, with them relying heavily on being 'discovered' by one of the cultural elites and through that being able to access resources to fund their creative output. He proposes that having close connections with art institutions, artistic communities, gallerists and associated organisations would increase their chances of being 'found' by an art expert and being then guided under their tutelage to success.

The complementary theorizing of the hidden art world by Greg Sholette, author of 'Creative Dark Matter' (2011), recognises that the majority of artists are independent, self-sufficient and are not aligned to any galleries or institutions. Sholette also adds additional collaborative partners to Dickie's and Becker's artworlds, such as those in the technology industries, the internet providers and software programmers who manage the internet, and those who support artists with their online social media campaigns and web presence. Sholette's artists work independently and are disconnected from the official art world, although they make up the majority of artistic practitioners. They are often in the avant-garde who produce artwork on minimal or no financial support. He claims that the nature of their art is a very personal one and centred on a political practice which has the ability to hold those in power to account and certainly sits out with the established financially driven global art market's structure. (Sholette G, 2004, 2016, 2017) Simultaneously, he also wanted recognition of this alternative creative output to have status as untarnished true 'bare art' within that very same art world sphere. This group of overlooked artists are not included in the other theorists' formal artworlds and due to this omission Sholette's views offer valuable structural additions to these key theorists.

In addition to her feminist writings, Lucy Lippard (1973) explored conceptual anti-form based art where ideas take priority over physical output. The 'dematerialization' of the art object supports Sol LeWitt's premise that it was 'the idea or concept is the most important aspect of the work' (1967, p. 79). This idea was central and more important than the materiality of visual elements, where artistic thought and its context are enough to apply to any environment, performance or street work. Non art based subject matter allow artists to develop un-situated work and greater freedom to have that work exposed to a bigger audience, as they often move away from the traditional gallery and museum based patronage.

In the last twenty years there has been a blurring of lines between art, culture and the creative industries. In a period of rapid technological, social and economic change, the UK government has utilised this package of 'creative and cultural industries' as part of a forward looking narrative built around economic and social policy initiatives which look to harness artistic and creative activity towards the development of a post-industrial knowledge economy (Banks & O'Connor 2009).

"industries producing "cultural products"—defined as 'nonmaterial' goods directed at a public of consumers, for whom they generally serve an esthetic or expressive, rather than a clearly utilitarian function" (Hirsch 1972 p. 641)

The fluid boundaries can make it difficult to recognise the difference between those visual artists on the fringe of the 'artworld' who are meeting the needs of the art market and other types of creatives who are employed in the cultural industries serving the capitalist economy more directly. The UK government believed there was a political value in pooling them together within a creative industries sector. Both creative groups have common employment issues, with the majority having challenging working conditions, often having to manage multiple jobs and a precarious livelihood, generating income sporadically with either sales of art or moving from one creative design contract to another. The artists tend to work individually whereas those in the cultural industries often work as teams where they may also have more secure employment. Both recognise the importance of developing and promoting their personal brand and having qualities of integrity.

They initially appear to be working in parallel fields of creative production with differing audiences and markets, although perhaps artistic production still holds the religious illusion of mystery and awe with an elite art market sitting behind it. The artist has still the possibility of being elevated and consecrated by the artworld as a creative genius, reflecting back their impressions of the world that we live in. In addition, their creative work could appreciate in value if accepted into the art market place and become a worthy investment for their benefactors. The artwork always will be unique, distinctive, novel and authentic and could lose its appeal and value if it was turned into a mass produced commodity. It is imperative that artists do not pander to the art market or they will lose their unique vision. With conceptual art, the artist may even delegate the production of their idea to a craftsperson or not even make anything at all if it is a performative piece (Becker H, 1984, Banks, M. 2010, Caves 2000). Throsby's (2001) concentric circle model places the purest form of art at the centre and radiating outwards there is a dilution of purity as it is mixed with more commercial outlets.

In contrast, creative freelancers and designers are most likely to be involved in low brow, mass produced, commercial projects within the world of creative design. Those in the creative industries work to commodify and supply mass produced popular culture to a global audience. Industries employing new media designers (Gill 2007), jazz musicians (Banks et al 2014) and fashion designers (McRobbie 2016) are all included within this sector. There is unlikely to be any mystery or spirituality surrounding their work. It is often prescriptive and derivative, tuning in to what is fashionable at the time, with less scope for originality in meeting the client's brief and the market's needs. The creative industries can be influenced by what is happening in the art market and their forms of creative output rarely increase in value over time.

However, just as in high art there is high fashion, with leading fashion houses promoting their own consecrated designers. In film there are directors who produce art house films for a select audience, projected and viewed in elite film theatres. Music also has its own high-end musicians and orchestras housed in architectural masterpieces who create special work for the elites and not for the popular music market. Even architecture could be included as there are also elevated architects who are worshipped as visionaries, surrounded by teams of designers interpreting their creative musings. It could be argued that these creatives have their own equivalent unique versions of the 'artworld' and have built institutions set within their own disciplines, who bestow their own marks of approval, making judgements on their work and are the sole arbiters responsible for defining their status.

“the interconnectedness of the field of cultural production with other fields, especially the economic and political fields constituting the ‘field of power’, but also the educational and intellectual fields.”

(Hesmondhalgh, 2006, p27)

Frith and Horne (1987) identified the relationship between fine art and the creative industries being developed out of the radical and anarchistic art schools at a time of social upheaval, as western societies moved away from heavy industries to a service industry and information society.

“from the 1960s onwards, innovations in ‘pop-art’, pop music, avant-garde and counter-cultural politics, commercial practices of design, publishing, retailing, and all the creative affordances of an expanded media culture, most productively came together in the art school context, so providing blueprints for what have since become known as the ‘creative industries’ in Britain.” (Frith & Horne, 1987)

Perhaps the traditional art school divisions of fine art and design schools hold the key to any perceived differences. Fine artists promote themselves and their practice to business networks of gallerists, museums, curators and critics who mediate between them and the patrons of the art market. They have differing processes and requirements to that of creative designers who work for a variety of corporate clients and marketing agencies in meeting the needs of the manufacturing and service industries, often working to a budget and remaining anonymous within the process.

Most avant-garde artists have potential for a greater freedom in what they creatively produce and often can take their time in the completion of their creative work as they are not subject to outside demands, whilst those in the creative industries are likely to be working for a client with tight timescales, deadlines and budgetary requirements. In this case, freedom is limited and often curtailed through the overriding demands and control of the market and ultimately down to their clients personal taste and whims. The quality of their working lives and of their well-being is concerning due to the intense pressure placed on them to deliver results on time and to budget, but there is limited protection or support network for them if things go wrong in their lives. Often artists need space and time to develop work that just is not available for those working in the creative industries.

Financial success in the art market is often about being noticed and discovered by someone in a position of power. (Bourdieu 1984, Csikszentmihalyi 1975, Sternberg R. J., (ed), 1999, p. 328) Once they are elevated and consecrated, the art market helps sustain them, often for mutual benefit and financial gain.

At a private gallery event held by the B.LA Art Foundation in Vienna April 2022, a select body of the Viennese elite were personally invited to view the 'high art' paintings of Austrian artist Monika Kus Picco. The general public were not invited to the ceremony. The event was introduced by Dr. Klaus Albrecht Schröder, Director of the Albertina in Vienna, who opened the exhibition at the Ottakringer Brewery's dynamic gallery space and spoke at length to the audience highlighting the merits and attributes of the artist's work. The select Austrian 'artworld' was in attendance, being introduced to her new artworks commended by the gallerist. The artist's large abstracts were selling for approximately 40,000 Euros each and four had already been purchased. The gallery was set within a beautiful, edgy, modern venue where the artworks were hung from the ceiling, and had a free bar for the guests. The artworks were ubiquitous and exclusive with a cultural history attached to them, which Schröder promoted. This ceremony consecrated the artist as Austria's next leading abstract expressionist, since her mentor, the action painter Hermann Nitsch had recently passed away.

There are similar exclusive environments displaying the haute couture of top fashion houses such as Gucci, Chanel, Dior and Louis Vuitton. Again, we can see, high end fashion is turned into a performative artform, aimed and sold exclusively to an elite customer base.

Nothing appears to be further from that experience to that of someone working in the creative industries as a freelance gig worker, whose life is part of the precariat. The precariat is a social class who live without predictability or security around employment and it is a term that is useful in describing many of those working in the creative industries. Being brought in to contribute to a creative project on a low wage with no welfare support structures in place and living in a risk economy with no future certainty appears to be something quite different to elevated artists. Creativity when working to a fixed budget often results in free labour being given by the designer to achieve the clients' set goals as there is always ambiguity and issues of personal taste in the design solutions being proposed and accepted (McRobbie 2002). However, a fine artist who is working on their own projects or still awaiting success is likely to have very similar experiences of financial precarity and lack of certainty in a similar way to the creative worker, although they will likely have greater control over their own artworks.

In certain sectors such as 'new media', the work status of creative designers is more fluid, with some having different experiences of being freelance, an employee and even of establishing and running their own businesses. These creative workers are extremely highly qualified and are passionate and enthusiastic about their work which is located in a cool, hip cutting edge environment. Many of these freelancers routinely work between fifty five and eighty hours per week and it is not uncommon for them to be working throughout the night. They are poorly paid and feel very insecure about their careers. The special characteristics of this specific group includes their stamina, an ability to learn and utilise new technologies quickly and their having an eye for new technological trends and innovations. (Gill R, 2007)

Other more recent 'creative and cultural' theorists joining the creative debate tend to be more interested in a variety of broader areas such as race, gender, sexuality and artist activism. In *Feminism-Art-Theory; An anthology 1968-2014* (Robinson H, 2015) and the work of Griselda Pollock (1981, 1988, 2005, 2013, 2015) feminist critiques of art history and engagements in a range of gendered perspectives around art and the creative industries are explored. There is also research into the changing working patterns in a neo-liberal society where precarious working conditions for cultural workers are highlighted. In feminist cultural studies, academic Angela McRobbie's 'Clubs to Companies' (2002) explains what has been happening to the cultural industry sector over the last two decades. After the Thatcher government and New Labours neo-liberal focus on developing the UK brand of 'cool Britannia' the advent of rapid and ongoing changes in working conditions for the creative industries workforce in the UK has come at a personal cost to those involved. The industry promotes itself as inherently rewarding and being a source of self-actualisation with participants needing to be multiskilled, entrepreneurial, and self-reliant but the reality is often quite different.

This sector appeared to have benefits of more flexible work environments for those who are often more disadvantaged in the workplace, such as women, and in particular mothers, the disabled and ethnic minorities, giving them greater opportunities to develop successful careers. It might be imagined that a flexible creative cultural sector would be the ideal place for those who were disadvantaged and for minorities to be more successful, but with the limited data available this appears not to be the case, as older working patterns where the marginalisation of these groups is re-emerging and continuing with nothing to hold it in check, as the forums and political venues for these issues to be raised and discussed are no longer available to them.

This new capitalism absolves itself from any responsibility in maintaining social structures (Baumann, 1999). Without any support from institutions, organisations or trade unions there are no opportunities for dialogue or social critique through workplace democracy, leaving those impacted disempowered and with no avenues of redress. Cultural workers tend to work in isolation, having transient and impermanent lives, disengaged from traditional community-based workspaces where human resource departments' policies monitor quotas, equal opportunities, anti-discrimination and organizational responsibilities.

Informal networking is a key issue in the continuation of this inequality. The status quo is sustained as an artist's reputation requires trust and the minimizing of risk in meeting customers' satisfaction where those working together feel more comfortable with those they understand. Within this type of environment women are disadvantaged and there is no possibility of change ever happening. In the new economy of post-modern capitalism, creative workers are required to be competitive, flexible and opportunistic, developing new skills when required to survive in a fast-burn capitalism. They also need youthful stamina and the ability to work long hours (Morgan G & Nelligan P, 2018).

What is recognised is that contracts and freelance work are given out through informal knowledge channels to those who are likely to be friends in a trusted network. Since freelance employment has no official accounts of employee work history or employer references around work experience and achievements, employment opportunities become more about who you know, how successful you are and what project you last worked on. Freelance workers' reputations are their key attributes in finding and outsourcing work through networking, developing and sustaining personal connections. This is carried out offline through face to face connections and

social events or online through social media and constant self-promotional activities (Cote & Pybus, 2011). Since trust and personal characteristics are paramount to any business relationship, any risk to the reputation of the creative freelancer which could damage their relationship with a client must be avoided at all costs (Gill 2007 p. 6, Franks, 1999).). Therefore, it is understandable why bringing in marginalised or unknown workers who may possibly carry greater unknown potential risks is potentially too problematic and is to be avoided where possible. So wholesale discrimination goes unchecked in this progressively unregulated industry as the mechanisms to contain them have themselves become redundant. Anyone in the industry speaking out about this inherent discrimination and bias would automatically be seen as a potential trouble maker, which would immediately decrease any opportunities for them to gain employment, thus leaving them in a catch twenty two scenario of damned if you do and damned if you don't.

The de-regulation and casualization of the cultural and creative sector expanded, in part as government cut and privatized previously subsidized cultural provision (McRobbie 2002 p519). Old work patterns where staff were employed on full-time contracts were no longer the norm, being progressively replaced by temporary freelancers bought in to complete individual projects and then being released.

Self-reliance is part of an 'individuated' way of working, where individuals take on all the risks of being self-employed in an unstructured and fluid state which have no government social support and no social benefits if there is an inability to find new work, or if they are unable to work through ill health (Bauman, 1999, 2000). Due to labour costs falling in the culture sector there is no opportunity for anyone but the super successful to create any financial cushion to protect themselves from life's mishaps. Recognising that creative workers have sole responsibility for their own success requires them having 'reflexivity' in addressing any difficulties that arise. Self-blame comes with self-responsibility if success is not achieved, which has a de-socialising effect on those workers. To sustain ongoing employment, self-employed cultural workers need to constantly promote themselves, utilising their informal networks to make work connections that bring them ongoing employment.

McRobbie believes that raves and dance parties in the 90's were run by entrepreneurial artists, who built up skillsets in events management, helping transform the cultural sector into one that engaged with a wider, younger audience. This commercial approach in cultural production helped to break down the class divide between high and low culture. Opportunities of 'networking sociality' have opened up through social media platforms, within an information and technological society and the opportunities of the promotion of individuality has created new ways of making a living in the cultural industries (Wittel, 2002).

McRobbie's 'Be Creative: Making a Living in the New Culture Industries' (2016) rails against the right wing neo-conservative political and economic agenda promoting the development of a precarious risk economy and a life of unstable working patterns for those involved in the creative economy. Her quote from a fashion journalist "Once you've tried doing four jobs, you'll never want anything less" (McRobbie 2016, p. 27) highlights the harsh realities of an extremely stressful, and competitive working environment with its lack of security in a freelance career. Working for low pay in a sector with minimal employment protection is not sustainable for many. She explores the conditions and quality of life of creative workers whose expectations and aspirations often cannot be met and therefore they can become disillusioned with the industry and leave (McRobbie 2002, p523). McRobbie looks at the social and business networks required in building sustainable environment for

creatives. She identifies the issues in detail and debates the ideas around what would be required to return the creative economies back to pre-Thatcher left wing political ideals but fails to really provide any practical solutions that could be implemented to help solve the problems discussed.

In Bridget Conor et al's, 'Gender and Creative Labour' (2015), issues are raised around the illusion of the cultural and creative industries being cool, egalitarian and diverse and looks in detail at work patterns in the film and media industries. They also believe that the sector suffers from seriously embedded inequality and discrimination around class, age, gender, race and disability (Gill 2007, p. 35). However, they recognise there is a lack of research and statistics around discrimination in these industries and that government appears to have little interest in addressing these issues nor even in seeking to understand or define them. It is also recognised that in spite of the hype around the cultural and creative industries' ability to develop national economies, increase employment, regenerate inner cities and promote a country's creativity there are serious issues to be addressed around the nature of the precarious, temporal, and unsupported working practices of those employed within it.

Analysis of UK data shows clear gender inequalities and sexism within the television, film and media industries. There is also the claim that 'underlying social class inequality' has often been excluded from the debate around discrimination (Acker 2006). It extends into architecture and classical music where female participation in these industries is minimal. Gender inequalities particularly around age and the parental status of women were clear (Dent, 2019) as was discrimination against black, Asian and other minority groups who have been seriously under represented to the degree that there have been justified claims of institutional racism within the industry.

In addition to discrimination by gender bias, ethnicity age and disability, the creative industries are structurally organised by class (Banks et al. 2013, Eikhof & Warhurst, 2013) Opportunities for the working-class to be employed and develop careers within the creative industries are progressively getting worse, due to the 'colonisation' of creative industry jobs by the middle-classes and the systemic disregard for working-class applicants.

The art world also sits within a structure of elite power and class. It is historically driven by a Eurocentric male perspective and has been highly discriminatory against women and the creative voices of other minority groups. Since the eighties, progressive attempts have been made to force the industry be more inclusive and substantial changes have taken place to challenge the gatekeepers of the artworld to accept a more global production and audience for that work.

Freelance labour markets where employment is fragmented and insecure have the capacity to compound problems of structural discrimination as practices aimed at reducing inequality are more likely to be implemented in larger organisations with HR support. Equal opportunity policies are therefore doomed to failure where there are no structural organisations to monitor and implement them (Holgate and McKay, 2009).

"Between 2006 and 2012, the number of BAMEs working in the UK TV industry has declined by 30.9% . . . The total number of black and Asian people in the industry has fallen by 2000 while the industry as a whole has grown by over 4000. Or to put

it another way – for every black and Asian person who lost their job, more than two white people were employed”. (Khaleeli, 2014)

Banks (2009) also raises the issues of insecurity, inequality and exploitation within the creative industries. Under-representation of women in the cultural industries is sustained through ‘gendered segregation’ by the stereotyping of the roles that women and men have traditionally carried out and this is particularly prominent in the film and television industries (Hesmondhalgh & Baker, 2011). Boundary-crossing where there is a lack of distinction between home life and work, and between cultural paid and non-paid work such as internships, where being able to survive with no salary was also related to class and relative privilege. Structural racism in the UK limits the educational and employment opportunities of minority groups through lack of support, social exclusion and stereotyping. For example, British jazz represents multicultural music which bridges both art and culture with a distinct approach to music making, however black jazz musicians have low wages and poor career prospects, with a lack of any industry support and investment. (Banks M et al, 2014)

The UK government has promoted the employment opportunities and economic benefits that the creative industries could bring and is seeking to exploit this sector further. In the de-traditionalisation of work, creative work is promoted as autonomous, self-expressive and individualistic. ‘These values predispose them to pursue self-employment and entrepreneurship in a spirit of self-exploration and self-fulfilment’ (Leadbeater & Oakley 1999, p. 15).

“creative work is now imagined only as a self-actualizing pleasure, rather than a potentially arduous or problematic obligation undertaken through material necessity” (Caves, R. 2000)

Banks & Hesmondhalgh (2009) have identified that in the UK government’s creative industries policy, the challenges and problems inherent in the creative labour workforce have been ignored. Issues around sustainable creative employment, where those who are self-employed or working as freelancers struggle with the generation of a sustainable income from irregular, short term contracts and limited social support if difficulties arise. Earnings often are at subsistence levels and impacted by an over-supply of labour and are inadequate in building any type of financial safety net and often a need for other jobs are required to make ends meet. Risks encountered in this state of economic uncertainty are disproportionately carried by the low paid and insecure and diversity issues in particular impact women, minorities and ethnic groups (Neff et al 2005). However, an alternative competing narrative has been suggested by a government funded research group and it is suggested that rather it is those specific individual’s capabilities and cognitive competencies that are the core issues, not institutional discrimination, racism and sexism, according to a report compiled by Work Foundation (2007, p. 142) for the DCMS. The limited research on these issues does not bear out that view.

“the creative industries are peopled by creative talents who themselves get pleasure and utility from what they do. They are ‘called to their art’. One upside from the business perspective (although it attracts complaints of exploitation) is that their ‘reservation’ wages – the lowest they are prepared to work for – are lower than the marginal value of what they produce, making labour particularly cheap. A downside is that the ‘talent’ care deeply about how the creative work is organised, which may discourage concessions or compromises to management.” (Work Foundation 2007, p.102)

Although projects are often team based, creative labour is largely individualised and the sector is largely unsupported and casualised. There is little collective identity or solidarity which leaves creative workers open to exploitation. Ursell (200, p. 807) identifies an intensification of the self-commodification within each individual as they are forced to personally compete for any available work. The UK government has chosen to ignore primary difficulties found in the precarious working environment of creative workers and in two commissioned reports; *Staying Ahead* (Work Foundation 2007) and *Creative Britain* (DCMS 2008) which looked into the creative economy's issues around its skills and employability and the core issues contributing to employment being not economically sustainable for many who are forced to leave the sector due to the difficulties encountered were raised. Instability, insecurity of employment, unfavorable working hours, issues of low pay, poor working conditions and institutional discrimination have not been tackled and have failed to be addressed through any government strategy. (Work Foundation 2007, p. 113)

Arts graduates often struggle to find jobs in the creative industries, estimating that only half of all art school graduates find jobs in that sector, after graduation. It is strange that government continues to subsidise this mismatch between graduates and jobs in the creative market place. The majority of jobs in the creative sector tend to be taken up by graduates from the elite Russell Group universities, often without having any arts-based degree expertise. (Comunian, 2010, p. 400). Transfer of creative skills and knowledge to other sectors when industry churn happens is seen as a benefit, not as a waste of resources spent in education and experience. The government's only concerns appear to be around ensuring that the workforce is flexible and skilled and most able to contribute to businesses and the economy.

UK DCMS is well aware of the inequality and exploitation within the creative industry. It also recognises systemic issues around the operation of informal employment networks which are often inaccessible and closed to outsiders.

“for too many at the moment, the chance to start a career in the creative industries means moving to London, working for free or knowing someone who can get you a foot in the door.” (DCMS 2008, p. 7)

The Cox Review of Creativity in Business (Cox 2005) focusses on skills development in aid of competitiveness around developing the national brand of the UK against the threat of emerging economies in India and China. It believed that universities and art schools must prioritise the development of 'economically valuable skills' that meet employers' needs. (Leitch 2006, p. 2-4).

UK DCMS commissioned the McMaster report 'Supporting Excellence in the Arts' (2008) which concluded that excellence should be aimed for and that they should be putting trust in the artists, as opposed to taking an instrumental approach around them meeting targets and audits. However, this narrative was used by the English Arts Council only in regard to resourcing and supporting national institutions, not in its support of any form of decentralised democratic cultural policy or in support of grass root organisations.

So, there appears to be little meritocracy within the creative industries and the route to success is grounded in class, status, private education, wealthy parents and graduating 'in any discipline' from an elite university. The

informal and individualized recruitment processes within the creative industries serves this discrimination, especially within the fine art, television, film and journalism sectors.

Banks (2009) identifies a number of challenges to the idea of a coherent creative industries sector. He questions the validity of the commercial, social and cultural benefits attributed to the creative industries and claims there are no clear definitions of what it means, nor measures of success. For such a supposedly important sector he wonders why there is a lack of governmental strategy around the creative industries.

Rational for choice of theorists utilised within this thesis

Several theorists were identified from the literature review who have helped develop a structural framework that could be utilised in defining the relationship between contemporary artists, society and in particular the power dynamics of those supporting their artistic practice

Although the more recent research and enquiry since 2000 appears to have a range of differing focus on the creative industries in relation to that of the Bourdieusian dynamic relationship between the cultural elite, the specifics of the artworld, the art market place and the funding of artists' practice, there are certainly major overlaps in the working conditions of those involved. Livelihoods within the broad scope of the cultural industries set within a neo-liberal economy are often precarious and poorly paid, located within an environment of discrimination and disadvantage manifesting through class, race, sexism and ageism.

However, for the purpose of this paper investigating how artists navigate and interact with the power dynamics and ecosystems of the Scottish artworld, four theorists have been chosen; Howard Becker, Pierre Bourdieu, Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi and Gregg Sholette all have important detailed and complementary understandings of the interactions of artists particularly with regard to networks and connections within social and cultural contexts which could be useful to this research process. Their research offers additional detailed, unique and significant insights into the social dynamics and relationships within the artworld, set within the context of a broader cultural and political environment. A framework developed using the range, ideas and theories of these scholars would be a useful tool in the analysis of the lives of Scottish artists, allowing comparisons to be made and opportunities found to confirm or challenge their premise and assumptions. This would help in the understanding of the lived realities of these Scottish artists and the difficulties they face in their relationships with all aspects of wealth, class, the artworld, institutions, and in politics, located within a broader social network of connections. It is believed that these theorists' concepts encompass the core elements of artistic lives set within a cultural system of control where politics, economics and the artworlds interact.

Bourdieu's writings are of particular use to this thesis as his theories developed around the nature of cultural capital and its interactions with power structures is important in setting a critical lens in the analysis of the Scottish government's cultural policy set out in the next chapter.

Further development of the four theorists work chosen will now be expanded upon.

I have chosen to utilise the seminal work of Pierre Bourdieu and related theorists, in their development of ideas and theories around the production of art within the context of cultural working.

Bourdiesian theoretical and methodological principles will be explored and challenged within this research looking into the Scottish artist network with a view to validate his core theories and identify any issues and changes over the last fifteen years since his death that have been brought about by social changes, the development of global internet connectivity and the advent of social media. The supporting works of Becker, Csikszentmihalyi and Sholette will also be included in this literature review to both support his position and to challenge his assertions. Other theorists in this field at that time were Kearney (1988), Diffey (1969), Danto (1992), Dickie, (1993) and Hagberg (2002) who introduced ideas around the cultural and institutional contexts of the artworld.

Pierre Bourdieu

Pierre Bourdieu (1930-2002) was a sociologist, philosopher and intellectual, who had interests, among many, in the dynamics of power in society and was a product of the French elitist education system. He was responsible for developing research methods and frameworks that introduced concepts applying to the business of cultural working, together with its production, circulation and consumption.

His ideas explored concepts of cultural, symbolic and social types of capital and refined distinctions within the structures of broader economic capital often within a very catholic narrated framework. He also developed a language which helped define the power dynamics that support, validate and legitimise certain types of art practice over others, and identified aspects of cultural working that are core elements in the production of creative goods, such as the habitus, the field, symbolic goods, creative capital, cultural capital (embodied, objectivated, and institutionalised) and reproduction. Individuals are constrained by the amount and quality of their cultural, economic and social capital that they have available to them. Bourdieu intended his theories around habitus, the field and forms of capital to be utilised as tools used within empirical research (Peillon, 1998, p. 241)

He also coined the term 'symbolic violence' which defines all the structures which reinforce the ruling classes' political and cultural positions through the hidden 'norms' that set boundaries and definitions of each class in a society and explain how social inequality is perpetuated and reproduced (Nash, R. 1999).

Thus, it is clear that the literary and artistic field is constituted as such in and by opposition to a 'bourgeois' world which had never before asserted so bluntly its values and its pretension to control the instruments of legitimation, both in the domain of art and in the domain of literature, and which, through the press and its hacks, now aims to impose a degraded and degrading definition of cultural production.

(Bourdieu P., 1996, p. 58)

Bourdieu has theorised and developed models of relational thinking around the interactions of visual art practitioners, their creative outputs, and their creative supporters, which propose that artists inhabit an inter-relational world where the production of artifacts set within a cultural economy are surrounded by a range of contextual markers which are core to the generation and maximisation of their economic value – ‘a field as a structure of objective relations’ (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 312). It is also the site of struggle between the dominated and the dominant group’s symbolic power within each contested field, which ensures that the powerful always have overall control of their field, allowing them to maintain that privileged relationship (Burkett 2004, p. 236). Bourdieu defines the art ‘field’ as highly specific, with its own beliefs, histories, traditions and spread of agents within it and it is distinct, operating within its own social rules.

The artists’ habitus, which contains the skills they bring to the development of the creative artifact, together with other associated specific capital such as class, recognition, reputation or notoriety are parts of that broader economic value. The habitus of an artist is also composed of their disposition, upbringing, interactions with the outside world, the institutions and the academies they are members of, their published output in journals and magazines, what galleries they exhibit in, the relationships with curators and the differing types of media that they engage with and who write, talk and critique them. Even their more personal qualities and relationships are part of that value, together with how much they are seen, promoted and commented on publicly. It is one of many variables a researcher should consider (Nash, 1999, p. 185). Thus, the habitus can be generally perceived as embodying our gender, social status, class and ethnicity.

Bourdieu’s builds and expands upon Marxist concepts of economic capital, introducing social, and cultural forms too. His definitions of these differing forms of capital which are convertible and transmissible are; ‘economic capital’, which are material assets that can be turned into money and are connected to wealth and property, ‘social capital’ which is made up of social networks, memberships and relationships, which have the capacity to secure material or symbolic profits in certain situations and which may be institutionalised in titles such as nobility (1986, p. 249) and ‘cultural capital’ which can also in certain circumstances be turned into economic capital through social structures such as educational qualifications.

Cultural capital is a “form of long-lasting dispositions of the mind and the body” (Bourdieu, 1986, p. 243) and it contains cultural behaviours that are internalised through socialisation. Bourdieu breaks ‘cultural capital’ down further into three fundamental forms; the embodied, the objectified and the institutionalized. The embodied state refers to social status and wealth (Nash, 1999 p. 185), the objectified state refers to ownership of goods or artefacts and the institutionalised state refers to things like memberships of institutions or academic qualifications. This allows an individual to directly convert capital between the cultural and economic currencies, through ‘a certificate of cultural competence which confers on its holder a conventional, constant, legally guaranteed value with respect to culture’ (Bourdieu, 1986, p. 244-5). In addition, symbolic capital can be used to highlight and assert the power of the dominant class and the social positions of the actors involved (Siisiäinen, 2000, p. 183-204).

The meaning of the creative artifact ‘is defined in relation to the space of opportunities’ (Bourdieu, 1983, p313) that surround it. The artistic meanings of the creative piece will always change within the context of the audience or the observers in relationship to the broader environment. When new art collectives are formed,

discovered and manifestoes launched into the art field, they create ripples of change that have impact on the status quo, energizing and challenging cultural norms which may begin to degrade and start a progressive decline of the current dominant art scene. The current perspective progressively becomes dated and outmoded, as can be seen through progressive historical art trends. There is always conflict between those who have success and made their name and wish to continue to be at the forefront and those who struggle to relegate them by surpassing them through ‘discontinuity, difference and revolution’ and a recognition of the difference between those in the avant-garde and in the art work of the successful elevated ‘consecrated’ ones. The function of defining the name of artistic schools and the forming of explicit manifestos of the new art movement is to allow easy classification of these pseudo-concepts by art interpreters, critics, academics, dealers, gallerists, media and historians, and as a vehicle and tool in the process of promoting their cause and brand. Taste is constructed through a social, class-based hierarchy which is constantly changing over time and being constantly reinvented. It sits within a temporal field, which is constantly being overtaken, displaced and renewed. To bring a new cultural producer into the market place the older established producers, products and systems of taste need to be overtaken and relegated. This cycle is constantly reoccurring with the old order being replaced by the new, together with a supporting educational system that defines and historically updates the taxonomies surrounding art that guides those innovators who follow it.

Power relations

Bourdieu also explores the dichotomy between the artists producing ‘pure’ artworks which are driven by their own internal personal creative activity with total independence and no regard for the market place as opposed to those whose artworks are subordinate to market demands, usually being commissioned or designed to meet the interests or aesthetic values of the dominant classes. Symbolic goods can be defined as having either ‘signification’ which has a symbolic value or merely being ‘merchandise’, which has only market value, where both are independent of each other. (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 141).

“Only if something has symbolic representation can it “exist”. Only then can it be recognised by society.”
(Docampo, 2005, p.15)

This can also be seen in other markets such as fashion where haute couture sits at the high end of signification and merchandise of high street fashion sits at the other end of the spectrum.

“art's status as a symbolic good, it must distinguish itself from, and thereby carve out a privileged space against, other commodities. And it does this by presenting culture "as a kind of superior reality, irreducible to the vulgar demands of economics." (Bourdieu, 1993)

There is also the issue of defining who can be called an artist. The ‘charisma ideology’ is the basis of belief in the value of a piece of artwork which is solely created by the genius of an artist. Who has responsibility in taking on the mantle of king maker and is legitimately authorised to bestow the title of ‘artist’ onto someone who is a cultural worker? Is it their peer network of fellow artists, is it the art schools, academies and groups they are aligned to, or is it those with economic resources and the social capital to identify and invest in or purchase the artifacts? Historically it appears to be primarily those who commission and critique the creative

artwork who bestow the title, but yet in a broader context the artists themselves form a collective or institution with its own independent power to confer that status onto one of their own.

The place of art in society is driven by a collective belief in the definition of what constitutes art and that there is a common understanding of when the creative artifact is acknowledged as sitting within that cultural realm. It is clear that the artist does not sit within a cultural vacuum when they are developing their creative work and there is a reliance on the cultural power system to formally recognize that creative worth. (Dickie, 1974, Barret, 1997, Hagberg, 2002) The critical narrative and historical discourses developed to support the value of the artwork legitimize it and at the same time reaffirms the power hierarchy that bestows that legitimacy upon it. A critical discourse developed around the artwork legitimizes both the artwork and the appointed critics simultaneously. The artwork is deemed worthy of being part of legitimate discourse through its recognition. The critic through their polemic affirms that in their judgement it is a valuable, legitimate contribution to the ongoing production of creative work and this adds to its cultural value. Simultaneously the work of art elevates itself to be consecrated as a symbolic piece of contemplation, particularly in gallery spaces and in museums and as a result the creator is rewarded with artistic prestige. The power of the creative work is diminished and neutralized through its inclusion in institutionally sanctioned places of reflection. This also serves to conserve the positions and power of the established order and its hierarchy. So, works of art only exist if they are recognized as such by an educated audience who can identify them. The critics need to understand the social context of the physical work and through it their understanding of its relationship to the artist, to other historical art movements, cultural references, social origins etc.

“Never in question was the ‘high’ art assumption that works of art – no matter how strange they looked or unskilled they seemed to be - were conduits of transcendent meaning, of truths from the unconscious, expressions or revelations of universal human concerns that the artist was uniquely endowed to apprehend and transmit”. (Dissanayake 1991, p. 124-137)

There is a direct relationship between the field of cultural production and the field of power. It is a site of struggle between the heteronomous principle, in the interests of those who dominate politically and economically, such as when a commission is taken by an artist to meet the needs of a patron, and the autonomous principle, where artists, with a limited resource and capital identify with a degree of economic independence and produce their own independent personalized work, and with no apparent relationship to the desires of the market place, however their work might sell in a limited way. (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 321)

There are also relationships between art produced for a field of restricted ‘high end’ production at high cost and that of broader ‘mass audience’ appeal where ordinary consumers are able to purchase the artwork. The broad appeal of an artist will determine the value of their creative work which is then ‘consecrated’, set between bourgeois art where it would be given a place of honour and a lowlier industrial art which has popularity with a broader audience. These two oppositions; economies of large-scale production and niche output, where the niche output can be again sub divided into the consecrated and the avant-garde, all attracting differing audiences and values. The evolution of artistic practice continually highlights the constantly evolving new heresies of creative work that supersede the old conservative cultural orthodoxy through the ongoing desire to be unique, distinctive and radical as new creative fields evolve. This is balanced by an ongoing process of familiarization

and changing taste of the audience of consumers ultimately leading to the displacement of the previous artistic acts. (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 338).

“The ‘young’ have an interest in describing every advance in the internal hierarchy of the sub-field of restricted production as an advance in the hierarchy of the field of cultural production as a whole, and therefore contest in the independence of the internal hierarchy.” (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 339)

So, Bourdieu believes there are three competing principles of legitimacy. The specific principle of legitimacy which accounts for artists who are autonomous and self-sufficient producers. Then there is legitimacy corresponding to ‘bourgeois’ taste and its consecration by the dominant class and those in power. Thirdly, there is the principle of legitimacy which is ordained by the general public representing the ‘mass audience’.

Art lives independently within a capitalist system often driven with a specifically aesthetic intention and an indifference to economic realities, but also often set within a tension around broader relationship of hierarchization and exploitation by those in a more dominant position with an economic disposition and a profit motive. Cultural workers are able to critically reflect on the social world, particularly in times of crisis and are often in solidarity with those who are economically and culturally dominated. They can utilize their creative power to mobilise and give support to the dominated classes against the dominating fields of power as can be seen in the theories of Sholette (2010, 2016, 2017).

‘Pure’ artists work in a space of freedom, protected from the “bourgeoisie” and are often at odds with state institutions, bureaucracies, academies and salons, and since they belong to an ‘autonomous’ field they can actively produce artifacts focused directed against the interests and values of the power hierarchy. They take the most risk-based approach even when it is unlikely to secure any economic capital and only those who are able to persevere are likely to make any symbolic capital from it. They are likely to be most financially independent and privileged, allowing them to focus on developing their craft and avoiding a ‘day job’ to support themselves. Being financially independent also breeds self-assurance, confidence, audacity and a disregard for economic success. They are also likely to have networks that bring large social capital and a deep knowledge of the field, which translates into recognizing and understanding new directions of travel and riskier investments that have the potential for the generation of the most symbolic capital. (Bourdieu, 1983)

“a rule those richest in economic. cultural and social capital are the first to move into the new positions (and this seems to be true in all fields. economic, scientific, etc.)”

(Bourdieu, 1983, p. 350)

Bourdieu also regards art as having similarities to religion, in parallel with the sacred value of old texts, pure artworks are only accessible to pronouncements of the ecclesiastical, cultural clergy who have the critical and esoteric knowledge around the metaphysical arts which are beyond the understanding of mere mortals, allowing them to sanctify and translate the meanings of the artworks (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 147). He proposes that it is the scholars and the educational system who define and uphold the consecrated works of the past and are responsible for recording the relationships and contexts of these sacred artworks. They mediate on behalf of the artists and their work and the supplicant consumers. There is an inherent value to having these gatekeepers

however, as it allows them to use a range of cultural rules to keep a tight control over which artworks are acceptable and through this, they keep their domain credible. After a long process, the system canonises the artworks and submits them as classics through the process of inducting them into museums and the education curriculum as infallible and consecrated works of art.

Boris Groys, another theorist in this field, contests Bourdieu's position on the power hierarchy, where Groys believes the curator has no power to elevate the work of an artist, without the explicit consent of the artist who chooses to exhibit his work through the opportunities offered by the curator, whose function now is to contextualise the artwork and narrate its relationship to the field. Groys believes that the public wants the impact of unmediated access to artwork without the curatorial practice. He believes the curator creates his own art object through assembling artistic artifacts in creative ways. He does not use the objects for their own sake but is rather an abuser of the core artworks for his own purposes. (Groys, B. 2008 p. 43)

Role of dealers as Symbolic Bankers

Art as an economic activity cannot succeed if it is not supported by art dealers and critics who act as the cultural and symbolic bankers in this field, where art and the market place converge, and artists need to understand the specific laws inherent in the functioning of their field and its specific requirements for them to have any chance of economic success. "The price of a painting has no relationship to the production costs of time, labour and raw materials. Like the chicken and the egg, who is the true distiller of the inherent value in the work? Is it the artist or the dealer (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 149, Bourdieu & Nice, 1980) ?

With the advent of new media structures and social networking it remains to be seen if there is any potential for artists to bypass the traditional gatekeepers of cultural meaning through the building of direct relationships to investors, buyers and the broader general public. In addition to providing the artworks, dealers offer collectors an associated lifestyle of gallery openings, art parties and dinners (Velthuis, 2005, p. 26). Bypassing those who locate the work and define its broader meaning has its downside, as without their knowledge, blessing and support, what other objective indicators of an artwork's quality would there be? They would have to rely on the market place to make judgements solely on the aesthetic and intellectual value and quality of a piece of work, thus taking it out of the realm of the sacred and ethereal into the purely financial.

The more consecrated within art circles the dealer personally is, the more value they can imbue into the art work that they have 'discovered' by bringing it to the market place through the promotion and consecration of the work within the catalogue of an exhibition or gallery space. It is also an investment in the dealer's prestige, reputation and what historical successes they have had in discovering and bringing new artists to the fore. They bring a passion and a desire to elevate the artwork on behalf of the artist who in a sense is discovered and 'owned' by them and often brought to the marketplace almost as their protégé. They help build and promote the personal face of the artist, cultivating their image and voice and create a charismatic aura around them, which energizes and valorises their work. The dealer acts as a cultural banker and guarantor of the purchaser's economic investment, mediating between the buyer and the artist's creative work through their reputation which has been built on all of the symbolic capital they have accumulated in their ongoing relationship with the art

world. Being a cultural banker is not without its own potential risks, as a poor choice of artistic temperament and creative longevity has the potential to damage that built up cultural capital, although this is unlikely, as there is an inherent balance in the system that relies on the confidence of the buyers in that system being sustained, since they would all suffer a mutual loss of investment if the bank for any reason collapses.

In the Financial Times, 3rd October 2020, Francesca Gavin interviewed Phoebe Saatchi Yates around her opening of a new contemporary art gallery in Cork Street London. As the daughter of Charles Saatchi who was one of the most influential art patrons and dealer of his day, she has been exposed to the running of her father's Saatchi gallery for the last three years, learning all aspects of the business and 'increasingly playing the role of art advisor to Charles'. After building connections around the world with internationally famous art institutions and collectors she is about to set up an art gallery business with her husband. She lays out both her economic and cultural capital, referencing curatorial role models and great names in the art world such as New York dealer, Leo Castelli whose business ethos they wish to replicate. "He really maintained the whole charm of the art world, yet the innocence of the art world. That's something we really want to replicate: Castelli elegance" (Gavin, 2020). Their gallery will be one of the biggest in the West End and they are looking to 'make the difference', showing cutting edge, breakthrough work in the centre of art land, giving a platform to young artists and radical new art, and discovering mostly by chance new creative work, not through the traditional routes but from friends' recommendations and via social media channels. They see painting as the most appropriate medium to meet their clients' taste, as they plan to both meet the needs of established collectors in addition to cultivating and growing a new generation of art collectors. Her father has been acting as advisor to them both. We can see that the cultural resources and economic capital that Charles Saatchi has accrued can be passed onto to his daughter who utilises old networks and parental support to offer a new package of cultural work that will hopefully appeal to new investors in this field, potentially bypassing historic routes to success and her taking a very personalised approach to finding and developing new talent which utilises new social media channels in the pursuit of the new wave avant-garde. We can see how effortlessly Phoebe Saatchi Yates can set herself up as a new cultural guardian, with a very modern perspective sitting within Bourdieu's framework of the powerful cultural elites acting as symbolic bankers within the art world, as they seek continued control of the art field.

The dealer's investment needs to be constantly managed through the elevation of the newly discovered work, then through stages of assimilation into the art world's catalogue through collective exhibitions, single personal shows, museum acquisitions, biennials and entry in to prestigious collections. The artwork paradoxically needs to be selectively viewed and discretely managed and cannot be excessively promoted, or commercialised. The dealer needs to build relationships with critics and the media. Finally, the artwork is purchased and valued economically by dealers, collectors, trawlers and speculators, and symbolically by those who are privileged to read about it or to view it, giving it high status, meaning and value (Velthuis, 2005, Thornton, 2009 p. 91). Even buyers have a pecking order whilst in pursuit of the best, most current pieces of art, as the value of the art is impacted by the status of the buyer. 'The owner of the work affects the reputation of the work' (Thornton 2009 p. 258).

"It is the field of production understood as the system of objective relations between these agents or institutions and as the site of struggles for the monopoly of the power to consecrate, in which the value of works of art and belief in that value are continuously generated." (Bourdieu P & Nice R., 1980, p. 265)

There is also the broader competitive struggle where the field accumulates social energy as all the participants in this discipline seek to enhance their positions through their generation of value gleaned from cultural goods and creative activity within the production process, all of course set within a climate of high moral and cultural positions untainted by economic realities. They compete from positions of the old guard versus the new and the status quo bourgeois art is pitted against the avant-garde which are the key principals of division.

“Avant-gardism has nothing to offer to guarantee it’s conviction beyond its indifference to money and its spirit of protest: ‘Money doesn’t count for him; even beyond the notion of public service, he sees culture as a vehicle for social protest’” (De Baecque, 1968 in Bourdieu & Nice, 1980, p. 268)

Bourdieu highlights the systems in place where over the last two centuries old-school gatekeepers have been defining who should become celebrity artists and what the nature of successful art practice should be like. Does the potential of social media and AI algorithms have the capacity to influence and act as new cultural gatekeepers through a more public democracy generated where new structures of art appreciation could be formed by clicks and likes? This direct approach might collapse the historic trend for cultural bankers, critics and intermediaries to set the art agendas but it would possibly be at the expense of dumbing down and devaluing the important narratives surrounding any elevated artists and their artwork.

Howard S Becker

Bourdieu recognises and builds on the work and ideas of sociologist Howard S. Becker (1974, 1976) who also believed that ‘art is social in character’ (1974, p. 767) and that the definition of an artist and their artistic practice is through consensual negotiation. He had an interest in the work artists do and the relationships they have in the creation of that art work but was not overly interested in the actual artworks that they were creating. As in similar ways to the creation of music and literature by musicians and writers, the visual artists are the central players within a radiating network of supporting personnel, who not only support the creative production process but also create added value to the artistic endeavor through their own contributions. The artwork is produced through a wide range of artistic outputs, and created through ‘collective action’ which would also include the support and involvement of curators, critics, gallery owners, publishers and media organisations who locate the placing of that work within a cultural context and define its meaning and value. There is also the need for cultural educators to promote and inform the consumers and investors of the creative artifacts in their understanding of that contextual, symbolic and sacred nature of the work. He also includes members of the audience who respond to the work, critique and appreciate it.

“To say all this goes beyond the assertion that art is social and beyond demonstrations of the congruence between forms of social organization and artistic styles or subjects. It shows that art is social in the sense that it is of people acting created by networks together, and proposes a framework in which differing modes of collective action, mediated by accepted or newly developed conventions, can be studied”

(Becker, 1974, p. 767)

Therefore, it could be claimed that the artist is only one of a number of contributors to the creation of the final artwork (Becker, 1984, p. 25, Sholette, 2011). Becker even expands the idea of collective action outwards to include the contributions of the manufacturers, framers, producers of the canvas material, paint and even the paint brushes. He also takes it backwards to include the previous historical work of those artists who created the canonic pieces that have developed the narratives that the newcomers have built upon or rebelled against.

“An artwork was a status conferred on an artifact by the network of people and conventions involved in the “art world”- thereby treating the work as “a candidate for appreciation.”.... places it in a social context.”

(Hobbs, 1997, p. 53)

As a social scientist, Becker saw the artist as just another cultural worker and claims to not ascribe any unique status upon them as Bourdieu appears to do. His focus is not on the unique nature of art as both a cultural and spiritual activity but solely as a market driven consumable artifact built on the human interactions around the creative processes developed within the context of art production.

He proposes that there are standardized modes of support which artists make use of to develop their work and this helps build a common aesthetic through this cooperation. There are creative myths and rationales which understand and can identify when art is of exceptional quality and supports the notion that the creation of these artifacts is good for society and contains the romantic ideals that fill a spiritual void that society cannot do without. Artists are given license to lead lives that are very different from other workers and to behave contrary

to social rules of taste and decency without regards for any of the normal consequences. Through these actions, the myth suggests they can invoke and bring to society artwork that has invaluable magical properties. According to Becker, the unique works of artists appears to be only held in western societies, and those they have influenced, since the time of the Renaissance. To ensure that only the most gifted artists are given this freedom to step outside the norm, society has utilised a number of organisations such as guilds, institutions and academies demanding long apprenticeships and training programmes for the chosen ones. He also raised issues around artists' reputations and the suspicions society has around the authenticity of artists' work. The reputational value of artists directly equals financial value. This has become more so in the world of contemporary and conceptual art where the idea is the art.

Who decides what the standards and rules of the art world's membership should be? There is a collective feedback loop that allows participants in this field of endeavor to know what the requirements for their continued involvement within the art world are, and who have the talents and gifts that allow entry. Through the process of idea development, creation, support working and audience appreciation, together with the critiquing and reviewing of the final piece of work which will judge its appropriateness, the artists can identify their place within the overall structure. If it is unappreciated and unsupported then it will have no impact on the field. If this definition of art is challenged by new artists creating new models of activity then the rationales and conventions need to be updated and refined. This will always be contested as there is a risk that the old-world order can lose out if it is unable to absorb the new rational or embed itself within the developing new paradigm in the world of art's canon.

“An attack on sacred aesthetic beliefs as embodied in particular conventions is, finally, an attack on an existing arrangement of ranked statuses, a stratification system. Remember that the conventional way of doing things in any art utilizes an existing cooperative network, an organized art world which rewards those who manipulate the existing conventions appropriately in light of the associated sacred aesthetic.” (Becker, 1974, p. 767)

Although he asserts his model as a way of understanding the social relationships of art production, he does not claim that all artists need or are forced to be part of this chain of connections to produce artifacts, just that being a part of the collective is more effective and it is easier to be successful.

To illustrate an extreme example of creative support workers within a creative artifact, he highlights the long cast list of technical credits for the 1978 film 'Hurricane' where there is a tradition of giving public credit to every member of the creative team for their contribution. (Becker, 1982, p. 7, 1984, p. 1)

Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi

Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi has developed a simple elegant model of processes in the development of creative artifacts which complements Bourdieu's (1977) thinking and modelling of art and cultural production. (Fulton, J., Paton, E. 2016). Creativity has at times been seen very much as a person-centred gift, grounded in the individual, Csikszentmihalyi explores the greater dynamics at play and offers his systemic approach which defines a structure that highlights the components that make up the creative act. (1975, 1997, p. 24, 1990, p. 200)

His model is made up of three dynamic and interactive elements; the artist bringing creative skills and crafts, set within a clear domain of knowledge within a cultural context, that can have its integrity judged by a group of authoritative experts who understands the domain and make decisions regarding its skilfulness and impact. These three subsystems correspond to the personal, the domain and field of his model through which each has an impact on the other. (Csikszentmihalyi, M., 1997, p. 7)

So, within the system of cultural production, the act of creativity is an interaction between the subsystems of personal, domain and field. The domain supplies information to the person, the person produces a variable response, which may be recognised by the field who will then update the domain with new information in a cyclical way, each informing the other in turn. (Csikszentmihalyi 1990, p. 200, 2003) The work develops, grows and mutates in an evolutionary way, as can be seen through the historical and cultural accounts of art practice, particularly over the last one hundred and forty years. This evolution of any creative movement appears to have a life span of half a generation (Clark, 1990).

It is not a one-way flow, creative artworks are not only assessed and judged before being consecrated into the world of high art, they simultaneously influence and affect the culture through the change in symbolic systems that are impacted by the artwork's acceptance. They generate Dawkins type memes that have to be learned by society and spread through its culture. Once indoctrinated into the world of high art, artists also have an effect on those who engage with their work through that process.

Csikszentmihalyi believes a creative artifact needs to have an effect on the way we think, feel, or act or that artifact cannot be deemed as a creative act, so the gatekeepers have a primary role in managing that interpretive process.

He recognises that the success of creative artists is often determined by chance events, where a connection to a mentor opens doors to successful recognition of the artist by the creative field. (Sternberg, 1999, p. 328) Being a gifted individual is not enough to succeed. As we can see, it is the creative communities who make the specific act of creative art production valued as they nurture new talent and induct them into the art world. These communities share understandings of artistic practice and have common positions on thinking about and appreciating art. They learn from each other and together progressively define what is the nature of art and creativity.

The chances of success happening are increased where the artists interact with bodies and collectives centred around artistic activity such as universities, art schools and centres of artistic practice. Those in the field judge the artistic output through the lens of the cultural and symbolic nature of the domain, identifying what is deemed elite art and rejecting what is unacceptably poor and not worthy of success. These gatekeepers are endowed with the task of making the decisions around who has membership of the art world. Their judgement is based on current trends, specialist training, domain expertise and includes their own cultural bias and personal taste. These trusted experts in the field are those socially interacting around the artistic domain, include lecturers, gallery owners, curators, art critics, agency directors, art buyers and the marketplace who decide who is allowed through the doorway into their cannon of creative excellence and life-time membership.

“It has been said that in the United States 10,000 people in Manhattan constitute the field in modern art.”

(Sternberg, 1999, p. 316)

This esteemed group will decide who meets their criteria for what high art is through the decisions they make around the purchasing value of paintings, sculptures and other creative outputs and what artifacts they will introduce to a public audience and deem be worthy of collecting and of being catalogued. In the sixties it was suggested that artists living in New York in adjoining postcodes to influential art critics like Clement Greenberg were given prominence as to being the next new art movement. Location appears in certain contexts to play a major part in the visibility and definition of cultural values, particularly when it is close to homes of those in powerful positions. Latham and Rogers (2015) believed that physical location was the key to the narrative developed around the modernist art movement; Paris Rive Gauche, New York Greenwich Village and London Bloomsbury were all central areas within its defining boundaries, that is accessible within viewing distance of key art critics.

“Damien Hirst and Tracy Emin, both British artists are the same age and his contemporaries, and it appears that if you're going down that route of getting on the contemporary gallery scene, you're effectively appealing almost exclusively to six to ten people acting as gatekeepers who will decide on who is successful.” (Evans, 2020)

Csikszentmihalyi has also interesting thoughts around the nature of the new and novel work needing to sit within a context of what is old and passé. The new needs to be appropriately different from the old. Original thought does not appear out of thin air. It has to be set within a context of pre-existing ‘objects, rules, representations or notations’. He proposes ‘without rules there cannot be exceptions and without traditions there cannot be novelty’ (Sternberg, 1999, p. 314). Those cultural rules define what creative outputs can be for the field to be fully supportive of new works.

He also saw a direct relationship between creativity and persuasion, as there is a need to persuade and sell all new creative ideas to the cultural gatekeepers.

Greg Sholette

Sholette's focus is on exploring the many creative workers who help support and underpin the art world. He has defined the term 'creative dark matter' to highlight the numbers of underclass cultural producers who are actively hidden from view, unrecognized by the gatekeepers of high art and who are not compensated for their creative work. He gives a historical context for activism in this field and explores the political conflicts generated through the tensions in the system. There is also a detailed look at the broader terrain of art practice in society with him having a particular interest in the mechanics of socially hidden creative works and broader cultural production processes.

Sholette similarly puts forward his understanding of the uneasy but complicit relationship between the art sector and capitalism by stripping away outdated definitions of 'high art', which is simultaneously elevated above and distinct from the capitalist market place while historically being completely encapsulated within it, and this departure from all other deep humanist acts of artistic and cultural practice, which he has defines as 'bare art'. The 'art world incorporated' is constantly sifting through the constantly developing creative art output and detritus embedded in cultural reflections, material and supportive bodies looking for profit (Stallabrass, 2004).

For him, the deep pure human values attached to art and culture and the location within it of the historic and spiritual manifestation is at odds with its relationship to neo-capitalism. High art's exceptional status, struggles to sustain that spiritual position whilst it is located within a fifty-six-billion-dollar capitalist art market place. Within the ever-expanding global arts economy there is more cultural production around the world than ever before. The art world is very selective in its choice of who becomes a member of the small group of elite artistic successes and has no recognition of the majority of the marginalized and hidden cultural producers who work outside of its deliberations. Half of the value of sales in the art auction markets came from only one percent of artist's creative work in 2016 (McAndrew, 2017, p. 14). In Guy Debord's 1958, 'Situationist Manifesto', he describes bourgeoisie culture' as a "rigged game", where dominant powers forbid subversive ideas to have direct access to the public discourse and block their promotion.

Sholette highlights the core values of art and culture being progressively appropriated and embroiled in the political dark dealings of businesses and nation states. These businesses recognise that investments in artistic endeavors improve their corporate image, in addition to other 'direct and tangible benefits' of healing division and social unease. (Maxwell, 2011, p. 339) He has been involved in progressive action with artists working against this agenda to divest cultural activities from inappropriate capitalist ventures, resulting in the scrutiny of corporate cultural support and greater activism and focus within this arena. A number of artist collectives, such as the Art Workers' Coalition Global Ultra Luxury Faction (GULF), Liberate TATE, Decolonise this Place, Debt Fair and Occupy Museums, have protested and effectively taken direct action against these large corporations' infiltration into the art world since the late 1960s, forcing public discourse around their incompatible and problematic activities.

Sholette highlights the pyramid of unsuccessful artists propping up the small elite of successful artists at the top. He calls this underclass of creative producers 'creative dark matter', which has a similar metaphorical structure to the astronomical definition of massive cohesive structures in deep space which hold everything in the cosmos

together. Creative dark matter is hidden from view and is not recognised, particularly by the cultural gatekeepers; buyers, critics, dealers, collectors, curators, and art historians, who are all responsible for supporting and defining cultural taste. Those artists whose creative output is not recognised, ignored, rejected nor given any recognition by the art institutions and establishment includes the amateur, the unofficial, the autonomous, politically active, counter institutional and collaborative creatives who often choose to remain invisible & anonymous from public scrutiny.

He particularly raises the uneconomic production and over supply of arts graduates, of which the majority are going to fail at achieving anything significant in their chosen field is an aberration of neoliberal demand and supply economics.

“We can measure the waste of artistic talent, not only in the thousands of ‘failed’ artists—artists whose market failure is necessary to the success of the few—but also in the millions whose creative potential is never touched ... this glut of art and artists is the normal condition of the art market.” (Duncan, 1983)

The development of digital communication technologies which support neoliberal capitalism and global monetary flows has indirectly opened up opportunities for those surplus creative artists to generate a politically charged undercurrent of activist artistic output which cuts across the traditions of the elite art marketplace utilising these inexpensive communication technologies to spread their creative ideas to an international audience. One manifestation of interventionist cultural activism is ‘Tactical Media’ which has the ability to turn the new forms of digital communications technologies against the power and authority of global corporations and governmental bodies. It utilizes hit and run guerrilla tactics, culture jamming and media pranks including website hacking and flash mobs.

Western welfare culture and left-wing politics have been progressively dismantled after the gains of the world war two post war period having being wiped away during the Thatcherite years in Britain which has left the non-successful artists with no other option than to embrace low paying jobs to support their creative endeavors located in a gig economy.

Just as Bourdieu and Becker see the bigger picture in the overall production networks of the artistic manufacturing process, Sholette also looks into the production process of digital communication technologies which includes the network providers, glass-fibre cable layers, coders, system designers, manufacturers of computers, laptops and mobile phone sub-components, and even includes those involved in the recycling businesses in Asia who dismantle and reclaim value from the technological waste products.

Sholette’s primary interest is in the evolving production processes of the contemporary art world and those who control which artists are chosen and those who are rejected, and working to undermine the system from the outside. He explores the alternate ways that these rejected rebel artists working outside of the artworld, engage with society and make their creative voices heard, utilising digital technologies to re-imagine mainstream politics within the age of enterprise culture. A number of art collectives, political activists and art interventionists, together with other discarded artists looking for a community, are all creatively working with the capacity to undermine the status quo.

“The creative economy embraces entrepreneurship which dominates all aspects of contemporary art from its production and dissemination to its reception” (Chin-tao Wu, 2003)

Sholette believes that the artistic mass of the missing creative dark matter is becoming more dynamic, bringing forth a “revenge of the surplus”. Combined with the deskilling of post-modern art practice and the loss of artisanship in creative practice which has been left to the dark matter fringe, the art world now embraces much more philosophical and conceptual art practices.

“This vast, irregular congregation includes pattern-swapping knitting circles, Flickr photo clubs, garage-kit sculptors, fantasy role-play gamers, devotees of Goth culture, open-source programmers, mash-up music samplers, right-wing groups and militias, and eBay pages filled with the work of both serious and Sunday painters.” (Sholette, 2011, p. 30)

Since 2006, The Artist’s Resale Right (ARR), part of an EU Directive, entitles artists work to receive a royalty each time a piece of their works is resold through an auction house or art market. This really only applies to ‘high art’ being sold through auctions and art market professionals, as private sales are not included. This contributes to the symbolic good’s economic capital and adds to the associated artists or their estates, but does nothing to support those artists struggling at the lower end of the market. Sholette proposes a greater share of art market income be spread more equitably amongst participating artists who are part of the broader art scene.

What is culture and how is it defined?

The second phase of the literary review research will be looking through a lens into the relationship between culture and power interacting with the arts and what support structures have been introduced within the cultural policy development of the Scottish government. It will be introduced through a broad analysis of how culture is defined and progressively narrowing down to that of its role in societies, communities, individual belief systems and in customs supporting art and creativity. How does it relate to both the theorists' positions and to the visual artist interviewees, seeking to understand the arts ecosystem as it is applied to Scotland?

There are many differing ideas of what culture is and what constitutes cultural activity. Culture can be interpreted as having an anthropological social meaning which focusses on the values, behaviours, practices and creative artifacts through which a society expresses itself. From a western perspective, there is a focus on cultural high arts such as painting, sculpture, ballet, opera, classical music, literature, drama and poetry, all being set within a class based context, sitting alongside a more degraded popular culture of fashion, pop music, television, magazines and film.

Historically culture was initially used to describe the development of civilisations and beliefs held by societies. Its scope was narrowed down in the 19th century to focus on broader definitions around the stages in individual state building, progressively zooming into more detail around that of societies, communities and individual belief systems and customs. Now it can cover group activities, and even those of businesses and corporations who define their own work culture and identity.

UNESCO defines culture as a system that is centred on values, lifestyles and beliefs.

“the set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features of society or a social group, that encompasses, not only art and literature, but lifestyles, ways of living together, value systems, traditions and beliefs” (UNESCO, 2002)

In an anthropological context, an ‘essentialist’ view of culture is one that defines a group with unique set of characteristics and attributes which all members must have to belong to that group. It can refer to the practices and values ascribed to any majority or minority social groupings. It is particularly set around the identity of a cultural group and its relationship to other competing groups, usually around status or access to resources (Moore, 1999, p. 35). It is often used as a political tool by these differing cultural groups, who often claim legal protections for their particular groups’ cultural activities. It is also possible for people to be simultaneously members of differing cultural groupings in differing settings. (Lenard, 2020)

A societal culture encompasses the lives of its members “across the full range of human activities, including social, educational, religious, recreational and economic life, encompassing both public and private spheres” (Kymlicka, 1996, p. 76). Culture has an importance in shaping a “collective consciousness” offering a value system that supports the emotional and physical wellbeing of its members. (Walzer, 1983, p. 28)

“a culture which shapes to a large degree their tastes and opportunities, and which provides an anchor for their self-identification and the safety of effortless secure belonging”. (Margalit & Raz, 1990, p. 448)

This assumes that everyone in that culture holds the same identity, values and practices, but this is far too simplistic a position to take, as its members will always have a variety of commitments and tensions around these encompassing cultural practices. In the background, who defines what these norms and values are, how are they encoded and what mechanisms are there to enforce, challenge or contest them? Most people in a community are likely to have fluid boundaries around their cultural beliefs and are also likely to subscribe to multiple cultural groups (Parvin, 2008, p. 321).

Societies shape their culture through shared experiences, language, family structures, education and through their combined history. Members share experiences of ‘social formation’ through a set of practices that are different to other groups (Patten, 2014, p. 39) This common experience does not generate a fixed set of norms, as there is space for members to challenge and contest that shared upbringing without breaking broader common values. Once again, who is responsible for defining the values of these cultural institutions? It is important that the community members have control of the institutions that are central to that shared experience of ‘social formation’. Even then, there will always be issues where institutional members do not fully represent and take on the views of all of the collective members and there is a potential for abuse and extensions of power in the creation and formation of cultural norms and practices without overall agreement amongst them.

Culture evolves through group memberships, their shared narrative accounts, experiences, stories and rituals. Forums and institutions where culture is defined, negotiated and shared need to be robust and resistant to external forces to be sustainable. In addition, a monitoring of internal power structures and dominant voices which have been historically male is required to challenge any oppression of those less powerful within the group. Culture can also be negotiated through dialogue by its members and in their relationships with others. Since members are constructing cultural practices they are dynamic, fluid and not fixed.

“continuously contested, imagined and reimagined, transformed and negotiated, both by their members and through their interactions with others.” (Tully, 1995, p. 11)

Cultural Hegemony

In Marxist philosophy, the term ‘cultural hegemony’ primarily derived from the work of Gramsci (Litowitz, 2000), defines the domination by a ruling class, or dominant rationality, over a culturally diverse society who control and manipulate that society’s culture. It does this through management and definition of the narratives that are allowed, together with all of the rules, values and beliefs it promulgates. The political, social and economic circumstances that advantage and solely benefit the ruling class is promoted as the universally accepted dominant ideology. The ‘ideological state apparatus’ controls legal, education, politics, religions, mass communications and cultural ideologies (Althusser, 2014). Through this, society’s morality, customs and taste are influenced by these institutions, schools, churches, museums and also through popular culture. The supremacy of the dominant class has been achieved through physical force and that of the courts, and also

through a consensual submission of the dominated groups where the controlling groups narratives of intellectual and moral leadership are used to (mis)lead and subdue them (Hoare & Nowell Smith, 1971).

Bourdieu (1984) suggests that historical and cultural assumptions lie behind what is defined as good taste (grand gout). Cultural taste is presented as indicator of social and cultural capital and of educational achievement and it allows those with decision making powers to defend their personal choices against criticism of their discrimination and exclusion of others. Cultural capital is an investment in symbols and meanings used by dominant groups as a way of maintaining their social dominance. (Bourdieu, 1985). People of high taste have distinct social practices and behaviours that Bourdieu calls 'habitus' which are quite different to the social life of those of a lower class. They are detached from the popular culture of that lower class. Habitus creates a unified class identity where options and choices are distinct for that class.

Claims of heightened cultural appreciation and expert knowledge allows that use of power in the subordination of disadvantaged communities and blocks legitimate alternate voices. This illusion perpetuates the myth around the personal inadequacies of those being disempowered due to their lacking the values of bourgeois taste, hides structural and systemic inequalities in the decisions taken around the support of public culture and is an act of 'symbolic violence' imposed upon them. To counter this, is it possible for cultural democracy to be developed through education and by developing new mechanisms of competing voices to challenge those elitist positions. The decision making choices of those in control of resources needs to be more publicly transparent, more inclusive and for there to be clear understandings of the criteria for the allocation of resources, which may help reduce the risks of systemic biases being introduced.

Who defines cultural values?

One key debate concerns the instrumental uses of culture in government policy versus broader cultural values which appreciate culture for its own intrinsic worth. Should the public have a say in what aspects of culture they want to be involved with and what types of cultural outputs should be produced and consumed? Currently there are difficulties in understanding what cultural activities the general population are involved with or even desire., Research into the cultural field has often been reduced to a specific set of measurable parameters that both represent and help reinforce the status quo. The nature of that cultural involvement is set within a context of cultural bias focussing on specific elite activities (Taylor, 2016).

“The value of culture cannot be expressed only with statistics. Audience numbers give us a poor picture of how culture enriches us” (Holden, 2004)

In Eleonora Belfiore (2020) 'Whose cultural value? Representation, power and creative industries' she challenges the discourse and focus that is centred on the economic impact of culture and its value in contributing to economic growth in the UK and advocates for a more holistic approach to its broader values. She raises issues around how power controls the lens in which cultural value is allocated. Theorists such as Janet Wolff (1981) have identified that cultural value is mediated through relational processes where that 'value' is either allocated or denied to an artistic or cultural form or practiced by certain social groups.

“Understanding art as socially produced necessarily involves illuminating some of the ways in which various forms, genres, styles, etc. come to have value ascribed to them by certain groups in particular contexts”
(Wolff, 1981, p. 7)

This relational nature of cultural validation and value allocation operates within social, cultural and political power relations, which are contested and a site of struggle and inequality over ‘meaning, representation and recognition’. Different social groups utilise ‘symbolic power’ to legitimize certain aesthetic and cultural practices and to allocate cultural value to what benefits them (Bourdieu, 1984).

Belfiore’s article highlights the problems with cultural policy discourse, in that power can obscure and hide the asymmetrical distribution of that cultural authority and its unequal influence over the control of symbolic representation and its meaning. As government instrumental narratives are the only agendas discussed, real and substantive issues around competing cultural value, democracy and justice are never allowed to be raised.

Since the process of defining cultural value and allocation of resources is not an impartial one, but rather it is a site of struggle between those in power and those competing with them for investment and resources, the politics of representation, identity, class and taste cannot be unpicked from these competing agendas. Fundamental challenges to democratic accountability require new approaches which acknowledge and address the unequal distribution of cultural value and symbolic power within government policy decisions. Even though they are complex and nuanced, cultural values will always be politically debated and contested. A goal of social inclusion should be aimed for, with open and diverse opportunities to access the means of cultural production which empowers communities to develop and choose their own narratives and values. This does not mean the targeting of groups who appear to be disengaged and disenfranchised with patronizing offerings of passive forms of ‘legitimate’ approved cultural events.

“culture plays a central role in the legitimation of social relations of inequality and in the struggle to transform them.” (Jordan & Weedon, 1995, p. 62)

Often culture is defined and understood through a range of cultural activities. David Throsby (2001, p. 8) classified the cultural activities as comprising music, dance, theatre, literature, visual arts, crafts and multimedia and also included museums and galleries who support the visual arts. It could be perceived that the cultural sector can develop the intellectual, moral and spiritual being of an individual or a community through its generation of symbolic meanings.

“Culture gives meaning and pleasure to life. It encourages us to understand our own place in history and helps us challenge established social convention. Urban regeneration, economic growth and cultural development are all inter-related” (Rogers, 1993)

Throsby also recognises there is a relationship between the cultural outputs of the creative arts and those of the non-cultural fields of architecture, advertising and design who often utilise their work in developing their own parasitic ‘cultural statements’ thereby propagating the symbolic meaning of the works to a broader audience.

Across western Europe the definitions of culture are diverse and national policies differ around the ideologies and resources allocated in the interrelationship between the governmental, public and private sectors. In Throsby’s (2001) study he defines culture as a tool which develops individual, intellectual and artistic cultivation. This has changed over time to encompass ‘the development of civilizations, and especially to describe the set of beliefs held in common by different societies and in the context of the nineteenth century it developed a particular relationship to strategies of nation building. Cultural identity supports a nations distinctiveness. Barker describes “culture” as a “mobile signifier that enables a series of different ways of talking about human activity” (2002, p. 15) and recognises the inherent problems in defining culture since it is a whole way of life and embodied within an active creative lived experience.

Bourdieu (1984, p. 11) identified the nature of conflict in the field of cultural production and its relationship to the dominant class. He also identifies historical and cultural tastes and activities that are approved and canonised by the state, such as opera and ballet which act as symbols of social hierarchy and elite cultural practices which are set within an internationally competitive framework. He also recognised that those class positions utilise education, knowledge and consumption of those expensive consecrated cultural forms, acting as signifiers of power and status which can be utilised in acts of ‘symbolic violence’ against those of lower classes. He identifies ‘legitimate’ cultural goods such as painting or music in comparison to more ‘personal’ ones such as fashion, furniture or cookery and highlighted the close relationship between cultural practices and educational capital and the relevance of class and social origins.

“how certain forms of cultural expression are privileged and with what effect, such that the systematic inequalities of a society can be both highlighted and countered.” (Miller & Yudice, 2002, p. 191)

Holden (2004) recognises the complexity of values expressed through culture. He identifies a need for funding of culture to be not just instrumentalised around targets and economic return but to incorporate those broader often subjective experiences that communities wish to be involved in. Instead of setting agendas, funders should

be responsive to the visions of the cultural organisations and the public they are engaging with. He believes the public should be equal drivers of cultural values addressed through cultural policy and recognises the tensions between governmental funding bodies and a public's needs for equity and fairness, where social inclusion and diversity can flourish and 'culture is seen as an integral and essential part of civil society'. He sees a need for a greater cultural dialogue between cultural funders and the general public. Culture should be driven by its intrinsic value not by its perceived impact and should be seen as an essential and integral part of a civic society. Demystification of cultural policies should be developed through education and empowerment. He identifies there is still a public unhappiness around exclusion from cultural decision making and alienation from publicly funded cultural choices.

Holden (2008) also identifies three types of cultural artifacts; those that are publicly funded, commercially produced and those defined as 'home-made'. In publicly funded culture, definitions are wide and encompassing and as such decisions are made by gatekeeping bureaucrats around that funding which are always open to being challenged regarding transparency and the fairness of the decisions made. Definitions of quality and excellence ascribed to 'high art' creative artifacts which are applied by the cultural gatekeepers are used to protect the status quo and the dominant class, actively blocking contributions by outsiders, hence the reasons why homogenous Eurocentric, white male creatives have been central to the art world for so long (McMaster, 2008). Commercially produced artifacts are driven primarily by business decisions around growth and profitability in sync with meeting the needs of customers. Funding of commercial cultural projects are still controlled and decisions are made by an elite group managing and holding the financial resources. Finally, home-made cultural activities often not recognised by the more official types of culture include everything from music, fashion, knitting, blogging, cooking, Instagram pictures and TikTok video uploads. The internet is a powerful enabler of the communication and development of cultural artifacts to a global audience. All three types of cultural production have a range of audiences for their work and there is not only fluidity between the types of creative material produced, there are also new opportunities for these artifacts to merge and develop across cultural boundaries with opportunities for the development of new audiences, collaborations and commercial projects. Resources involved in the creation of culture are now more easily available, such as musical instruments, video and sound editing software, online video support and multiple offline entertainment venues and platforms. Quality products are seen across all types of cultural artifacts. Everyone can be a musician, DJ or film maker and curate their own cultural preferences and define themselves by their cultural consumption and production which sits within a global artistic and creative culture. Cultural democracy is about supporting communities and artists with what they want to do ... not what governments want them to do (Holden, 2011).

Cultural policy development of the both the UK and Scottish government

Cultural policy is defined as strategic actions taken by government in managing the cultural sector. Since the post war, western governments have developed cultural policies to enhance the lives of their citizens through state funding of high culture within the visual arts, theatre and music. These were always centred around concepts of artistic excellence and meritocracy. In the broadest of terms this also latterly encompassed entertainment, leisure and recreation activities which could also include film, broadcast, heritage and fashion.

Historically, wealthy benefactors and philanthropists have supported the development of art and cultural resources in UK and US, such as in the development of museums and theatres as part of an educational strategy to civilise the masses through the arts (Belfiore & Bennett, 2006, p. 143). For example, a new museum and art gallery in the West End of Glasgow was funded by profits from an exhibition in 1888 managed by a society of business men who gifted it to the Glasgow City Corporation in 1901. Industrialist, William Burrell was another local benefactor who left his extensive collection to the Glasgow City Council for the education of the city's residents which is now held in the Burrell Museum located in Pollock Country Park. The Peoples Palace Museum and Winter Gardens were commissioned in the 1890's by Glasgow councilor Robert Crawford, who was the chairman of both the City Council's Health and Galleries and Museums Committees. He had a belief that the city residents had both a cultural and physical need for this type of resource (O'Neill, 1998).

The cultural policy field was primarily established after WWII where a number of cultural initiatives were developed by the UK and in other European countries, where there was a formalizing of cultural policy making which was part of the development of the welfare state. France created the Ministry of Culture in 1959, the United States established the National Endowment for the Arts in 1965, a number of bodies were set up to have responsibility for Nordic regional culture in the 1970's who introduced supportive funding schemes for individual artists and the Netherlands also established a Ministry of Culture (Zimmer & Toepler, 1999, Mangset, 2020). Totalitarian states such as in the Soviet eastern block of countries and Mao's Cultural Revolution also have a history of the utilisation of cultural policies and the arts within their differing communist party regimes as part of their Marxist political doctrines.

The UK's arts sector has been a leading light in the development of cultural policy and in 1942, the Scottish Committee of the Council for the Encouragement of Music and the Arts (CEMA) was formed. It was absorbed and renamed as the Scottish Committee of The Arts Council of Great Britain (ACGB) in 1947. Then its name was changed to the Scottish Arts Council in 1967 but was still a committee of ACGB until its devolution to the Scottish Office in 1994.

The Arts Council of Great Britain was set up by John Maynard Keynes, who in attempting to safeguard its artistic freedom used the 'arm's length from government' organisational model in setting up an independent board holding executive power. This was deemed important as it distanced itself from political interference from governments, their funding decisions and from problematic state bureaucracy. The Scottish committee of the ACGB used arguments around its nationhood, its distinct national characteristics and unique cultural heritage to both receive enhanced funding and with a 'double' arms-length position, gained a high level of independence and autonomy from both the ACGB and Westminster government. Critics regard the arms-length approach as

just an illusionary tactic that disguises more subtle political influences of the arts as funding resources and board nominations are always politically driven. In addition, the lack of transparency within these organisations as to how they allocate resources is a fundamental issue that needs to be resolved (Talfan Davies, 2007).

Westminster politics saw swings in position around the arts as each new government made changes to their cultural & funding priorities. In 1965 a post of Arts Minister was created by the Labour party and held by Jennie Lee, and the first ever government White Paper on the arts, *A Policy for the Arts: The First Steps* was also published. The government proposed a “new social climate” for cultural activities, allowing ordinary people to have a greater participation in the arts, and it supported more regional developments away from the metropolitan centre in an active democratisation of culture (HM Government, 1965). The Scottish committee was renamed the “Scottish Arts Council” within ACGB’s charter due to the white paper’s policy directives around enhancing the impact of the arts in the regions, and also may have been rooted in response to the upswing of nationalism in Scotland where a second Scottish National Party MP to Westminster was elected (Galloway & Jones, 2010).

Public sector reforms came with the Thatcher Government in 1979 who cut arts funding and directed arts organizations to look for alternative paths of support and sponsorship which were supposed to be found in the private sector (Hewison, 1995). In this environment, Arts councils were subjected to greater scrutiny and the introductions of targets were applied to them, as now public funding needed to show that it was efficient and effective. Funding was primarily centralised and now came directly from the Westminster government. The Scottish Arts Council was privileged during this process and avoided the impact of these financial changes due to the historic principle of the arms-length relationship in addition to their claimed national and cultural identity differences. However, tensions increasingly arose when the Secretary-General, Roy Shaw challenged the disparity in funding of amateur arts organizations across the regions, where Scotland and Wales had been able to continue to disperse funds that English arts organisations were unable to access (Shaw, Mason, 1981).

In a wider organisational change in the arts in 1994 amid the ongoing debate around devolution, SAC became a body appointed and funded by the Secretary of State for Scotland. Prior to devolution the Scottish Office had no part to play in co-ordinating Scottish cultural policy even though it was responsible for all funding of the national cultural institutions and agencies. After devolution opportunities arose for the Scottish Executive to develop a national culture policy with a dedicated Cabinet Minister. This resulted in greater scrutiny and accountability of the Scottish Arts Council, with the relationship now becoming “arms-length with hands on”, (Taylor, 1997, p. 465) now being fully integrated and supporting government policy directions. The decisions made by SAC were directly associated with government policy and through this accountability was now shifted onto government ministers.

This was highlighted after the Scottish Opera's financial crisis in 2003, where the Scottish government had to intervene and a decision was taken that funding would in future be allocated directly to the national performing arts companies who were then subject to greater financial controls, targets and delivery measurements. Ring fencing of specific outcomes were the key instruments used in managing creative expenditure in a similar way to the standard accounting practices of local government (Galloway, 2004).

After devolution the SAC progressively lost its independence and became much more of an agency of government (Madden, 2009, p. 27). This loss of the arms-length political relationship to government left the SAC in a similar position to its English counterparts. Treasury initiatives have been focussing on cost saving through public sector efficiencies during the Westminster New Labour administration since 1997. The Scottish administration has had to operate within the broader political agenda and finances always set by the UK government. This has led to more convergence and uniformity in governance and policy, both in the UK and within Scottish politics. Also, as the SAC distributed funds on behalf of the National Lottery there was a requirement for the use of a more rigorous management criteria which has been set at the UK level to allocate funding, which also has had a significant impact.

The newly devolved Scottish administration's cultural policy was developed in sync with the UK Westminster driven Department of Culture, Media and Sport and embraced the ideals of a creative economy encompassing the arts, and the development of the creative and cultural industries. (Schlesinger, 2009).

Throsby's (2001) connection between culture and nation building has a particular resonance for post devolution Scotland in 1999, as First Minister, Jack McConnell's St Andrew's Day speech in 2003 referred to the now devolved cultural policy sitting at the centre of government and it being crucial to the development of Scotland's national identity (Bonnar, 2014). In it he stated that culture would be at the core of government and that all individuals would have access to culture with art for all. He believed that creative enterprise should be the next major focus of society and be on a par with health, housing and education.

The opportunity of developing a collective culture and national identity was important for the new government to build upon after public consultations were carried out around the importance and value of culture to its institutions and the arts in 1999. These public consultations were looking for answers to questions concerning its meaning, strategic aims, roles of national institutions, education, international relations and support of its indigenous culture (Bonnar, Keenlyside, 2000).

In response to the consultation the Scottish government proposed four over-arching objectives.

“Promote creativity, the arts, and other cultural activity, celebrate Scotland's cultural heritage in its full diversity, realise culture's potential contribution to education, promoting inclusion and enhancing people's quality of life and assure an effective national support framework for culture.”

(Scottish Executive, 2000, p. 7)

Although it appeared that they were well resourced to implement cultural provision, local authorities did not have statutory responsibility to deliver it and due to this, problems in the resourcing of these cultural activities and developing inclusive policies were varied across Scotland. In addition, arts and culture activities were often aggregated in broader expenditure making it really difficult to understand exactly where these resources were actually being used (CTEEAC 2019).

The Scottish Executive (2000) believed that defining culture was problematic and worked with a wide ranging definition. Although very broad it still had the capacity to negate other forms of cultural participation in the everyday experiences of working class people:

“ideas, customs and traditions, beliefs, habits of thinking, religions, languages, identities, mythologies and histories, and the expression of these in myriad forms such as poetry and prose, visual arts, music, song, theatre, comedy, dance, architecture, design, costume, film, photography and a range of crafts. It is represented in the natural and historical landscape; archaeology; buildings; museum, gallery and library collections; archives and records; and shared memories and experiences. It includes aspects of lifestyle, such as sport and leisure” (Scottish Executive, 2000, p. 4).

Through the mechanism of public funding, the Scottish government legitimizes certain cultural activities with their approval and makes them worthy of support. Through this action it devalues other types of cultural activities, giving them a lesser validity. Working class leisure activities such as pantomime and musicals in theatres which are likely to be more popular than both opera and ballet would be seen as having less cultural benefits and as such would most likely fail to meet the standards required to access equal government funding support. (McCall, & Playford, 2012). They do not have access to ring fenced government funding. A Scottish Arts Council Survey even excluded certain types of music such as pop, rock & country music and even cinema from its cultural survey. Viewing and accessing cultural activities through alternate media such as TV programming, radio or online streaming of events were also not regarded in the same light as the acts of physically attending public theatre or concert events. A narrow group of decision makers in government are responsible for the choices and forms of culture that will be offered for passive consumption, claiming those choices enhance the quality of life for Scotland’s communities (Kawashima, 2006). The implementation of more democratic forms of cultural opportunities and a focus on the active consumption as opposed to passively consuming culture would be more democratic.

The Scottish parliament reviews of cultural funding post-devolution resulted in the development of the National Cultural Strategy. After the Quinquennial Review of SAC in 2002 and the Cultural Commission’s National Review of Culture in 2005, a decision was made to create a new national cultural development agency called Creative Scotland to replace the SAC, and which would also absorb Scottish Screen. Concerns were raised around the political context in which the decision to amalgamate the two organisations were made, as part of public sector reform and a cost cutting efficiency drive. There were also fears around the bureaucratic centralised decision making process, which would cut out the involvement and influence of the artistic community who had been active participants and beneficiaries of the older system. Responses to the draft bill consultation included submissions from the Glasgow School of Art and Scottish Artists Union raising concerns around the dangers of a focus on the instrumentalisation of cultural impact rather than on the intrinsic aspects of culture and around the failure to recognise the importance of funding support of individual artists in their practice (Scottish Government, 2007).

In 2007 a minority SNP government came to power after eight years of a Labour and Liberal Democrat coalition but the style of government in relation to culture seems not to have changed. It appears that the SNP has moved towards a greater instrumentalisation of this area, by implemented a more efficiency focused, economically

driven model through their National Performance Framework. The resulting decision making around cultural funding looked to be primarily an economic one, rather than recognising the breadth of more subjective and situated cultural forms. In response, Fiona Hyslop, the Scottish minister with responsibility for culture, attempted to distance herself from the instrumental approach and ‘promised to celebrate culture in and of itself’ (Hyslop, 2013).

More latterly the independence driven nationalist agenda of the SNP has developed further their Scottish government cultural policy, promoting and celebrating a distinctive package of belief systems that highlight cultural beliefs and activities which would clearly differentiate it from the rest of the UK. Since culture encompassed a ‘set of attitudes, expressions and customs’ (Throsby, 2001) common to differing societies, opportunities exist to build on those differences in growing the concept of nationhood through their policy decisions. However, there are challenges to how government approaches cultural development, which needs to align with the identities of a diverse population and which needs a collective approach. What are indigenous, traditional and authentic cultural artforms that should be financially supported and how should they be regarded in relationship to an economic, instrumentalised control of cultural activity?

“...the Government sees no advantage in a statutory definition of “culture” [...] even if it were possible to agree a definition of “culture” in the Parliament” (Scottish Parliament, 2008)

Cultural funded bodies and organisations such as Creative Scotland are primarily integrated tools of governance and are used as mechanisms to influence the cultural landscape which is overseen by the Scottish Executive. However, there is still a need for the Scottish Executive to create an illusion that they are still taking an arms-length approach. It can be recognised that control and funding of cultural activities are part of a broader governmental set of policies that are utilised to achieve certain desired outcomes such as in economic and social policy impact. This is often why there is conflict between what cultural activities the broader community wishes to be involved in and where governments wish to give financial support.

After the financial crash of 2008 government policy in the UK began to focus on austerity and cost saving. This further impacted funding for cultural policies which became more economic outcome focused and quantitative strategic narratives further degrading welfare policies and cultural support.

In 2012, one hundred artists lobbied Creative Scotland due to its changing and expanding criteria for arts funding, acting on behalf of a perceived Scottish artworld and cultural community. They believed it was inappropriate for non-artist bureaucrats to be solely in charge of defining and controlling access to public funding of the arts where instrumentalised policies of control would be implemented, ignoring the intrinsic value of their work. As a side issue to this, those artists believed that the involvement of the broader community in the decisions regarding what types of culture should be subsidised was not desirable.

“that audience participation in decisions regarding the supply of subsidised culture is undesirable, as they believe that “existing resources are best managed in an atmosphere of trust between those who make art and those who fund it” (BBC, 2012)

Ongoing crisis have surrounded Creative Scotland since its inception and particularly in 2013 where the cultural community were united in their dissatisfaction with its choices of funding decisions. Online networks facilitated the organisation of dissenters as a political group who wished to give their views on the subject. It has allowed those engaging to lead conversations on key issues rather than have government set the agendas and limits of discussion (Culture Counts, 2012). Perhaps in an attempt to close down debate Creative Scotland has also taken the position that cultural policy development will be limited to “artists, creative practitioners and staff” (Creative Scotland, 2012). This appears to be at odds with their ongoing commitment to ‘increase public engagement and participation’ where representation from broader forums and relevant communities could be missed thereby excluding the broader public from dialogue around cultural provision in Scotland (Creative Scotland, 2012, Stevenson, 2013, 2014).

There is certainly the perception that government subsidies clearly favour ‘high art’ through its ring fenced funding at the expense of ‘low art’ and it is yet to facilitate the democratisation of culture where everyone has equity of access to their own choice of cultural activities. To do this, the current decision makers need to engage with policy makers and the general public to facilitate the legitimisation of culture for all. There is a need for state funded cultural programming to acknowledge the rich variety of cultural activities and their importance in developing social capital, networks and communities and for resources to be made available within an organisational structure which can deliver policy objectives (Stevenson, 2013, Miles & Gibson, 2016).

Creative Scotland’s instrumentalised approach to funding of the arts is now appearing at odds with the UK government’s cultural position where the focus appears to becoming more aligned with quality of outputs and a more rounded assessment of success over time.

“...we must free artists and cultural organisations from outdated structures and burdensome targets, which can act as millstones around the neck of creativity.” (McMaster, 2008 p. 4)

Cultural policy and urban regeneration

In the 80's through the cultural renaissance in countries in western Europe, cultural strategies were developed primarily with policies that decentralised resources to local and provincial government across the regions particularly in Italy, Spain and France. In Britain, running against the trend of other European states, local authority power and resourcing was eroded by the Thatcher government's centralisation policies (Travers, 1989) although their cultural policy was seen as an exception to this. Regional Arts Associations evolved into Regional Arts Boards' whose funding was increased in an attempt to redress the bias towards London based institutions. Arts support funding in the UK in 1987 was considerably less than other EU countries, and five times less than Germany for example.

The socialist cultural policy emphasis on personal and community based participation in the arts that had been developed up to the 70's was overturned by more right wing conservative governments. Culture was appropriated and defined in terms of economic impact, investment and employment generation being central to the development of leisure activities and tourism. Policy directives became more focussed on urban redevelopment and joint investment with private developers in areas of urban regeneration, moving away from traditional heavy industries and industrial decline to a post-industrial society. Major branding exercises for cities centred on prestigious flagship cultural projects such as Vienna's Museum Quarter, the Kunsthau in Gratz, Hamburg's Elbphilharmonie concert hall, the Museumsufer Frankfurt, the Guggenheim museum in Bilbao, Oslo's new opera house, Copenhagen Opera House and more recently the V&A Design museum in Dundee were supported. These projects have been promoted as central catalysts for inward investment and the regeneration of inner cities and waterfronts (Bianchini, 1993).

Events such as international Jazz festivals giving a global promotion of a location will bring in top musicians to play at events which are open to a local audience in addition to them being marketed as part of an international tourism strategy. So, they stimulate the economy, develop the community's appreciation and understanding of the medium and build on the brand of the location which is in competition with other global urban centres. As part of a strategic package of cultural products, such as the awe-inspiring architecture, concert halls and city-based orchestras, art exhibitions, music festivals, fashion weeks and sporting events, it is claimed that it can attract and retain international financial investment through cultural development and offerings of a 'city of luxury' or of a 'gentrified city' (Marcuse, 1989, p. 703, O'Hagan, 1998).

At this time Glasgow's urban regeneration projects centred on its flagship cultural enterprise, the development of The Burrell Collection in the grounds of Pollock Park which first opened in 1983, followed by the National Garden Festival in 1988 held on old docklands which was one of five national garden festivals being held in the UK. This built momentum towards its bid for the European City of Culture in 1990. Since then the city has enjoyed an economic and cultural renaissance in the arts and music. Glasgow also has developed the second largest contemporary arts scene in the UK, where it promotes the annual Glasgow International arts festival. It was also the host city for a major sporting event in 2014 when it held the Commonwealth Games. The SSE Hydro performance arena opened in 2013 and is the third busiest music venue in the world (Scotsman, 2016).

John Myerscough's report (1988) included an analysis of the economic importance of the arts in Glasgow, which contributed to the City of Culture year bid. His research highlighted the arts as a mass employer, being a major contributor to the economy, in developing tourism and contributing to urban renewal. In addition, he recognised that there were additional broader benefits in improving the image and attractiveness of a city to its residents and investors. His research findings which promoted such a positive outcome were of interest to local authorities and regional cultural strategists looking to develop their own local economies. Cultural goods and services generate ten billion pounds to the British economy yearly. Bianchini identifies the use of cultural policy as an "image strategy" within this process (Bianchini & Parkinson, 1993, p. 15).

"boosting the confidence of the business community by adding to the vitality and vibrancy of an area, thereby contributing to quality of life and longer term appreciation of property values"

(Myerscough, 1988, p. 1)

A number of critics of Myerscough's research include economist Gordon Hughes (Belfiore, 2002) who challenged his methodologies and results. Holden and Bailey et. al. also believed that his methods of assessing impact of cultural institutions were flawed and noted there had been no long-term tracking of results (Holden, 2004, p. 17, Bailey, Miles & Stark, 2004, p. 50).

Complementing Myerscough's work, is research into the usefulness of art initiatives which can be used to address socio economic problems and the social benefits they can bring. Matarraso's 'Use or Ornament? The Social Impact of Participation in the Arts' (1997) focusses on understanding the social impact and benefits of cultural arts activities on the lives of participants and offered soft, qualitative methodologies and research outputs, identifying a detailed analysis of the benefits of involvement (Belfiore, 2002, p. 98). It challenged the financial lens brought to bear on cultural activities that miss the inherent value and the real purpose of the arts, "which is not to create wealth but to contribute to a stable, confident and creative society" (Matarraso, 1997). His study into the social impact of arts programmes was carried out highlighting the wide range of benefits participation in the arts brings to communities. They are educational, support personal and community development, increase participants' confidence, help in building networks and improve employment opportunities. They can influence social change, offer health and environmental improvements and can be part of a broader community-centred development strategy leading to a stronger cultural life and bring real socio-economic benefits to those involved.

For example, in the context of urban regeneration, community arts projects can improve social development and cohesion, and change the lived environment of those involved through celebrations of local culture and traditions. In addition to enhancing the health, wellbeing and motivation of its participants, it increases community empowerment and self-reliance, and the promotion of cultural activity can be viewed by the general public as generating new interests and understandings (Matarraso, 1997). It can also have secondary benefits through increasing international prestige, promoting tourism and developing an environment of creativity that support journalists, advertisers and commercial television creators. However, it is not a panacea for all ills and needs appropriate funding and expertise for it to be developed successfully. The work needs to be built upon and to be part of an ongoing funded cultural strategy to maximise its impact. Merli (2002) is critical of Matarasso's

work on account of his belief that the work is driven by flawed methodologies and political ideology, although Matarasso notes there is no evidence to support these allegations (Matarasso, 2003, p. 341).

As the work of Myerscough and Matarasso show, the culture sector including the creative and cultural industries has the capacity to generate both economic and social benefits. Both researchers' findings have been of use in understanding the economic and social values that are central to the cultural policy debate.

In addition, the work of Richard Florida identifies valuable elements which support inner city regeneration. Florida's (2002) identifies effective regeneration strategies which at their core seek to attract the 'creative class' of technology and financial workers, artists and musicians, together with gay and lesbian communities, back into city centres, as he recognises that this socio grouping within a neighbourhood is attractive to property developers and investors who recognise their relationship to gentrification and refurbishment of the areas involved which push up housing prices and improve neighbourhoods often resulting in pushing out the original working class residents due to those rising housing prices (Florida, 2015, p. 78). These highly educated knowledge creatives draw in low paid service sector workers to support their enterprises. This builds on Griffith's identification of a service class supporting the creative and cultural industries (Griffiths, 1993, p. 42). Griffiths challenges the conclusions of Florida and believed that investment decisions are far less connected to neighborhood developments than the research had stated. He also believed that the investment is focused towards cultural consumption, not in supporting the actual creation of culture (Griffiths, 1993, p. 43).

There was little evidence to support claims that there was any positive impact on economic development in Glasgow (Bianchini & Parkinson, 1993, p. 45) This is also supported by McGuigan's research into the Greater London Council's cultural industry strategy, proposing that the strategy benefitted conceptual innovations rather than any practical achievements and questions who the beneficiaries of investments in cultural services actually were (McGuigan, 1996, p. 83)?

The cultural sector has also become more aligned with the creative industries, this is in addition to having a focus on building relationships between cultural activities, urban culture and economic and urban regeneration. Often there were public-private business partnerships between government and investors such as developers, financial institutions and notable corporations who were invited to support and co-fund government aims. Development of the creative and cultural industries sector has been promoted as a solution to industrial decline and the shift to a post-industrial economy of increased globalisation, liberalisation and privatisation after the economic recessions of the early and late 70's. This was at a time where there was a shift in globalised capital flows and the development of trans global supply chains, where manufacturing sectors were transferred to lower cost economies primarily in the far east and south America. Sector based strategies around the creative industries were planned, to develop local hub based economies such as in the software, game and film industries hub which is located in Dundee. Revitalisation strategies, first developed in America in the 70's and 80's within the inner cities utilised retail parks, leisure facilities, flagship arts venues and museums to add value to the mix of housing and commercial developments that were being developed.

'cultural policy has become an increasingly significant component of economic and physical regeneration strategies in many west European cities' (Bianchini, 1993, p. 1)

In big mega events all over the world, such as the London Olympics, massive regeneration packages are included in the offerings. The media promotes a construction of national identity, portraying “an idealized version of society, reminding society of what it aspires to be rather than what it is” (Bernstein & Blain, 2003, p.13).

There is a downside to this however as local communities are disrupted and often displaced to allow the new mega sporting events and Olympic villages to spring up. Residents are forcibly removed so that areas can be regenerated. What that means is that property developers can exploit the land where communities have lived, often for generations, to develop competing athletes’ accommodation, sports facilities and venues and later on after the events have concluded and moved on, to sell the upmarket desirable residential and business properties to more affluent buyers. The original occupants never reoccupy their neighbourhoods after being dispersed to other areas not of their choosing and are easily forgotten in the media hype.

Scottish Government's cultural policy (2015-20)

The Scottish governments cultural policy framework has been developed in relationship to the visual arts sector over the last six years (2015-2020), and this research explores all the documentation associated with its inception. This sits within an ongoing debate around the development of a National Cultural Strategy which was started and has been running since devolution of the Scottish government in 1999. Attempts had been made before the current cultural policy document for the Scottish government to engage with relevant bodies to articulate 'definitions of culture' and the extent to which it should include the arts, creativity and the creative industries' (Bonnar, 2014, p 136).

"Arts for all can be a reality, a democratic right and an achievement of the 21st century. I believe this has the potential to be a new civic exercise on a par with health, housing and education – the commitment to providing and valuing creative expression for all." (McConnell, 2003)

The research looks at whether the government's evolving cultural policy supports Scottish artists' creative practice and what measures it is taking to support them in developing their careers. Secondly it will look at the cultural policy support mechanisms currently in place which are being delivered through Creative Scotland and by Local Authorities.

In my literature review to date I have discovered that there have been quite extensive mapping exercises commissioned by the current Scottish National Party government into the creative industries in Scotland covering different sectors. These mapping exercises have followed a very neo-capitalist perspective and take very little interest in those who do not meet with Scottish government's 'excellent art' and Creative Scotland's 'high status' and 'international value' criteria. Their policy agenda has followed a very Becker & Bourdieuan model of creative worker hierarchy and appear to be driven primarily by hidden bureaucratic value judgements, economic forces, desire for international prestige and the extraction of economic value in this area.

It will also sit this research into government policy alongside the academic social theoretical frameworks discussed earlier, which position support of visual artists within a socially constructed hierarchical structure locating successful internationally acclaimed 'excellent' art producing cultural workers at one end of the spectrum and at the other those unsupported failed artists, all tightly enmeshed within a structure which is primarily controlled by elite gatekeepers who decide on which artists to financially support and which are rejected. It will also look at the potential broader roles it can take in supporting and developing cultural and creative activities in local communities.

How much does the Government's cultural policy framework support visual artists in sustaining their practice in 2020 and what ways are they able to help artists in generating income to cover living costs and expenses? Does support come directly from government, Creative Scotland or through local authorities? The Scottish Artists Union in 2018 carried out a survey asking members in the creative sector for information on their business status which shows that approximately eighty percent of those members are registered as self-employed. Sixty percent of members income is under £10k. Twenty nine percent have a turnover of between £10-25k and five percent have earnings of more than £25k. Artists are likely to be self-employed, employed by

small to medium companies, publicly funded or working for charitable organisations. Only twenty five percent of the union's members have received any form public funding from government through its agency Creative Scotland.

So, what are the ways that artists can be supported in the political sphere by governmental agencies and strategic policies? The Scottish government has a number of funding schemes to help support both arts organisations and creative artists. At a time when creative artists in Scotland face massive challenges in finding income to support their art practice, they are impacted not only through the chaos surrounding the massive economic downturn and depression currently being induced by Covid-19 and the global pandemic, but also by the Brexit withdrawal of the British government from the structures of the European Union which will conclude by the end of 2020. This will add to all the potential issues that artists have in accessing funding and being given any support from the Scottish governmental and regional public finances.

Culture Strategy for Scotland 2020

In February 2020, A Culture Strategy for Scotland was published by The Scottish Government which responded very positively to the recommendations submitted by the Culture, Tourism, Europe and External Affairs Committee's report published in December 2019 which looked into the future of arts funding. It was informed by the 'National Culture Conversation' which engaged with organisations, artists, musicians and creatives who helped shape the agendas taken forward. The strategy recognizes the strength and value in developing Scotland's culture and creativity sectors as part of a vibrant, progressive nation and looked to develop new partnerships, which were local, national and international.

It sets out a collaborative vision for culture and the guiding principles, ambitions and aims which will enable it to continue to flourish, evolve, and help to stimulate its transformational power across society.

(Scottish Government, 2020, p, 8)

The government's 'Festival Expo Fund' was set up to support artists and practitioners in developing creative collaborations in international settings as part of a remit to showcase and promote Scottish creative talent overseas. The Scottish government's network of international hubs enhances its profile abroad and develops opportunities to support their cultural diplomacy work.

The cultural strategy document locates culture at the centre of all policy areas which includes health & wellbeing and education, and it is seen as a key driver of economic growth. Exports from the creative industries in Scotland were £3720 million in 2017, which was 4.6% of its total for that year. The value had increased by 28.7% over the previous year. Synergies also exist between the creative industries and tourism, energy, community development and in international relations.

The Scottish government understands the important role of artists and the creative sector in empowering and bringing whole communities together. It believes that sharing cultural activities and experiences helps foster inclusivity, connection and greater tolerance. It enhances the lives of those living in mainland populations in cities & towns and in rural populations and island communities, where over two hundred unique cultural festivals are being scheduled each year, which are important to both the national and local economies. They have identified that cultural activities could be utilized as tools for tackling a range of policy issues around inequality, identity and social cohesion in local communities. They could also be used as platforms supporting and raising environmental & green issues. The document celebrates the diversity and breadth of cultures in Scotland and believes 'everyone has the right to participate freely in the cultural life of the community' and also recognises and wishes to develop each community's own unique local culture which generates a distinct sense of identity and pride.

Fiona Hyslop, the Cabinet Secretary for Economy, Fair Work and Culture has proposed that a 'National Partnership for Culture' be established to advise and influence government on cultural support issues and in realising the national outcomes for culture. It will support the delivery of the culture strategy and continue the national culture conversation. The partnership will be independently chaired and members will be drawn from 'all cultures, languages and communities' bringing together creative practitioners, culture workers, academics

and policy makers to develop partnerships and collaborative working. There will also be a Measuring Change Group which will be monitoring activity contributing to the National Outcome for Culture and the Cultural Strategy, building on previous research and identifying what indicators will be required to quantify impacts of change. The Scottish Government recognises the need to support artists and creative practitioners in producing ‘excellent’ creative work.

Several new pilot studies have been announced in the creative strategy; there is the ‘Arts Alive’ programme of activities which will be developed in conjunction with the Scottish Book Trust, where artists will receive fair payments for their work to bring cultural experiences to local communities through their interactions with nurseries, creative residences in schools and in libraries situated in areas of multiple deprivation. Skills Development Scotland working with Applied Arts Scotland are offering a new apprenticeship scheme delivery in the visual arts, crafts and design fields. There is also the intention to support Arts Culture Health and Wellbeing Scotland in all forms of cultural engagement, working to improve health, wellbeing and in addressing inequality issues. A Creative Communities programme will be launched in partnership with Creative Scotland and Inspiring Scotland, building upon the current place-based programme, to help empower communities to develop their own cultural activities, demonstrating the potential that arts and culture can bring to enriching the lives of individuals and communities impacted by it.

There is still a need to actively support artists in achieving fair remuneration for their work, even though regulations regarding the national living wage have been in place since 2016. Artists in the creative sector deserve to be able to make a living like everyone else and not be treated as a unique group with its own rules and terms of business. The Scottish government has recognized this issue and now insists that clear budgets outlining actual hours worked ensure that appropriate payment for creative work is included to ensure artists and creative professionals can earn a fair living wage. Creative Scotland now provides rates of pay guidance, highlighting codes of practice and industry standards, to its applicants in response to this. The government is committed to being a Fair Work Nation by 2025. They also have committed to exploring a feasibility study into developing a Citizen’s Basic Income to understand the opportunities and challenges that this can bring.

The Scottish Government also set up Senscot which is responsible for developing *Social Enterprise Networks*, supporting an ecosystem of community activists and social enterprises. They are supported by cultural and creative social entrepreneurs who include film studios, design agencies, theatres, museums, musicians and art centres, who have access to a ‘Cultural - Local Social Enterprise Network’ (SEN) which will support cultural and creative social enterprises make connections and develop collaborations in their local area.

Due to the complexity of public funding of the arts and the challenges of identifying and measuring outputs and impacts from that funding, a recommendation was also made, proposing an independent National Cultural Observatory be set up to liaise with local government and other important stakeholders. Cultural Observatories were first proposed by UNESCO in 1998. Their function is to monitor and analyse cultural activity and to support various governmental policy decisions with supporting data. They are responsible for both monitoring of activities and focussing on special research projects.

Creative Scotland & Creative Europe Desk

The Scottish government has set up a range of funding routes for the creative art sector through its non-departmental public body, Creative Scotland, established in 2010, with a board of directors solely appointed by them. This organisation was created through a merger of the Scottish Arts Council and Scottish Screen after a report by the Cultural Commission, headed by James Boyle, reviewed the Scottish arts and culture environment which was published in 2005 at the request of the newly devolved Scottish parliament which had been established in 1999. The report looked at issues around Scotland's national identity and focussed on national renewal which would utilise Scotland's distinctive cultures as a central theme and develop the creative and cultural industries as an economic driver (Blain, 2013).

Creative Scotland sees itself as a development agency, funder and advocate on behalf of the arts, screen and creative industries (Creative Scotland, 2019). They also see their role as exporters of outputs of Scottish creative businesses, organisers of cultural exchanges of artists, coordinators of imports of international experiences and having responsibility for the development of cultural diplomacy promoting and strengthening Scotland's unique cultural identity. They also look to develop its importance as a global centre of the arts, screen and diverse creative industries.

Creative Scotland's 2019/20 annual budget was approximately £92m (Creative Scotland, 2019) of which the Scottish government's contribution is two thirds, at £62 million. Its currently tenuous funding relationship with the National Lottery, whose income has been impacted by competing lottery schemes, has resulted in a fluctuating income stream which supplies around the additional third of Creative Scotland's funding of £28 million. (Creative Scotland, 2019) in regards to its support of arts and culture projects in Scotland. Comparative research shows this funding support to the creative industries is significantly lower than in comparable EU countries, and it is set within the constraints of a funding regime imposed by the UK government. (Drew Wylie Projects Ltd, 2019, p. 7).

Creative Scotland offers creative organisations up to three years of funding support. There is 'Open Project' funding which supports individual artists for up to two years and finally there is 'Targeted Funding' which is aimed at helping specific sectors, initiatives and projects. In their 'Regular Funding 2018-21: The Network' proposal (Creative Scotland, 2021), they set out their purpose and ambitions for the sector. They have created a network of one hundred and two 'Regularly Funded Organisations' (RFOs) who are given £101.6m of Grant in Aid funding and three years of budget commitment from the Scottish Government. (Creative Scotland, 2020).

In addition to the confusion and lack of clarity around most of the UK governments plans for post Brexit relations with Europe, there is the potential of future disconnection from funding opportunities and support networks currently operating between Scotland, UK and European Union, including the Creative Europe programme and the European Structural Funds which are at serious risk of being discontinued through the UK government's problematic Brexit negotiations.

Creative Scotland has responsibility for the Creative Europe Desk which acts as a resource for advice on EU funded programmes such as Erasmus+, Europe for Citizens and Horizon 2020. Funding for the the arts, media

and creative industries in the last ten years between 2007-17 amounted to £23 million coming from the European Structural and Investment Funds (UCLID, 2017) supporting in excess of three hundred and eighty creative arts projects which was critically important to the Scottish arts sector. The UK Government has proposed that a 'Shared Prosperity Fund' will be developed to replace the ESIF's funding support once UK leaves the EU, which Creative Scotland hopes will continue to support this important funding stream.

Worryingly for future investments in the arts in Scotland approximately sixty five percent of funding came from programmes which were not exclusively aimed at the arts sector. These figures are significant to arts funding in Scotland and may not continue within the new UK funding support structure that is currently being developed. It is particularly of concern as the current funding stream supported regional areas with social and economic need, such as Scotland's rural and remote island communities, where it offered them opportunities to build on a diverse range of culturally rich activities that have been developed to support these communities. This also has the capacity to enhance their social cohesion and helps sustain their economic viability. Arts and culture can play a substantial role in tackling root problems of inequality and they can be used as tools to support inclusive growth. It appears that Creative Europe funding has been lost and swift action needs to be required to introduce supporting measures to alleviate the funding loss incurred to Scotland's creative sector particularly for those with social and economic needs in the short term.

Due to the potential risks of losing ongoing support from Creative Europe, Creative Scotland endorses the position to seek alignment with Creative Europe beyond 2021 through the precedence that another thirteen non-EU state members engage with this organisation, where they accept some EU regulations and policies in addition to there being a cost for participation (Creative Scotland, 2019, p. 4).

Creative Scotland's perspective in relation to the UK government's Brexit White Paper is quite negative, and it seems very positively inclined to continue relationships with the EU around creative partnerships. In the UK government's Brexit White Paper 'The future relationship between the United Kingdom and the European Union, July 2018' they are very positive about working towards having a continued connection and support of European culture, which is the European Union's framework programme in supporting the culture and audio-visual sectors. With the UK being a world leading creative industries sector, it politically recognises its place within a broader European cultural framework supporting cultural diversity. It also believes that mobility of cultural and creative talent of both individuals and groups is important for continued UK-EU cooperation within this field.

They proposed an accord which facilitates a continued membership of EU cultural networks, and have expressed an interest in continued involvement within Creative Europe, and explore options that would 'build on existing precedents such as the EU's Cultural Cooperation Protocols with third countries.' (UK Government, 2018, p. 78)

This is quite a positive position taken which has an interest in continuing a relationship with Europe's creative communities, particularly when you look at its creative exports from the UK which account for ten percent of its economic activity; included in that are exports of £66 billion from its Fashion industry (Fashion United, 2016) and UK films global box office responsible for generating a further £6.2 billion (BFI Research and Statistics Unit, 2018) contribution to the economy. However, the concerns of Creative Scotland around substantial losses

to the Scottish creative sector if it no longer has access to support of the European Structural and Investment Funds are well founded, particularly around the fund's impact on regionally 'deprived' areas.

A report by the Culture, Tourism, Europe and External Affairs Committee in December 2019 which was driven by the artistic outcry over decisions and procedural inconsistencies around funding support delivered through Creative Scotland in that year, looked to understand the root problems of that unsatisfactory round of bids with regards to issues of making a living as creative practitioners and that relationship with funding bodies who were responsible for supporting the creative and cultural activity across the regions of Scotland. The report recommended a massive shift in focus, to one that was centred around the integrity of the work of practicing artists and supporting them through simple transparent mechanisms of an initial light touch in submission of proposals and awards, and offers of a 'fair wage' that adequately met the economic value of the artistic works produced. They proposed that the Scottish Government develop a new indicator within their National Performance Framework that focusses on how many artists were engaging with it and on having greater transparency in the process of appropriate direct funding to those artists.

"The Committee also recommends that artists and cultural freelancers should be included in the ongoing feasibility studies for a basic citizens' income funded by the Scottish Government."

(CTE&EAC, 2019 p. 1)

Considering that sixty percent of artists are unable to earn a living wage from their practice (Scottish Artists Union, 2018) there are clearly opportunities to develop a more sustainable system supporting creative artists' practice. The funding process also fails to understand artistic practice and recognise the importance of those artists who are not full-time but still contribute to the creative arts eco-structure (Sholette, 2011). The survey shows that the majority of members responding had never received any form of public funding support, although twenty five percent have received support from Creative Scotland, Glasgow Life or through Local Authority grants.

"Public funding of the arts will only be sustainable if artists are paid a fair wage and the Committee therefore calls on the Scottish Government and Creative Scotland to take urgent, robust action on this issue." (CTE&EAC, 2019, p. 1)

It also recommended that Creative Scotland review its funding allocation and develop focussed funding programmes which could include bursaries and stipends that would support both artists and art organisations. It was highlighted that a broader sustainable arts funding system should be set up, including a 'percentage for the arts' capital investment scheme.

"The Committee also recommends that the Scottish Government work with Creative Scotland to re-establish a programme of funding for regionally-based arts officers in local authority areas where Creative Scotland's investment is significantly below the Scottish average." (CTEEA, 2019, p. 2)

Local Authority Support

Cultural funding of Local authorities and their use of ALEO's

Scotland's thirty two local authorities are funded by central government to deliver cultural services to their local constituencies. They are given the financial freedom to operate independently, allowing them to be responsive to their own particular needs and circumstances. Challenges exist in the standard of delivery of cultural services across Scotland due to the differing interpretation of the responsibilities and duties of local authorities in providing what is ambiguously defined as 'adequate' cultural provision. Arts funding from central government is not protected or ring fenced and always at risk of being eroded in favour of statutory activities.

There appears to be no relationship between local authorities' priorities for cultural activity and the broader national government's priorities for arts and culture. To help bring local and national policy coordination closer together there is a value in local authorities developing an arts plan and broader cultural strategy which would help determine their responsibilities and priorities which could be viewed in concert with the national government's own agendas. Several councils are working on these plans but there is limited detail around some of their strategies and objectives (CTEEAC, 2019, Glasgow City Council, 2019, The City of Edinburgh Council, 2019).

Issues with local authorities and cultural and arts funding are made even more complex through the use of arms-length external organisations (ALEO's) which are set up as private charitable trusts by councils to save money through rates relief and which also allows these trusts to access funding streams that cannot be directly accessed by local government. Twenty Scottish councils have contracted ALEO's to deliver their cultural activities which also often include sport and leisure facilities within the remit. When the ALEO's access to alternative funding fails to materialize or if there is a lack of consistency in external financial support then it is possible that local authority cultural services could be impacted and reduced.

There are potential relationship issues between councils and these arms-length arts and cultural organisations, particularly around issues of transparency and direct accountability to the community. Their own governance structures are often disconnected from direct council representation, which risk challenges around resourcing priorities. The involvement of councilors and council members also needs to be managed appropriately.

"If the ALEO is not represented on the council's management team, the leader of the ALEO will not be at the table when the other chief officers have a discussion about budget setting or priorities, and they will not have influence." (CTEEAC, 2019, p. 25)

At a Culture, Tourism, Europe and External Affairs Committee meeting exploring a sustainable arts funding system for Scotland, statistical data was not easily accessible to specifically analyse arts funding and the impact of ALEO's (CTEEAC, 2019). They also identified that there was no ability to break down local authority expenditure on culture and heritage activities to allow identification of any specific arts related outlay. Data on expenditure on culture and related services also encompasses tourism and libraries in addition to recreation and sport which makes the task of disaggregating resource spend even more challenging. A lack of ring fencing of

cultural funding was also identified, resulting in council pressure to reallocate those resources into statutory services.

“some local authorities have absolutely decimated their culture funding, while others—East Ayrshire Council, Perth and Kinross Council and Stirling Council—have had positive experiences. It is hard to tell what local authorities are doing because so many of them now work through trusts” (CTEEAC, 2019, p. 25)

Per Capita Net Revenue Expenditure on Culture and Related Services by Local Authorities in 2017-18 shows the highest spend in the Orkney Islands, receiving £198 per person compared to the lowest, Edinburgh, receiving £61. (National Records of Scotland, 2019). From the data there appears to be a disparity of funding and arts support across the spread of local authority areas which needs further investigation, one that the Scottish Government has identified and plans to address.

In a letter to the Culture, Tourism, Europe and External Affairs Committee in June 2019, Creative Scotland had identified the need to develop and improve their relations with local authorities and had commissioned an external research body to look at the range of support offered to artists by local authorities across Scotland, and the potential challenges and opportunities for their future collaborations with them. This was also because national government has identified apparent shortcomings in the spread of Creative Scotland funding across all the regions of Scotland that they wish to be addressed, combined with difficulty in accessing appropriate data from local authorities when looking to identify expenditure specifically on creative activities within their communities. Regular arts funding provision for 2018-21 covered only twenty one of the thirty two local authorities. Eight authorities had made no application for any project funding at all. Sixteen local authorities were invited by Creative Scotland to be involved in its developmental, matched funding Place Partnerships Programme which was regarded by the participants as a significant initiative (CTEEAC 2019, p10). It appears that no clear rationale was given for the choices made of participants by Creative Scotland and why others were left out.

Capital investment in cultural venues across Scotland where artists can showcase their work have been progressively reduced since 1996-2014. Free local authority venues have also been in decline (CTEEAC, 2019 p. 44). It is also difficult to know what level of charges were now being made by ALEO's for the communities use of council facilities.

Further issues within the pattern of local authorities subcontracting out all cultural activities through ALEOS can be seen looking at the case of Glasgow City Council's Cultural and Leisure Services department being reconstituted and becoming Culture and Sport Glasgow (CSG) in 2007, then renamed as 'Glasgow Life' and 'Culture and Sport Enterprises' in 2009, under the auspices of the new Chief Executive Bridget O'Connell, wife of First Minister Jack O'Connell, whose primary focus was on the development of business interests around tourism and the regeneration of the city centre rather than directly supporting Glasgow's creative practitioners or utilising culture to enhance the lives of the poorer inhabitants of the city (Gordon-Nesbitt, 2008, 2009 p. 560).

Issues of concern were raised when it was discovered that CSG did not record its board meetings, therefore there were no publicly available minutes and no way to scrutinize any of their activities (Gordon-Nesbitt, 2011). Having an undemocratic, private company running the city's artistic and cultural activities was perceived to have a detrimental effect on those involved in the arts in the city. Its early history showed the organisations reluctance to take any risks to its own profile whilst exhibiting challenging or activist based art.

“CSG considers culture solely in terms of its use value, with the business people and bureaucrats at its helm having little sympathy towards creative practice beyond the cultural capital it confers upon them.” (Gordon-Nesbitt, 2009).

Belfiore (2020) identifies that ‘cultural value’ has become central to arts and creative industry policy debates. The articulation and measurement of economic value ‘in the guise of economic impact’ has been policy makers primary focus at the expense of broader holistic cultural, social or aesthetic values. She analyses the shaping of cultural values by those in authority and their use of symbolic violence to legitimize their activities and also how media representation supported their activities.

Risks to the development of forms of radical art practice challenging the established reality due to censorship of artists applications for funding were high. Gordon-Nesbitt (2009) believed that the art scene in Glasgow had been instrumentalised and harnessed by the market economy. Also, the focus on cultural tourism and city centre redevelopment fails to support a broader agenda of helping the poorest communities of Glasgow who were most in need of funding and resources to tackle poverty and ill health. Council resources have ultimately been channeled into supporting the activities of the privileged and ruling classes. When major financial cuts were required back in 2009, CSG undertook a review of services and proposed the closure of the Bellrock Community Centre in the Calton community facilities in what was one of the poorest neighbourhoods of the city. Glasgow City Council was forced to intervene and block these inappropriate and politically damaging proposals. It was noted that CSG priorities were clear, through its ring-fencing of budgets for the major tourist attractions at Kelvingrove, the Burrell Collection and Gallery of Modern Art, at the expense of vulnerable and less vocal East-End facilities (Gordon-Nesbitt, 2011).

However, a decade on, more recent activities show a new integrated approach to cultural activity highlighted by Glasgow City Council's quite radical proposal to invest £400,000 in an innovative ‘Creative Communities: Artists in Residence’ project, delivered by Glasgow Life in 2018. Its aims were to support its diverse communities in utilising creativity to develop dialogues with their Glaswegian neighbours and in opening up new creative opportunities and is part of the GCC's twenty five year Cultural Plan to champion art, culture and their relationship to overall health of the community. Twenty-three artists and arts organisations worked with local communities and organisations across all the wards of the city. It was estimated that 23,000 people had a chance to engage with a range of creative activities such as the visual arts, music, performance, filmmaking, photography, poetry and print making. Its success was recognised and rewarded through two more extensions of funding for the project with the third phase being launched on October 2021 (Glasgow Life, 2021).

“Our ‘Creative Communities – Artists in Residence’ programme takes arts and culture to a local level, into the heart of our communities where it become a tremendous force for good; improving health, well-being

and the general quality of life, boosting the confidence of individuals and communities, raising educational outcomes and breathing new life into some neighbourhood facilities.” (McDonald, 2019)

There is clear evidence that local authority regions of Scotland offer a variety of support to local artists, however the data making any more detailed assumptions is not available at present. Aggregation of financial resources means that those specifically aimed at supporting the arts cannot be identified. Further research into this area giving useful breakdowns of funding support in regional expenditure of the arts would be a useful contribution to this debate.

Thirty nine percent of artists in Scotland have been supported by their local authorities through freelance projects and commissions, which is a significant amount. Thirty three percent have had fixed term and full-time salaried positions, whilst others have been involved in learning and engagement, community workshops and developing public art commissions. Local authorities also are supportive of the creative arts through awards, grants and access to venues with in-kind arrangements. However, there is still a majority of Scottish Artist Union surveyed interviewees who have never had any funding support from Local Authorities.

A major focus of cultural and related funding is centred on Creative Scotland but its income from the Scottish government on culture in 202018-19 was only £66m compared to Scottish local authorities’ budget in the same year which was £575m. This is one reason why Local Authorities are so potentially important in the support of the artist economy (Scottish Government, 2020).

The Scottish government plans to work in partnership with their local authorities, the Convention of Scottish Local Authorities (COSLA), Culture Trusts, local networks and Community Planning Partnerships (CPP’s) to realise outcomes at a local level throughout Scotland. Local Outcomes Improvement Plans can prioritise employment support, physical and mental health development together with wellbeing issues. They will support local authorities through the introduction of Culture Conveners and Culture Trusts and intend to establish joint meetings of arts and culture conveners. This would re-embed a cultural voice within local authorities again after its dismantling during the austerity years.

The government believes developing community activities supported by national organisations will ensure the broadest reach covering all the local authority regions. At a grass roots level, it also has plans for a new initiative which will support and empower communities and individuals, to help them develop their own cultural activities through the launch of a ‘Creative Communities’ programme, working with Inspiring Scotland and supported by Creative Scotland.

“We support equal opportunities for people across Scotland to lead a cultural life of their choice with all aspects of cultural engagement – formal and informal“ (Blanche, 2015)

Richard Florida and his Bohemian Index

An example of strategic focus on the arts community by Glasgow city council, which has been influenced by the work of Richard Florida and his Bohemian Index, (Escotregen, 2005) strategically utilises the cultural capital of

artists to support their gentrification plans for the Merchant City. The arts were central to the rehabilitating of unproductive warehouse spaces and the council invested in the development of a creative cluster of subsidised WASP artist studios and gallery spaces.

“A creative strategy is easily bolted on to business-as-usual urban-development policies, while providing additional ideological cover for market-driven or state-assisted programs of gentrification. Inner-city embourgeoisement, in the creativity script, is represented as a necessary prerequisite for economic development”. (Peck, 2007)

The Merchant City Townscape Heritage Initiative (THI) was a Glasgow City Council programme focussed on property and public realm improvement grants and included the implementation of Glasgow City Council's Five Year Action Plan (2007-12). Of the thirteen projects listed for the final year of the initiative in 2012, four were quite substantial building refurbishments with an arts capacity building and curatorial focus including the conversion of a warehouse to an art centre at Trongate 103, restoration of a large Edwardian warehouse providing a centre for the arts and artist studio space, a conversion of a former bathhouse to an arts centre and a conversion of a large Edwardian warehouse to contain creative and cultural businesses.

As part of their art strategy for the city starting in 2005, they supported the Glasgow International Festival of Contemporary Visual Art (GI), described by The Guardian as the ‘most developed arts scene outside London’. The biennial generates significant cultural, economic and social value for the city and for Scotland, building on its aim to position itself as an international centre for contemporary visual arts. In 2019, Glasgow International was supported by the Scottish Government Festival Expo funding as part of its national network of major festivals.

“as a group of artists moved into a disused, shuttered shop to set up a temporary gallery for the duration of the Glasgow International Festival of Contemporary Visual Art (Gi). When I asked one of the artists how they had ‘found’ the space, she replied that a representative from Glasgow City Council had led the artists on a tour of disused shops in the ‘edge of success’ area around Trongate and the Gallowgate offering free leases for the duration of the festival.”. (Gray, 2009)

Florida highlights the potential downsides of gentrification and accommodating the creative class requires a support structure to be grown to service their needs, such as coffee shops and convenience stores. Poorly paid service sector workers are required to meet that need which is at the root of a society of inequality that has at its core, a disparate spread of poverty and wealth coexisting together.

Artist-run initiatives

Residencies and ventures which are self-organised and run by artists are seen as particularly important to the visual arts sector. They help form supportive, dynamic, cohesive groups and communities of artists offering collaborative opportunities, space for critical dialogue and help with networking. There are a number of specialist networks and production facilities funded by the Scottish government available to support artists including the sculpture, print and photography workshops in addition to LUX Scotland which are part of The Visual Arts Production Facilities Network, offering a range of creative and professional development opportunities. Artists residencies such as Cove Park, a charity funded by Creative Scotland, in support of other trusts and foundations, offers a supporting environment for contemporary artists where innovative work and collaborations can take place. These facilities are believed to be quite unique to Scotland (Creative Scotland, 2016, p. 19). In addition The Scottish Contemporary Art Network (SCAN), Engage Scotland, The Art Fund, The Contemporary Art Society and Artist Rooms offer skills development, training and networking opportunities. The British Council facilitates artists to be involved in UK and international exchanges, helping to build expertise and networks.

A number of artists make a living through both government support and private income streams. The Scottish government, Creative Scotland and local Authorities support artists through cultural policy directives in a variety of ways. Exhibitions and galleries are still the most effective income generation environment for sales for two thirds of artists with over three hundred and fifty venues supporting them, with online platforms becoming more useful for almost half the artists now utilising the web and social media channels to exhibit their work. Scan's survey of organisations in the visual arts sector in Scotland (Scan, 2016), highlight the importance of government and local authority support being responsible for over sixty percent of artists' income. Creative Scotland contributes 36% in association with the National Lottery, and local Authorities commit 16%. Trusts, foundations, donations, gifts and legacies supply fourteen percent, with only sixteen percent coming from earned income. (Blanche, 2015).

Outset Scotland is a charitable organisation which supports new art through donations given by patron circles, partners and philanthropists. They build networks and alliances with the private sector and support new art for public collections, raising over £10m worldwide in support of the creative arts ecosystem (Outset Scotland, 2019).

Scottish arts & culture support organisations' infrastructure visual map

There are over sixty-five arts focused organisations set up to support artists in Scotland, ranging from Advisory Groups to RFO Funded Arts Venues. This mapping exercise was carried out primarily through the process of extracting organisations' names from cultural review documentation and Creative Scotland information and mapped it out below. Creative Scotland funded organisations are highlighted in red and Scottish government direct funding is in blue. This map also includes lost EU funding.

Scottish Arts & Culture Support Map (Savage, 2020)

Figure 1

Interviews with Scottish Artists, 2020

The mature visual artists who were interviewed represent a community of those who have been able to develop their creative practice whilst being based in Scotland, ranging from those with successful careers to those who struggle to sustain their ongoing involvement within the visual arts creative community. They discuss their careers in detail and explain how they have interacted with the art market, dealers, gallerists, institutions and governmental bodies such as Creative Scotland and Local Authorities. They were also asked about their views on the impact of the Scottish government's developing cultural policy, Brexit and Covid on their lives.

The following artists took part:

- Dr Alison Bell
- Kate Downie
- Karen Monaghan
- Bryan Evans
- David Reid
- Bella Green
- Shona Barr
- Inge Smith
- Louise Ritchie

Dr. Alison Bell

<http://www.alisonbell.co.uk>

Fig 2. Artist: Alison Bell, Title: Form – Re-form # 3, Medium: Textile using silk, pigment, wax and metal, Dimensions: 16cms (height) x 13cms (width) x 9cms (depth) Date: unknown. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Alison has been a practicing, textile artist since 1977. She was educated at Glasgow School of Art and then Duncan of Jordanstone College of Art in Dundee, exiting with a DA in Textile Design and Printmaking in 1974 and a Post Graduate Diploma in 1975. She gained a PhD, through the University of the West of Scotland, where she self-reflected on ‘Exploring the Embodied Experience of Ageing through Creative Practice’ in 2018. She has exhibited internationally in Australia, Tokyo in Japan, Atlanta and Kansas City in the USA, and more locally in Maclaurin Art Gallery Ayr, Taigh Chearsabhaigh, North Uist, Outer Hebrides, the Collins Gallery Glasgow and in the CCA in Glasgow. She has also had a number of academic papers published.

After winning the Royal Society of Arts bursary competition at Duncan of Jordanstone, Alison was made a Fellow of the Royal Society of Arts. She has the title on her CV as a quality mark, but hasn’t engaged with that particular organisation any further.

Upon leaving art school, Alison was awarded an ‘artist in residency’ in Livingstone new town by the Scottish Arts Council. At the end of that year she was offered a continuation for another year but decided to get a teaching qualification in Secondary Art/Design Education at the Dundee College of Education. She worked part time as an art teacher for the next eight years.

She moved to the isle of Arran and set up a studio there called Arran Fine Arts where tourists watched Alison at work, as a form of entertainment and she had artworks available to sell to them at the front of the studio until 2006. She would do this primarily during the summer months, as winter was very quiet, and supplemented her income with some part-time teaching. She was chair of Arran Visual Arts, which served amateur and professional artists on the island.

A new initiative supported by the Scottish Arts Council funded four Craft Development Officers throughout Scotland, which is interestingly close to what the Scottish Government have proposed in their March 2020 cultural policy report. Alison approached the Craft Development Officer in Ayrshire, hoping he could be of use, and he took some of her work to a show in London. She was also given support to go to a conference in America, and to Tilburg, Netherlands, and then applied and became a special advisor for the Scottish Arts Council to support their selection panels and funding decisions. Alison felt she had been elevated onto the creative circuit where she has stepped up a level from just being an artist working on Arran.

There was also a call out for directors of the board of Craft Scotland, and Alison applied and was elected onto the board.

“And then I was a name. That was a name with a bit of clout as well, which was interesting, but the door that opened was really quite transformative, but I couldn't have opened it unless I had the capacity to come up with the goods. That was the start of it.” (Bell, 2020)

Alison had a really good relationship with the Scottish Arts Council organisation and has been given funding support from 2003. Her business on Arran supplied both aesthetic and commercial artwork to the tourist trade.

Alison believed the Scottish Arts Council took a chance on what they thought she could be capable of, which was based on the kind of work that she had been producing in her business. She sent in lots of images and that was enough. It helped launch her career. She feels that the artist's body of creative work was more important than actually what you wrote when applying to the Scottish Arts Council. Creative Scotland, on the other hand, set different drivers for their application and their criteria is now more instrumentalised and economically driven. She believes an artist's body of work is now of less importance to the funding process, so in order to get funding, you now need to be able to write, and this is what really annoys artists trying to access funding.

After closing her studio Alison started to focus entirely on her own work for which she had no market. Financially, it was totally 'nuts', but inwardly the best thing she ever did. She began to grow and that's what mattered to her. That was very important, much more so than economics. She created a body of work, and found a really nice gallery in North Uist, who was prepared to show it, and it was fantastic. It was the totality of the experience. It was great that she was able to also do a residency up there as well, which was wonderful. She also started doing 'artist in residence' projects to try to get some funding, as these were starting out and you had to reciprocate, such as working with schoolchildren. So, she did three of them, which were interesting, well paid, but very tiring. She also had part of the week to do her own work. She then decided that she would leave Arran, and make the break and she left for the mainland in 2007. She was able to show her artwork in America and Europe, probably because of her being a Craft Scotland board member, and this helped to expand her network.

It gave her a sense of new possibilities and a new life. So, from being a known entity in a small island, she came to Ayrshire and nobody knew who she was which proved to be very challenging. She then did a residency for a year in Maybole which helped feed her.

The first Craft Development Officer employed by North Ayrshire council. came to her and offered an opportunity to work at the University of West of Scotland where she lectured part time in the School of Education for a couple of days a week. She staying for eleven years until 2018, which opened up another world for her. She decided to do a PhD after being involved as a case study for a colleague down in Wales, which introduced her to the world of research, which was brand new and through that colleague's funding, she went to Australia, and showed her work there. This was an introduction to different worlds, the academic world of teaching and the academic possibilities of doing research. Also, being on Craft Scotland's board, opened up an awareness of what was going on craft wise in Scotland too.

After their involvement in a symposium and exhibition at the University of Newcastle in New South Wales in Australia, they then had an exhibition of their collaborative work in the Maclaurin gallery in Roselle who were really keen to host an academic symposium, and there was also a residency attached to that as well. She enjoyed all of that because it felt very fulfilling. She was helping somebody, was growing creatively and was being introduced to this new world of academia which was brand new for her and it was something she didn't really know much about. "You don't, because it's a closed world." So, firing on all cylinders she was really living to the potential of a PhD student. From going from Arran, all the way through to contacts, being at the right place at the right time, being ambitious, seizing opportunities and having a go and it all pans out. Nothing ever didn't pan out for her. She thinks that's just luck as well, through being in the right place, at the right time, and having the right ingredients made it work. This mirrors Csikszentmihalyi's views that the success of creative artists is often determined by chance events, where a connection to a mentor opens doors to successful recognition of the artist by the creative field. (Sternberg, 1999, p. 328)

She has used UWS teaching to fund the creative work that she wanted to do in the interim, and recognised that if you don't want to make stuff to sell, you have to fund yourself. The most cost effective way of doing that for her was being employed at UWS, and that paid for the other stuff. In the middle of that she took on a PhD, which has been just a transformative experience for her. So, she went from being on a small insular island, outgrew it, moved to the mainland, and just sought out the opportunities which came about. UWS gave her a funding source, which she quite enjoyed, and allowed her to grow. This was better than if she'd been stacking shelves, which is not going to allow anyone to grow, and it gave her an entrance into a different world.

Alison had a very interesting experience with Creative Scotland. In order to get some funding for an exhibition in Japan, which was going to cost about five thousand pounds, she developed a project to latch onto it which appealed to the funders of Creative Scotland, but it needed to feel authentic, and she needed to be able to pull it off and carry it out. She applied along with a colleague who wanted to accompany her as well and linked in her postdoctoral research, which she was doing independently, and applied to their Open Fund. There is a series of hurdles to overtake to progress through the funding system in Creative Scotland, and she managed to get through right to the very last one. But Creative Scotland gave feedback and felt there was some additional clarity to the bid required. So, she thinks of it as series of doors that you have to go through, and got through to

the last door, but didn't get through the final one. She got feedback, right up to the point of that final door, but with the final panel, you get no feedback, so she never found out exactly why she didn't get the funding. She has a fundamental objection to Creative Scotland's process, that there is no ultimate transparency. They are very supportive until that final point, but in that final panel it's a closed door, and the heads of each of the department decide on the final outcome, and there's no way she will ever find out why they didn't actually fund her. When she initially applied, they came back and said yes, this is a fundable project and just expand this a little bit and do that now and she did it all to the letter. They told her she got through all these financial stages up until that final panel before she was rejected. It took a solid month of her time to make the application. She also objected to Creative Scotland's Open Project fund which wasn't just for individuals, everyone was all in it together and the pot was shared among both organizations and individuals. And she thought that was fundamentally wrong that she should be up against an organisation like the Traverse Theatre, for example.

She also went to see the British Council and got in touch with Nora Campbell, someone whom she had met whilst working in Arran, who is head of Visual Art at the British Council in Edinburgh. The British Council works hand in hand to some extent with Creative Scotland and she was very keen to support Alison's trip to Japan. The British council do not supply funding but could have opened extra doors for her. But then Covid happened and literally everything stopped.

Alison is also currently involved as a special advisor to Applied Art Scotland who are assessing Creative Scotland and its funding model.

Well, it could be argued that with the Scottish Arts Council she's been one of the anointed ones. She's done very well out of their funding and received thousands over the years and still thinks that she's very good at what she does and has a whole creative lifetime to back it up. She believes that now's the time that she should be receiving funding. Alison is very interested now in looking at mature artists, and what the opportunities are for them, because there doesn't appear to be any. "There just isn't any, but that's another chapter."

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

We can see that from a Bourdieuan perspective that Alison Bell has built up her habitus which she believes underpins her relationship to the field and her creative and cultural capital. In her early career she was awarded Fellow of the Royal Society of Arts which is quite prestigious and then was successful in applying for the 'Artist in residence' in Livingston new town, a very competitive and quite important award. Later through her relationship with the local authority Crafts Development Officer, Alison's profile and recognition was raised at home and abroad. This was facilitated through the connection to a 'mentor' who opens doors for her, mentioned by Csikszentmihalyi (1997, p. 7). Through her actively identifying opportunities and accessing them she became a board director of Craft Scotland and then was appointed as a special advisor for the Scottish Arts Council to support them in their selection panels and funding decisions. This further elevated her position within the social field, and brings to her more institutional capital which allows her to access resources more easily through her understanding of processes and requirements of funding bodies and being part of a network of relationships helping advance her interests. (Bourdieu, 1986)

Surviving on Arran, Alison was a self-employed cultural worker, focussed her art working on fulfilling the demands of the popular tourist marketplace, meeting the heteronomous field of power and mass audience appeal. Once she had alternate resourcing through UWS, Alison was able to focus on developing her own artistic practice independently of the outside demands of the market place driven by autonomous and self-sufficient 'high end' artwork. (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 321)

There were times in her life when she was working in her studio in Arran that her artworks were deemed as merchandise, subordinate to market demands. When she was an 'artist in residence' there was a need to give back something in return for the funding. Then at other times she was working on 'pure' art, driven by her own internal personal creative activity with total independence and no regard for the market place (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 141). Her niche work is not elevated and consecrated by the bourgeois establishment but sits as avant-garde creative output supported by an intellectual critique. Now Alison does not sell her work, so there is no social energy or accumulation of value in the production process being released.

Critical discourse around artworks legitimizes both the artworks and the appointed critics simultaneously. 'The artwork is deemed worthy of legitimate discourse through its recognition' (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 141). In Alison's case this also includes the artist as the critic of their own work, and the resulting PhD awarded gives academic credibility and social status to that creative output. Bourdieu proposed that it is the scholars and the educational system who define and uphold the consecrated works and are responsible for recording the relationships and contexts of the sacred artworks (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 147).

From a Becker perspective there is currently little 'collective action' around Alison's work, with the exception in use of materials that contribute to her work. Becker recognises Alison's fellowship of the RSA to be a distinguishing feature as she has been chosen as a one of the most gifted artists of her cohort. She also helped set standards and rules of artist membership whilst being involved with Craft Scotland and the Scottish Arts Council funding process. She has required regular financial support to help her continue her art practice which has been her primary goal throughout her life. This support has been supplied through her developing network which has within it a ranking system of deserving artists (Becker, 1974).

Alison fits comfortably into Csikszentmihalyi's model of three components; the personal, the domain of knowledge and the field. As a skilled artist, who understands her work in context of the broader art world, she was judged by trusted experts, initially by The Royal Society of Arts, Craft Scotland and then later by the Scottish Arts Council, to be a cultural producer. (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997, p. 7) however she does not take her work to the market, so it holds no value to anyone but herself.

Her introduction to the Crafts Development Officer who became a 'mentor' opening doors for her, increased her chances of success (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997).

Greg Sholette sees 'high art' as elevated above and distinct from the capitalist market place while historically being completely enshrined within it (2010). Alison produces 'high art' which is completely distinct from the capitalist market place, but also has the qualities of Sholette's 'bare art' too. Alison's high art status is at odds with her relationship to neo-capitalism. It currently is autonomous, running independently of it and through that

it retains its spirituality, but for her to survive financially as a single parent she had to commoditise her work during that period of her life. Alison embraced entrepreneurship which dominates all aspects of contemporary art from its production and its reception (Chin-tao Wu, 2003). She has now become a hidden cultural producer who works primarily outside of the art market place for her own pleasure.

Alison's work is not political in nature, but she clearly has the personal skills to navigate the art world's political and power structures comfortably, working at all levels of the industry.

Alison promotes herself through her own website and LinkedIn account and has artwork in the Scotland's Artists Online Gallery.

Government support – how Scottish Government cultural policy has impacted the artists

Alison has had a number of grants and awards to support her art practice starting with the 'artist in residency' in Livingstone new town which was funded by the Scottish Arts Council.

The Scottish government initiative of funding local authority Craft Development Officers was very important to Alison's career. The officer promoted her work in London and more importantly found funding for her to go to a conference in the USA and to Tilburg in the Netherlands.

After becoming a special advisor to the Scottish Arts Council helping support their selection panels and funding decisions, Alison certainly had the skillset to navigate her funding requests through their system. She had a really good relationship with the Scottish Arts Council who supported her with funding bids from 2003 and believed they recognised her professionalism, gained whilst working in her gallery in Arran and that her artistic output met their criteria. There was no requirement then for artists to write extensive bids for funding as is now required for access to Creative Scotland's resources.

She has received funding to support her many 'artist in residences' from the Scottish Arts Council, Carnegie Trust and Creative Scotland which were well paid.

Alison's experience recently with Creative Scotland highlights the issues of artists who apply for funding, spending a huge amount of time interacting with the funders, but ultimately receiving nothing for their efforts. Her rejection letter just stated there was a lack of funds to offer her an award at the final decision stage where there was no transparency regarding the decision making at that point. They were very supportive until that final stage, but in that final panel it's a closed door, and the heads of each of the departments made a final decision to not award her support. It probably took a solid month of Alison's time to make that application which is untenable for many artists.

The Scottish government have taken up some of these issues at a review point after Creative Scotland was severely criticised for mismanaging the processing of funding submissions that year, and this issue of separating out artists competing against organisations among others was highlighted. It also recognised that the amount of

time it was taking artists to go through the funding bid was disproportionate and problematic. Proposals were made that Creative Scotland should signpost what bids were potentially unsuccessful at an early stage so that minimum time was spent on a full bid. This would not have been helpful to Alison as she was given positive feedback in the early stages of her bid only to fail at the last hurdle. Those in power are unaccountable for their funding decision choices.

Kate Downie

<http://katedownie.com/>

Fig 3. Artist: Kate Downie, Medium: unknown, Dimensions: unknown, Date: unknown. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Kate is a relatively successful full-time artist and studied Fine Art at Gray's School of Art in Aberdeen to post-graduate level. She has spent the past 25 years exploring Scottish urban landscapes, contrasting with less interesting edges of city coastal locations. She has lectured in art colleges and universities and has had responsibility for major community and public arts projects. She severely lacked any role models when she was younger.

“the white male privilege, you know, even though Glasgow wasn't necessarily privileged at all, the opportunities were given to the new Glasgow boys, but she kind of forced her own way...”

(Downie, 2020)

After graduating she had a part time job briefly as an illustrator for educational books working for the College of Education in Aberdeen, lasting for five months, but working in a real job was not for her.

Her father was a doctor, so she did have some parental help until she was about 25. She had a Wasps studio, like most of the artists did and it was thirty quid a month and her parents paid that for a couple of years after she left art school. That was it really, but for a lot of other people, if you were from a really poor background and had built up debt through college, and you were female, then you really were a bit stuffed.

She has held many artists' residencies in the USA, Amsterdam, Paris, Corsica and Norway, and has established studios in novel and interesting places such as a maternity hospital, a brewery, an oil rig and an island that sits beneath the Forth Rail Bridge.

As President of the Society of Scottish Artist from 2004 to 2006, she co-curated international contemporary visual art projects, including the Bodyparts Live art Festival at the RSA in Edinburgh and an exchange exhibition with artists from India. She was shortlisted in 2005 for the Jerwood Drawing Prize, and became a member of the Royal Scottish Academy in 2008.

Her work has appeared in many public and corporate collections which include HM The Queen, the BBC, Adam & Co, Glasgow Gallery of Modern Art, Gracefield Art Gallery in Dumfries, Aberdeen Art Gallery, Rietveld Kunst Academie in Amsterdam; City of Edinburgh Council, Kelvingrove Art Gallery in Glasgow & New Hall College Art Collection in Cambridge.

There have been times when financially it's been really hard, when she had children, and struggled with poverty, and then couldn't claim for childcare against expenses to be able to work in her studio. She did have a partner at the time, but he was mostly touring with a theatre company, so if she wanted to work, she needed to find that time. So that was just gob smacking that she could bring up two kids and be forced to not carry on, unless she accepted a level of poverty that most people would find unacceptable. She had a part time job at Edinburgh College of Art, then even though she was pregnant with her second child, when a job came up as a permanent part time post, they gave it to a guy whose wife was pregnant, because they said he would need the steady income. So, a lot of the poverty was neither necessary, nor of her own making.

The last time she got a fairly big chunk of funding was in 2013, for the production of a catalogue for a major show, and that was printed in both Mandarin and in English, whilst she was working in China for a while, and the show was touring there as well. But the funding she really wanted was for a project, she didn't get. Then she decided to employ someone to help her write her funding applications, because she's a bit dyspraxic and can't spell.

Her husband had a touring theatre company in the 80s, through to the early 2000s. Most of their time, it seemed, was taken up with writing grant applications, and she could see what it does to people's heads, and there's a really delicate balance between self-determination, and grant application. And the people that are very good at it can often get you one and then from that you might get another. Also, you sometimes get to do the most amazing collaborations, because in the act of dreaming up these projects and working with people from different countries, it sparks other things and funding streams from those other countries.

Pure thought and action get things moving and then once they are moving, they create their own momentum. So, if you have pending applications that you're negotiating in the midst of all that, it destroys you, and especially, even when you do get it, you've almost explained it so hard that you've forgotten what it was you really wanted it for in the first place. All you are worried about is their response, rather than to be yourself, but more so.

Kate had twelve months of Arts Council funding in the eighties, to live in the Netherlands, in the Amsterdam Studio. She was the first woman artist to have that opportunity, and it was life changing. It was completely amazing. All her art history knowledge, awareness and contacts came from that year spent in in Holland and she could nip off to Paris and go all over Europe. After that, she lived in Paris for a year, and did residencies in Japan, China, in Norway and in Corsica and, so she has been out and about a bit, ...not so much recently.

Kate is chair of the Friends of the Royal Society of Arts, and is an RSA member. She also used to be president of the Society of Scottish Artists, and she completely loves the networks that they created on an international level, and really loved inviting artists from other countries, who came to stay because they didn't have enough money to put them up in hotels, and all of that stuff. She's still in touch with loads of artists in India, China, Japan, and in the States because of that, so their experiences coming here has enriched her.

She also is represented by the Scottish Gallery, and they do not ask her to ameliorate her work for their market. She's lucky that they like what she does, and she gets to develop and they sort of accept it. She has other exhibiting outlets, but the fact is that people actually pay from time to time, big lumps of money for her work. She knows that a lot of the time, grant aided work doesn't necessarily have a collectible market, say locally in Edinburgh which is so conservative, relatively speaking, that she would have to go much further afield to find a home for it. Her most important thought about this is that of the sixty percent of 'failed' artists, there are some very good artists who might be seen as quite traditional, who given half the opportunity would step into areas far more contemporary, far more about dialogue, far more conceptual, far more radical, if they were given a small amount of chance to step off the hamster wheel of making saleable work.

Kate thinks you sell an idea, almost a lifestyle, when you sell work, and she can see that people love that thing of, 'Oh, God, I wish I could do that'. She didn't even know until a few years ago that she had this awareness that everything is to do with the pricing of your work and your status. A lot of it's to do with the platform with which you present your work through. This is on an obvious stage, it's a plinth, or it's a frame, so her networks involve people who make her stretchers and source the quality of her canvas. She sends off for them, handmade from London or wood panels and she has worked with three different framers, depending on the scale of the framing, whether it's huge, or whatever it's for. Her partner does installation photography for the Gallery of Modern Art, and he used to do Inverleith House so he's a handy person to have. Her daughter helps a bit with the website, and she has got another website designer somewhere else. So, all of these networks, just even before the work leaves here are quite hefty, even before the work goes into the gallery. And then of course, there's the gallery website and having the Scottish gallery, which she kind of decided was the right one for her way back, and then spent about ten years trying to get them to agree.

The Royal Scottish Academy has a number of organizations, and she chairs their supporters' friends group arranging live studio visits to RSA artists' studios, and she loves going into other people's studios anyway and has learned a huge amount because of it, through that particular network.

She's old enough to know that the networks that you put into, do not give you instant or obvious returns. Being an artist is a bit like being a crofter, you have to be a bit of a polymath, and you have to be good at a whole bunch of stuff in order to be financially successful. She thinks that one of the things that you learn to do is

recognise what you're good at, and what you're not, and then to ask others for help. And that's taken her years to learn to do that, because she was so independent before.

“The most interesting aspects of the COVID lockdown, we all suffered, a creative lockdown. which was that guy who developed the Artist Pledge. The wonderful thing that he built into that policy was that when an artist hits one thousand pounds, they have to invest two hundred pounds of that money into other artists work and none of this is policed.” (Downie, 2020)

She received some funding from local authorities just before lockdown for a really exciting project. It's not like it's a huge amount of money, but it's a kind of validation. She's worked with lots of local authorities; a big mural commission up in Aberdeen, City Art Centre in Edinburgh, Dumfries and Galloway council, Glasgow museums and galleries, a big residency years ago at Rotten Row maternity hospital, which was epic, and just mind boggling, and that had continuous repercussions. She works locally and internationally, with whatever comes her way. It's who the people are behind the scenes and some of the most engaged, such as Dumfries and Galloway council, are fabulous. But it's actually the really enlightened individuals within these organizations, such as the woman who's incredibly dynamic at Gracefields in Dumfries. These people at a local level have been really personally supportive, helping people find studios, giving them advice, even giving them work to come in and teach in evening classes or run courses, helping in the artist collectives. Dumfries and Galloway region is just seething with artist collectives now, supported by two or three key people. Also, there's been huge amounts of support, and indirect funding from organisations like the Printmakers Workshop Networks in Scotland, so that that kind of thing has been really massive and co-publications of prints carry on making her money.

She is greatly impressed with Dumfries and Galloway council who brought her in to support their artist community, offering professional practice training to those who wanted to have open studio organizations.

One project she has developed is 'Little Bridges..', a little film which brings challenges for galleries, as they don't have the infrastructure for the artists that are moving into video production installations, and folk still come into traditional gallery spaces looking for paintings on walls, so there's a need to develop a combination of both. Kate's next exhibition at the Scottish Gallery is going to be all tree paintings, and she's going to get them to completely turn the venue into a blacked out space, so you walk into a kind of weird forest.

Her projects are often self-funded, on the back of an exhibition and sales. She's also been invited and funded by Stavanger, Norway's European city of culture. The Chinese government funded her indirectly to do a residency in the Hengshui Province. She had already self-funded herself to go over there and she's also had funding to go there and do research, so she usually decides what she wants to do and finds a way of getting it to happen. Occasionally wonderful opportunities might land on her lap, but that's not very often. She just keeps asking and likes adventure.

She was also on the board of directors for Art and Healthcare Scotland for years and has had some interesting commissions of mural work in the past, which have been massively successful in terms of reach, like hospital arts. Her father was a hospital doctor, so she was very comfortable working in hospital environments. She feels

really passionate about quite hefty campaigning for art to be seen more than just in galleries, and in helping people deal with their collections of art through moving those collections into public spaces.

She's not as deeply affected by Brexit because she's been around, and probably will survive, as you'd have to kill her to stop her making art. She thinks that where it's going to feel really horrible is probably one or two years down the line. The effect of it is that people will carry on, but then as there's less money swirling around all over, artists will become marginalized or there will be a lack of funding streams. So, it will affect those kinds of things, like all the big EU supported touring exhibitions, which are the ones that tour original places, and that means regional schools can't actually see decent art. It's massive, because however good virtual is, when it comes to making art, you really need to go in front of it.

Covid was hard for Kate because she basically had to evacuate her very aged mom who has dementia and who is pretty deaf & blind, and sprung her out of her tenement flat in Glasgow, and took her to live with her. So, she became the twenty four hour main carer for ten and a half weeks and didn't get a lot of work done in that time. It was hard, but she saw what happened to other people's families, and has zero regrets. Her mother has a little bit of vision left, and they did a parallel painting project, where they would paint together and she could assist her and then she put the work online. And so, she actually turned it into a project about compassion and caring and using art on a very intimate scale. Because you're a big artist, you've got to keep doing stuff, but other people were going nuts with what they did with themselves. She has just completed a print series for the Artists Pledge, and that has now led on to a new series of works.

At times she feels her hard work was deserving of more recognition and should give her more access to more international and some more exciting public arts opportunities in this country.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

Kate Downie has an interesting relationship within the theoretical models of Bourdieu, Becker and Csikszentmihalyi. She has the habitus of a middle-class upbringing, art school educated, with some support from her parents in her early career, set within a lifetime of working in the field of visual art practice, both locally and internationally, having solo and collaborative exhibitions, international residencies, awards, publications and her work is held in a number of notable public and private collections adding to her creative capital. She has enhanced institutional capital through being a member of several art institutions including the Royal Scottish Academy and was President of the Society of Scottish Artist and is currently acting as chair of the Friends of the Royal Society of Arts. She is also represented by the Scottish Gallery in Edinburgh, all building on her social capital.

She has issues around Bourdieu's symbolic violence, manifesting in institutions' failure to support women artists when categorizing art movements, re the elevation of the New Glasgow Boys, and during her career where women were disadvantaged initially through having limited income which then resulted in no social support funding when having children. Particularly of note was the taxation system's indifference to supporting

working women by not allowing child care to be treated as a taxable expense, penalizing her attempts to make a living as an artist and forcing her into poverty.

Kate produces her own artwork and the Scottish Gallery, which acts as her symbolic banker, is comfortable with her independence in this matter and does not ask her to tailor her work for their market. Her art work has a degree of 'signification' which has a symbolic value (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 141). With her profile, Kate Downie deserves to be called an artist, and not a cultural worker, but she feels her worth has not been fully recognised. She has had a number of media reviews of her art work and has been deemed worthy of legitimate discourse through its recognition. Her artworks elevate themselves to be consecrated as symbolic pieces of contemplation in gallery spaces and in museums and she has been rewarded with artistic prestige. She also serves the established order and their hierarchy through her associations with them. Kate sits within both the heteronomous and autonomous principles, working independently but selling her artworks to the system. (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 321) She also sits within 'high end' art production for bourgeois consumption and broader mass market appeal. She meets the specific principle of legitimacy as she is autonomous and self-sufficient. Then there is legitimacy corresponding to 'bourgeois' taste and its consecration by the dominant class and those in power which applies to her also.

Kate is very aware of Becker's and Sholette's networks of supporting personnel who help in the creation of her artworks. She talks in depth around the creation of her work and around the platform it is shown on. (Becker, 1974)

"so my networks involve the quality of my canvas, who makes my stretchers, I send off for them handmade from London, you know, or wood panels. And she worked with three different framers, depending on the scale of the framing, you know, whether it's huge, or whether whatever it's for."

(Downie, 2020)

Becker sees Kate Downie's work solely as a market driven consumable artifact developed through human interactions within the creative processes. He sees that guilds and academies ensure that only the most gifted and authentic artists are acknowledged socially and we can see the quality of Kate's art practice has been recognised through her belonging and being accepted into those power structures.

Csikszentmihalyi's systemic model supports Kates artistic position where she brings skills and craft within a domain of knowledge with a cultural context, and then is judged by that field and by trusted experts. The work grows and mutates as it evolves. The artists are impacted by the culture of which they are both influencing and being influenced by.

We can see the worth of creative communities making specific acts of creative art production valued and they nurture new talent and help with their induction into the art world. It can be seen that Kate benefitted from those creative communities throughout her artistic career and by her many collaborations and residences and the status it has given.

Csikszentmihalyi saw a direct relationship between creativity and persuasion as there is a need for the artist to persuade and sell new creative idea to the cultural gatekeepers. Kate talks of spending ten years to get the Scottish Gallery to accept her work.

“the Scottish gallery, which I kind of decided was the right one for me way back, and then spent about ten years trying to get them to agree.” (Downie, 2020)

Kate’s artistic practice comes from a whole variety of idea generation inventions and fit with Sholette’s ‘bare art’, a deep humanist act of artistic and cultural practice. Her work sits within bourgeois consumption and she supports the elite, but her practice contains a deep human drive to create art whether there’s a market for her work or not and ‘you’d have to kill her to make her not make art’.

She is impressed with the Artists Pledge web initiative which supports and keeps money circulating through the artist economy.

Government support – how cultural policy has impacted the artists

She has been funded regularly by local authorities and recognises the role of enlightened individuals working for those organisations and the support to artists that they give. She was also supported by Scottish Arts Council funding to live in Amsterdam Studio for a year early in her career, and she also recognises indirect support like Wasps Studios, and Printmakers Workshop Networks in Scotland. Often her projects and art working are all self-funded.

Negative government policies on taxation and support of childcare was very impactful on her life, forcing her to choose a life of poverty in order for her to continue as an artist.

A grant writer gave her support in making an application for funding to Creative Scotland as it was not her strength and she recognises the challenges for artists to use this pathway in supporting their artistic practice. She also highlights the fundamental incompatibility of artists having to document a project which then needs sanctioned before it can proceed is the antithesis of artistic creative practice and is damaging to the process.

She recognises that experimental grant aided artwork may not be suitable for the art market to collect, and may be difficult to find a home so it particularly needs support. She is also aware of the importance of the big EU funded supported touring exhibitions that tour remote places which will likely be affected by Brexit.

Karen Monaghan

<https://www.facebook.com/bigwhalesmakebigwaves/>

Figure 4. Artist: Karen Monaghan, Title: Wha's Aucht, Medium: oil on board, Dimensions: 50cmx40cm, Date: 2019. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Karen really struggled to get into art school as her family had expectations of her going to university, not to an art college. Whilst at art school she chose jewellery as her specialist course, merged her love of painting with quite big jewelry, and small scale printing using a lot of dyes and resists and loved the colour and the texture. She recognises the critical point of the art school graduate show, and remembers how at that time you were pushing the boundaries which were innovative and interesting and now that type of work has become mainstream.

'It's being in the right place at the right time, and if you miss that boat, then you're always on the backfoot' (Monaghan, 2020). It was a very patriarchal community and women were not treated seriously, and she thinks that as a female artist, there's a whole layer of additional challenges. She also thinks it's important to collaborate and not be judgmental around other peoples' practice.

She has won a travel scholarship, prizes and has exhibited cross the country and her works are held in private collections in USA, Canada, France, Portugal, Spain and New Zealand

After graduating from Duncan of Jordanstone Art school in Dundee and doing a post graduate course there too, she moved abroad for twelve years, living in the Middle East, where she taught art classes there.

After coming back to the west coast of Scotland in 1998, she set up her studio there and had been working on her own personal projects. She has now moved to the east coast and her studio is in East Linton, which is absolutely jam packed with finished paintings stored in two rooms.

Karen had been teaching art in a residential school for ten years, working with troubled young people who respond positively to a creative environment, but more recently is working with young people to help them get back into employment. She starts very early in the morning and finishes early, allowing her to do her creative work afterwards. She wishes she could do that all the time but needs to survive financially.

"But one of the things that we were told was this thing about Sunday painters ... and you've got to be starving for your art otherwise, you know, nobody will take you seriously" (Monaghan, 2020)

The only financial support she has been given in her career was through the school where she taught, who paid for her to do print making courses at Leith School of Art and weekend courses to support her practice in the classroom.

She has started to make jewellery again and would like to do workshops but needs support in promoting and advertising them. She also has been trying to find galleries who will show her work without success. She has a website, Instagram and Facebook account and has sold directly from her Instagram site

She found the creative networks easier to be part of in the west coast than in the east of Scotland. There was much more going on, with open exhibitions in a decent gallery and decent space. She has approached a local gallery but has not had any opportunity to show her work which is quite demoralising.

"My dad passed away last year from Alzheimer's. And within about eight years over the time when he was ill, I did a lot of writing and poetry and I drew him a lot. And I did portraits when he was ill in bed and I sent him (the gallery owner) some, I mean, these are not necessarily things that a commercial gallery wants to show because they're quite personal but I think they are connected with other people. Yeah, you know, there is something that a lot of people are going to experience at some point in their life. And I did think it was an interesting thing that I've done" (Monaghan, 2020)

She planned to make an artist book from that work and the gallery owner was interested in seeing it, but hasn't progressed that. That work did get a lot of positive feedback from some artists groups online. She was a member of 'Women in the Arts, Scotland', where people post work there and use it to get feedback. She also contributed to Creative Writing Scotland, to the Scottish Society of Arts and has creative content in Visual Arts Scotland. She used the sites looking to network with other artists and to collaborate or chat.

"I'm not particularly disheartened. You know, I love what I do. And I'm going to keep doing it, because I feel like it's sort of, you know, like a band waiting for the first break, you know, if they don't play the music, then they're not going to get it." (Monaghan, 2020)

Karen is aware of the 'Artists Support Pledge' website set up to support artist during Covid, which is a great thing. She thinks whoever started that had an inspired idea, but she didn't get involved as she had another job and it wouldn't be fair. She also knows of another artists' pledge online group called Patreon - Artist Pledge.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

Bourdieu's theories on symbolic violence seem to apply to Karen's experiences of misogyny within the art world and it being more challenging for women to succeed as artists and a feeling that the art school treated women unfavourably (Nochlin, 1971). At the graduation show it was critical to succeed and be recognised by the powerful, or it was very difficult to recover from that point onwards.

Currently Karen has no avenue to sell her work through galleries, although she has sold work online. She has the habitus of knowledge in developing creative works and has trained to a post graduate level, so she has some institutional capital, but has limited impact on the field of production and has little creative or cultural capital to draw on (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 58). Currently she works solely for herself.

She sees the absorption of her early creative and innovative ideas becoming mainstream (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 313) without her capitalising on it due to a number of reasons, including her focussing on bringing up her family. She fears being marked as a 'sunday painter', believing that the market has contempt and disregard for them. Sholette also mentions the post-modern artisanal amateur and 'sunday worker' (2011, p. 30). Her work is 'pure' and of the avant-garde, where she creates work with no commercial outlet, recognising that the eight year project embracing her father's illness, although of merit, is not likely to be appropriate for a commercial gallery to promote or ever be a saleable commodity. She has some legitimacy as an artist, being invited to demonstrate her skills at Troon Art Club, but the cultural power systems at play have not formally recognized any of her worth. Without an avenue to exhibit her creative work, she has limited ways to promote herself or develop dialogues within the arts community. The project set around her father was autonomous (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 321) which was personalised work with little interest from the marketplace. The work was neither suited to the field of 'high end' production nor to mass audience appeal. It was a niche output meeting a personal need for catharsis and resolution, and independent of the field. Karen has the specific principle of legitimacy as she is an artist who is autonomous and self-sufficient, but she has a limited network and poor social capital (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 350).

Karen has struggled to persuade art dealers who act as the cultural and symbolic bankers in this field to invest in her creative work. She has also not been discovered or found a mentor to open doors for her. The dealers critiquing and reviewing of her work judged its appropriateness, then she was able identify her place within the overall structure (Becker, 1974, Csikszentmihalyi, 1997).

Without prior cultural capital built through having credibility with the dealers, it is challenging to promote and sell work online as anything more than a commodity, priced for whatever the market would offer, for its aesthetic value.

Karen sits within Greg Sholette's world of 'creative dark matter' and has had limited recognition for her creative work. Currently she is hidden from view with a studio filled with artwork and not recognised by the cultural gatekeepers, and is likely be one of the majority who are going to fail at achieving anything artistically significant in the art world, although she is forever optimistic.

Government support – how cultural policy has impacted the artists

Karen has not tried to access any government or local authority resources. This artist feels she has no avenues to find any form of support and is disenfranchised from the Scottish government cultural policy.

Bryan Evans

<http://bryanevans.com/>

Figure 5. Artist: Bryan Evans, Title: Last leaves of Autumn on Horselethill, Medium: Watercolour, gouache and watercolour pencils on paper, Dimensions: 70x50cm, Date: 2019. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Bryan Evans completed an art foundation course in Dyfed College of Art in Camarthen, and then studied for a degree in fine art at Loughborough College of Art in Leicestershire. He came to Glasgow as an exchange student for three months back in the 1987 and liked Glasgow, so came to stay a year later. His works are mainly in watercolours, etchings and mezzotints. He lived in bedsit land and took his work around galleries and shops knocking on framers doors and asking if they would buy his work. He did the potboiler paintings to try to make an impact and has managed to always been employed throughout his artistic life and has been earning a living since 1990. Bryan, as a creative practitioner is obviously part of the arts scene in Scotland but has always felt himself very much as an individual getting on with basically selling his creative work.

His network is small and he uses the Print Studio and used to work out of a Wasps studio in Dennistoun in Glasgow, and has exhibited in a number of galleries in the west of Scotland.

He has seen individuals who apply for grants and it's just not really in his makeup to do that sort of thing. He just doesn't have the mindset to tell people what he thinks they want to hear, and so he basically produces things that enough people want to buy to keep him in business, and so he has never applied for any grants. He knows some artists who have gone down the funding route and they've really put a lot of effort into it for little return and the majority, will be making little pockets of money to help publish their catalogues and things, He believes they never get money to pay to help them actually do what they want to do. Applying for grants is a skillset all of its own, which involves a lot of work, and he neither wants to put the time into it, nor has the skillset to do it.

Bryan is not a member of any kind of art society. He puts artwork into some of the shows occasionally and they get success some of the time. He sees it as an embarrassment to be associated with the art organisations, and feels more strongly about it the older he gets. For political reasons he has a problem with ever putting work into anything with 'royal' in the title.

His art work is fairly traditional and representational of what's around the Scottish urban landscape. He planned world domination, starting in the West of Scotland, but hasn't got very far in Scotland and a little bit further afield. Expats as far as Canada, Australia, Europe and America, buy his artwork, and he sells reproduction prints, cards and calendars of his work. Ninety plus percent of his income comes from Scotland. It's quite nice, because he's got a feeling that of any place in the world that you want to try and make a living as an artist, Scotland is incredibly difficult. There is a lack of appreciation of what creative people do, and if that's taken one hundred hours to do and therefore, it's got a value of 'x', people here just say no, they won't pay the actual 'hour based' value. Pricing is such a weird thing. Until someone's give you money for something, you are just selling them pigment on bits of paper or board. What he produces could sell for millions, or it could end up in the skip. Bryan believes the dividing line between that is a strange one with no logic behind it and you're only worth what someone's willing to pay. Quite a lot of Bryan's income comes from selling reproduction prints of his work. He does have a sales representative who sells some of his prints for him, who is part of his support network. He produces the artworks and then prints them in his studio and sells them directly, offering original prints, paintings and reproduction prints and reproductions of other things. He tries very hard to delineate between the two and doesn't do limited edition reproductions.

For the last twenty years, his salesman has been selling prints to the framing trade, and sells a lot of Bryan's prints. Originals, reproductions and everything were selling pretty nicely. 2020 was a lot different. He's relied less on galleries over the last few years as opposed to the early 90's, when he started living in Scotland and everything was sold mainly through small commercial galleries. A lot of them have gone by the wayside over the last ten years and he's not really tried to replace them.

He's had a website for almost 20 years, and uses Facebook and Instagram and people can find his work if they go online quite easily.

Things have changed over the last eight months as virtually all his income has been through online sales, and he thinks it will totally change how his paintings will sell. He sold a painting recently and swapped messages with the buyer who said, "it's so great that we've cut out the galleries", and because that reduces his sales costs, ordinary people can now afford to buy his work and he's been selling quite a lot.

He appreciates the support galleries have given him and is where he is because of them. But over the years, he's learned the benefits of galleries, and the downsides of them. There are still several galleries who sell his work, and he is very happy with them. He also exhibits in some of the bigger open shows if he can get his artwork accepted. He works on the principle that he'd rather have ten percent of a million pounds than a hundred percent of nothing. He's always tried not to annoy galleries by selling work online and thinks that the decent galleries accept that, so it's trying to get the balance right.

Damien Hirst and Tracy Emin, both British artists are the same age and contemporaries of his, and it appears that if you're going down that route of getting on the contemporary gallery scene, you're effectively appealing almost exclusively to six to ten people acting as gatekeepers who will decide on who is successful. He's always been dubious about that and coming from a fairly working class background, would much rather let people decide if they like his work and that dictates what he does. If money had never been a necessary part of producing his artwork, the work would probably be very different to what it is now, but, he's had to produce things to sell. The contemporary art world doesn't have to worry about that in the same way, but they are all selling something of course.

So, you can sell to the collectors, but you're appealing to the gatekeepers, who want cutting edge stuff. They warn you that you can't be looking over your shoulder, paying the rent at the end of the month. You're looking to see what the market wants and you can't be off because if you are too far out, you're going to have no one to buy your work.

He avoids using the term 'artist' because it opens up a can of worms about what art is. He's a painter and printmaker, and struggles with the term artist, but fundamentally he is one.

All artists want to produce brilliant art. He would like to producing great work that will be remembered in years to come. He produces prints and cards and does original prints, etchings, metal prints and paintings. So, if you were to add up all the people who've bought his work over the last thirty years or so, it's in the many thousands. He produces his own inkjet prints, and small scale stuff, and if he wants some larger things he gets it done commercially.

At the moment, his work is virtually all painting because he hasn't been going to the Glasgow Print Studio after the Covid locked down. He's got a studio in the garden, and has actually bought a small printing press, but barely uses it at the moment. So, pre-pandemic, he was probably spending about ten percent of his time producing original prints and one day, every two weeks, he'd be doing printmaking. And then there's the reproduction prints and these are just the practical things to do to earn a living. Probably twenty percent of his time is doing the practical elements of cutting, folding, printing, preparing for print, meeting with his sales rep, and probably sixty percent of the time is painting and twenty percent on original prints.

For the first couple of months, he was just painting away quite happily, hermit like, in his studio, enjoying the Covid break and then in early May, he thought he'd give the 'Artist Support Pledge' a go with some of his smaller works and it really took off. And then he started selling lots of things through that route. It was the impetus for him to start selling stuff online and people who've seen his work started buying there. In the last six months, virtually every painting he has sold has been of a tenement close. He's been doing lots of closes. He wanted to paint them purely because he found them interesting and they served a purpose for his abilities. But people in the west of Scotland like them, so he produced thirty artworks of tenement closes. You have to produce paintings that people buy, but a lot of the time, you don't know what it is until you've done it. It's all about luck, but it seems to have a direct relationship between working incredibly hard and being lucky as well.

John Hegley, who is a poet, and musician, wrote a book, and he said, if two thousand people buy a CD from you a year, that's a living, you know, it's ten quid, twenty thousand pounds in the bank, that's your basic living. But, if you can bang stuff in the back of your car, and drive around, doing a gig for 50 people, a couple of times a week, and a bunch of people buy your CD, that's your living. Well, that's sort of the principle Bryan works on, if he sells a few, handful, two or three reproduction prints a week, painting every now and then, bits and pieces here and there, that's a living. Occasionally, people have asked him for advice for up and coming artists or painters, and he says to persevere, because if you carry on going long enough, the opposition sometimes literally dies off and if you stick with it, eventually you've sort of become successful to some extent, just because people can see you're still doing artwork thirty years on.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

Bryan Evans artistic career has an interesting relationship to theories of Bourdieu. As to a creative identity, he does not regard himself as an artist, even though he is clearly one. Bryan has no regard for arts organisations and academies and subscribes to the philosophy of Groucho Marx in that regard. He has some institutional capital through his art qualifications.

He bridges engagement with the symbolic power of the dominant group, set between bourgeois art, where he has been given a lowly place of honour and a section of his work is defined as merchandise, a much lower production of industrial art which has popularity with a broader audience (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 141). He has the ability to maximise the economic value of his work through printing and selling multiple versions of his intellectual capital through printed cards, calendars and prints, together with sales of the original work. His artistic practice has broader 'mass audience' appeal where thousands of ordinary consumers are able to purchase his printed artwork.

He believes that if you're going down the route of getting into the contemporary gallery scene, you're effectively appealing almost exclusively to six to ten incredibly powerful people acting as elite gatekeepers who will decide who is successful.

His legitimacy corresponds to 'bourgeois' taste and its consecration by the dominant class and those in power through the exhibitions of his work in galleries. Then he has the principle of legitimacy which is ordained by the general public representing the "mass audience" who purchase his print work. (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 350)

In the post-modern world he believes that painters are a dying breed. He is clearly a cultural worker producing creative goods for the cultural economy and his work is subordinate to market demands. (Becker, 1974)

Although he is not avant-garde, his work has been consecrated by the elite through his work of art being elevated as a symbolic piece of contemplation in a gallery space and he is rewarded with some artistic prestige.

His habitus brings highly developed skills in painting and printmaking together with an entrepreneurial flair which has given him a full time career through his artistic practice. His business acumen utilises galleries in the west of Scotland and he has a sales representative to sell and promote his work, often to niche customers in the

framing trade. He balances sales of his work through these different channels. There has been some critical discourse around the artist and his work in local newspapers.

With Covid and online selling, Bryan has embraced this medium, which bypasses galleries for the time being and this allows him to engage directly with his customers, offering them better value for money. He appreciates the value that the galleries have added to his work and in their promotion of him. Bryan has already built up his artistic profile throughout his working life in partnership with the galleries and clients appreciate his style and subject matter, so stepping into online selling has been very positive for him.

Becker's 'collective action' applies in a limited way to Bryan's artistic output. Galleries, newspapers and his sales rep have supported his sales but he is becoming more self-reliant and independent, taking on more of the sales and promotional activities himself. He still calls upon external help in printing large artworks but is able to manage the smaller production material himself.

Csikszentmihalyi offers his systemic model of artists developing their skills, whilst producing creative artworks, within a cultural context, and overseen by the field, within a social context of trusted experts. Bryan taps into the culture of the west of Scotland and his artwork is influenced by his environment. Gallery owners give his work value and credibility. He has constant feedback through customers' purchases of his range of artworks and tailors it accordingly.

Bryan didn't have a mentor to open doors and support him. He had to open the doors all by himself and in his case, being a gifted individual and salesman was all he had to succeed. He needed to develop good persuasive selling techniques as he had to sell his creative work to survive. (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997)

Nothing that Bryan produces is politically motivated, or counter institutional and he sits in between Sholette's elite high art workers and those hidden creative dark matter creatives who are not given any recognition and are rejected. He sells his artwork to middle and working class customers. Bryan embraces neoliberal demand and supply economics where market demand dictates the nature of the artworks he produces. However, his republican values show through with a disdain for royalty and of elite institutions.

Bryan now utilises the digital communication technologies, developed to support neoliberal capitalism, which have indirectly opened up sales opportunities for him and allows communications directly with his clients, cutting across the traditions of the elite art marketplace.

Scottish Government Support – how cultural policy has impacted the artists

Bryan has no interest in engaging with government or local authorities funding to support him. He has seen individuals who apply for grants and it's just not really in his makeup to do that sort of thing. He believes that artists spend a lot of time applying for funding for very little return. Some will get support to help publish their catalogues and things but they never get any money to help them actually produce artwork that they want to do. Applying for grants is a skill set all of its own, which involves a lot of work, and he neither wants to put the

time into it, nor has the skill set to do it. He uses the Glasgow Print Studio which does get some financial help from government, and so he has benefited to a small extent from that support.

David Reid

<https://davidreidart.wordpress.com/>

Fig 6, Artist: David Reid, Title: Lady Cosgrove, Medium: oil on canvas. Dimensions: 60"x42" Date: 2013. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

David always wanted to be an artist, and felt it was inside him. He had innate creative talent, but felt he never had a mentor or anyone to guide or support him down that path whilst growing up in Irvine, a west coast provincial new town, with its own issues of poverty and mass unemployment since the deindustrialization of the Thatcher years. His education and employment history included completing his apprentice fitter training at ICI, studying as a first year maths undergraduate at the University of the West of Scotland and gaining a graphic design HND at the College of Building and Printing. This was all wrapped around a range of temporary jobs and work placement schemes, including working as an illustrator on a historical manual of Kilwinning, as a clerk in the Post office and being a house husband to his two daughters till they went to school.

In his late 30's, after being a regular visitor to the Vennel Gallery at the Burns Heckling shop in Irvine, which was run by the local council, and developing rapport with staff there, he was presented with an opportunity by an arts officer to show his creative work. Eighteen months later, at his first opening show which was very

successful, he was able to highlight his developing artistic portraiture skills. This led to him being offered a further opportunity to develop a series of portraits of local people and a contract to work over the next two years on local 'well kent faces' focussing on public inclusiveness, by Jo Levison, North Ayrshire council's senior arts officer who went on to promote him, launch his artistic career and help to turn him into a well-respected local portrait artist. The 'well kent faces' exhibition was launched at the opening of the redeveloped Harbour Arts Centre in Irvine, and through it David was introduced to a broader creative network of artists and patrons. As part of the contract, his two years of work was owned by the council and the collection of eighteen paintings is now primarily kept in storage from where works are in constant rotation for view around council and public buildings

His raw talent was identified and nurtured by Jo, as a local authority gatekeeper, resources were allocated and opportunities offered. A lot of this was based on luck and good timing. His portraiture commissions developed from working with the local towns folk to paintings of more well-known dignitaries in Glasgow and at the height of his 'fame' he was commissioned to paint Lady Cosgrove, Scotland's first female Supreme Court judge. He has since then had a regular number of requests for portrait commissions. David has utilised the Wasps artist studios at the harbour side on and off for a number of years.

At the end of this period he made the choice to develop an art teaching career when he was given the opportunity to present his work initially to school parties and then to develop art projects with local primary schools. He then progressively developed leisure workshops supporting old age pensioners at the Harbour Arts Centre in Irvine until he had a full time position. After this he struggled to manage his commitments to both his teaching and the amount of commissions he was able to produce, resulting in a progressive decline of his artistic output.

David defined himself as a painter and did not regard himself as a true artist. He saw himself more as a portrait painter, who worked for clients and painted what they specifically wanted him to paint. Real artists worked on their own projects and had a different skillset and did things differently. All his life he has seen himself as a painter inside, even when he was doing something else. As an autodidact he has been working on developing his skills by creating artwork in the styles of famous artists using their techniques of composition and application of paint. This initially generated a confusion in his style of working where he no longer saw himself but now he sees his own style shining through again, incorporating new learnings into his practice

Covid and lockdown have been the catalyst for David to review and reflect on his artistic practice and career progression. There is currently no opportunity to teach and he has focused back on the completion of a backlog of commissioned work. He has recently been approached by an Edinburgh gallery to exhibit with them and a steady stream of portrait commissions are in progress, together with the mental space that is allowing a renewed interest in developing his craft through the exploration of painting in both digital and traditional techniques. Focusing on local landscapes and still life have brought the opportunity to develop personal work for himself again. He feels this Covid break has given him time to recognise deep change happening within him and that process is still evolving and has still some way to go before its resolution.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

From a Bourdieuan perspective David is well aware he is offering a creative 'service' to his clients which is subordinate to market demands. However, he is often working for clients within his community who are not dominant, but of equal class, however he still has to meet their aesthetic values within his work. His work of family members may be the only painting that they own. With most of his work being of paid commissions, this comes with a lack of independence in the production of his work, reducing his artwork to that of merchandise and lacking any 'signification' (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 141).

Although he does not define himself as an artist, the quality of his work was recognised and identified as such by several art officers at the Vennel Gallery who offered him exhibition space there and then later in the Harbour Arts Centre in Irvine, which has an art gallery exhibiting local artists work. His work was elevated progressively through these exhibitions, with the collection of his 'well kent faces' and then through commissions for portraits of clients of progressively higher status and social standing in Scotland. There is a clear field of power within the patrons who utilised his skills to articulate and symbolically embed that power visually within his commissioned portraits, highlighting the heteronomous principle of those who dominate society both politically and economically. His title as an artist is legitimised, both through his work meeting 'bourgeois' taste and being consecrated by those in power, and though its appreciation more broadly in a local context by the general public representing the 'mass audience'.

David Reid utilises new media structures and social media to keep in touch with his audience through a blog, Instagram and Facebook. He has limited connections with galleries and critics, choosing instead to work within his community and offers a service to them. Since he no longer serves powerful clients he has reverted back out of the realm of the sacred and works again in purely financial terms. Bourdieu does not mention the fluid dynamics of artists who move in and out of the art market place due to personal circumstances and time of life. This is often a gendered issue, although not in David's case.

David's story is an interesting one where he has been 'discovered' by the arts officers who brought value into his work by promoting him and consecrating his work and bringing him into the arts market place through the two gallery exhibitions (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997, p. 7). The prestige of Jo Levinson, the council senior arts officer was also enhanced through her 'discovery' of David and her ability to commission a collection of work that now acts as a community resource, and a metaphorical bridge between civil society and the power held by the local council. The council arts officers invested time and resources in David, simultaneously building their own prestige and reputations in the process, and meeting their functional remit in successfully discovering and bringing new artistic talent to the fore. Jo's passion in supporting David and her team's efforts to maximise his talent and create a supportive environment for him to flourish is commendable. They elevated his work, helped build a profile for him through their own networks and certainly created a charismatic aura around him. Jo Levinson acted as cultural banker and guarantor of any purchaser's economic investment, through her own economic support in the purchase of his collection on behalf of the local council. She utilised her own symbolic capital created both within and out with her job to connect him to the art world.

David's habitus brings creative artistic talent from a working class background, but his personality is shy, and withdrawn. His fear of rejection and failure and need for a peaceful and stable life has acted against him in sustaining and developing a high profile artistic career focusing on high quality portraiture. The paradox of this is he has now developed his outward facing communication skills through working as a full-time art teacher. He struggles with identity as an artist, perhaps because he has never gone through an art school training even though others praise his work and he clearly had the many attributes of a practicing artist. There is a derivative nature to newer aspects of his work in landscape and still life, and a true voice and independent thought are still being developed. The quality of his work is of a very professional standard.

He certainly fits comfortably within Becker's model where the artworks are created through 'collective action', and the support of the local authority art officer team was critical to his early success. They developed his understanding of what it took to be an artist, developed his interpersonal skills and worked on growing his confidence to build a career as an artist. David believes he has no elevated status as an artist, and comfortably sits within the role as a cultural worker. He is personally driven to create artworks but does not speak of his work in terms of cultural and spiritual activity, purely as selling his portraits as a market driven commodity.

Csikszentmihalyi identifies that the success of creative artists is often determined by chance events, where a connection to a mentor opens doors to successful recognition of the artist by the creative field (Csikszentmihalyi, 2007, p. 341). This is so appropriate in David's case, where the Vennel Gallery arts officers identified someone who had talent and progressively developed and elevated them to a national level of scrutiny. Csikszentmihalyi also notes that being a gifted individual is not enough to succeed. Creative communities make the specific act of creative art production valued and they nurture new talent and their induction into the art world. The arts officers at the Vennel gallery initially did this for David and then support was further enhanced by their team leader. These creative communities share understandings of artistic practice and have common positions on thinking about and appreciating art. David noted that due to the banking crash and Westminster politics of austerity this whole sector within local government was erased due to service cuts and all the art development staff involved were made redundant. The recent Scottish government Cultural policy has identified a need to redevelop this area within local authority priorities and a focus on cultural policy is to be enhanced.

There initially appears to be no real relationship between the work of David Reid and the political art practice and theorizing of Greg Sholette. David is not political within his work, and has no activist agendas. He has been successful in his own terms and certainly doesn't fit the dark matter of Sholette's world. Although there was certainly a power dynamic between David and the council arts officers who enabled and elevated him, their motives appeared noble and were not overtly exploitative. They used their positions of power and access to financial resources and opportunities to benefit David and help him maximise his potential in the community.

As the art world is opened up to David and his fame spreads he increases his prices for his work by ten-fold, but the pressure and the stress of working at that level acted as a disincentive to him. He would much rather be a big fish in a small pond, and he reverted to being the painter of portraits from photographs in his community. This was a political act of choosing to engage with the art world on his own terms. He charges for his work based on what he thinks his customers can afford, a very socialist approach to pricing.

We can see that many of the arts theorists' ideas around the nature of arts practice apply directly to David.

Scottish Government Support – how cultural policy has impacted the artists

We can see that the Scottish government and local authority arts policies at that time were highly effective in finding new artistic talent and nurturing and growing his talents to a point where he was able to develop a successful artistic career. Giving access to a gallery space within the local community and having a team of arts officers there to educate and support him and other local artists was a very valuable resource.

The encouragement and enabling of the arts officers took embers of talent and brought it into to life and David's experience shows what that support can do for an individual, and his creativity connected with the production of the lives of 'well kent faces' in the community. There is a recycling of the cultural capital produced through the collection of work, with his portraits enhancing the community public spaces, and then coming full circle through his learning journey and his passing on of his creative skills onto others.

It could be seen that David failed to financially capitalise on his early creative success when he was at his peak and after his work had been given a form of sanctification. He then withdrew progressively from the art market into focussing more on teaching creative workshops at the HAC in Irvine. His development as a successful community arts teacher suits his temperament and has been central to his creative growth and his identity as a sophisticated painter of portraits who enjoys working in his own community.

Bella Green

<https://www.bellagreen.co.uk>

Fig 7: Artist: Bella Green, Title: Tuscan studio, Medium: oil on canvas, Dimensions: 24 x 24", Date: 2014. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Bella has lived and has her studio in Lockerbie, Dumfriesshire since 1997. Her arts education was initially at Harrow School of Art followed by a BA(Hons) in Fine Art Painting at Norwich School of Art which was then led to a postgraduate year earning her an Advanced Teaching Diploma from Leicester University. Afterwards Bella taught for several years before moving into computer graphics training & support. She continued to paint and tried computer art but was never satisfied. She moved to Rotterdam and found a studio to work in whilst still working part time two days a week in London. From there she moved back to Scotland, set up weekly art classes, an occasional art club and taught a summer school for the next ten years. She worked part time but mainly as an artist and exhibited at local galleries. Her network at that time was mainly through her students on her courses.

When Bella decided to go full time as an artist she collected ten pieces of artwork and with her CV approached several galleries to talk to them. She was working on her big art pieces whilst running a summer workshop and her students saw them in progress. One of those students promoted her works through a written piece in the Glasgow Herald and arranged for her to exhibit them for the first time, and after that at another gallery which had the space to hang them. She also bought one of Bella's big paintings and gifted it to the Woman's Library in Glasgow. Her husband, David Donaldson, a university professor, told her about a cousin who ran an art school, at the Centro d'Arte Verrocchio in Tuscany, so Bella applied to teach there, and a vacancy arose in the second year of asking. She has taught two courses there for the last twenty years and has been very successful, and teaches people of all ages and professions intensive courses in art practice.

It was only when she moved from the north of Scotland down to Dumfries that she really developed a supportive artistic network. Dumfries council had an arts officer who supports a community of artists and Bella wanted to live near a more supportive creative environment. She offered her services and volunteered to be part of a 'visual arts focus group' and that was the beginning of her new network. So, by volunteering in an area where nobody knew her and through networking at monthly meetings where they would talk over ideas generated by the arts officer, it gave her the opportunity to bounce her own ideas off other practicing artists and helped grow Bella's creative network. This focus group was responsible for the development of the Spring Fling, a very successful, artist led initiative where locals and tourists travelled around the area, visiting artists in their own studios and gallery spaces, which is still going on sixteen years later. She found opportunities through all of this to connect with galleries, which also expanded her network.

There are four art societies in Scotland, the Visual Arts Scotland (VAS), the Society of Scottish Artists (SSA), the Royal Society of Scottish Painters in Watercolour (RSW), and the Royal Scottish Academy (RSA). Members need to be elected to join these four top societies of professional artists in Scotland. Bella planned to submit to the Royal Scottish Academy summer exhibition, although she has been a professional member of VAS for twenty years. She exhibits regularly and has work in many private collections in the UK and worldwide. Her works are held in collections at Gracefield Arts Centre, in Dumfries and in the Women's Library, Glasgow. Recently she has shown at quite a few galleries including Hertfordshire, Edinburgh and in Glasgow. Of the most recent shows, she had approached two galleries directly and three galleries had approached her, most likely through her contact details being available in the Spring Fling Catalogue. She used to go quite regularly every year to the Affordable Art Fair in Battersea and to the Edinburgh Art Fair.

Bella has become aware of new art market trends where dealers no longer have premises anymore. They build up an online portfolio for the gallery and then go to the art fairs to make personal contacts and sell their artists work. They would then sell online to the new clients that they acquire through this approach, and that's a new selling model to her.

When she starts looking at galleries taking her work again, she will approach different specialist galleries, showing one her landscape stuff, one her still life stuff and one gallery for the mixed media stuff, as each gallery caters for a unique clientele and she needs to tailor her work to meet these differing audiences' expectations.

Bella believes there's a gender bias against women artists. In her generation there was definitely cultural conditioning to not push too hard, and a sexist environment to deal with as a young woman artist. Early in her career it was very noticeable. She wonders if in your dotage women get to compete on equal terms. When she was younger and something didn't work out the first time, she would just assume it was all her fault and scuttled away. And now, she knows it's not like that at all, but it's taken her a long time to get to that realization. So that brings a different kind of confidence. But she realises now that making your own luck is all about getting yourself out there. With a bit of luck, and perseverance you can be successful, just keeping on going, and not taking failures personally, which is quite hard to do. There's also this Scottish cultural thing of 'who do you think you are'? Don't put yourself out there on a pedestal and don't show off what you can do.

Bella believes there's now new pressures on artists in managing social media on the internet, with Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. She doesn't want to spend her life on a computer, but she's got a Facebook page, and uses it occasionally but not enough. She has an Instagram page, which has been set up to promote her jewelry, which has not been started yet and she has found that Etsy is not very good. She just wants to do it all in a different way. She has a website, which she has paid for to be set up, and she's got stuff on it, but it's not being promoted yet because she's not ready, as there's certain things she wants to do with the photographing of her jewelry and hasn't had time to do that. She's been trying for two and a half years to get this set up, and so before the next exhibition she has decided, to just get content up there that is good enough. It wouldn't be perfect, but would be okay and it can be tweaked and made perfect afterwards.

Bella has another idea where she finds an outlet that has a different business model to galleries, where you can just hire the space on the shelf, and take the space out for a year to drive people to the website. She is a painter who makes jewelry, with a lot of interesting one-off pieces that might bring people to look at her paintings, so she believes you've just got to be flexible and look at other ways around. The main thing for Bella is that she loves it and what makes it sell is her enthusiasm in sharing her process openly with people.

Bella, understanding the limitations of her website, has experimented with a pop-up shop and sold a lot of her jewelry at the Spring Fling event. There were very limited clients passing through but she made a reasonable amount of money through it. A good thing that came from the pop-up shop was the social connections she's made in Lockerbie as local business people came in to see what she was doing. She hoped to have a pop-up gallery set up for Christmas where she would rent space just for two days and notify her mailing list of her opening hours. She would include some small paintings into the mix. She also has other entrepreneurial ideas such as offering polymer art and prosecco parties at her home. She is unsure of advertising on Facebook or Instagram, as she has no idea as to its effectiveness. Her main experiences have been that everything goes by word of mouth, and that's how you get to be known. Simple as that! It's the most important thing. And she also believes that being willing to tell people a bit about her backstory is important, because they connect to it. When a client buys a piece of art, it is for emotional reasons. It's a beautiful thing, and she's very grateful. Bella thinks as an artist you have to not think like somebody who's just selling a commodity and she never takes it for granted that people are willing to buy her work.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

In Bella's career path she has been a practicing artist all her life, holding down full-time jobs in the arts industry to support herself. Her training as an arts teacher has been central to her financial stability and as she has become older she has been able to support herself more fully, making a living as a full-time artist, supplemented by her two weeks teaching art in Tuscany during the summer time.

Csikszentmihalyi suggests that the success of creative artists is often determined by chance events, where a connection to a mentor opens doors to successful recognition of the artist by the creative field. We can see this play out when Bella's work is recognised as of high quality by one of her students who helped launch her publicly, actively promoted her work through the facilitation of a large written piece in the Glasgow Herald and arranged for her to exhibit a body of work for the first time. She also bought one of Bella's big paintings and gifted it to the Woman's Library in Glasgow. Her husband, David Donaldson, a professor at the university, told her about a cousin who ran an art school, the Centro d'Arte Verrocchio in Tuscany, which opened a doorway for Bella to teach there. She has delivered two art courses there for the last twenty years which gave her some 'guaranteed' funding each year. Csikszentmihalyi also believed chances of success happening is increased where the artists interact with bodies and collectives centred around artistic activity such as art schools and centres of artistic practice.

She has a balance between the heteronomous and autonomous principles, having the ability to create work for herself and artwork for the marketplace, although she looks out for opportunities to exhibit her new passions, but the marketplace does not direct that specific work. Bella's niche work in polymers is clearly sitting within the avant-garde, with her challenging and contesting the materials used as purely 'craft and hobbyist', as worthy of recognition as having a 'higher' art purpose, or as Sholette suggests, the deskilling of post-modern art practice that the artisanship of creative practice has been left to the 'amateurs' as the art world embraced much more philosophical and conceptual art practices. Has Bella been left behind in old ways of art production or is she forging a new path?

Bella has a small network of galleries supporting her fine art sales and has regularly attended art fairs to promote her work. She is actively trying to utilise online platforms to promote her work but struggles to find time to do this effectively and understand this new landscape. She sees a need for an entrepreneurial spirit to sustain her, most recently trying out a pop-up shop for a week during Spring Fling in Lockerbie.

She recognises that she is a producer of creative artifacts within a cultural economy. She also identifies with the notion that even so, art isn't a commodity and that clients' purchasing of artwork is primarily driven by emotional reasons.

Bella has been a professional member of Visual Arts Scotland for twenty years, and submits for the Royal Scottish Academy summer exhibition, tapping into the reputation of these organisations to validate her artistic position and increase her social capital. Becker notes that only the most gifted artists are allowed access to these academies and to be labelled as artists.

She has not made any efforts to access any direct Creative Scotland or apply for any other specific funding.

Bella's work sits between a field of restricted 'high end' production supplied through conventional art galleries and art fairs and broader 'mass audience' appeal, where ordinary consumers are able to purchase her artwork and artistic jewelry at affordable prices in innovative contexts like her pop-up gallery shop, indirectly offering a unique, distinctive and radical approach to materials she has used.

Bella hurdles all three principals of legitimacy, being autonomous and self-sufficient in allocating time to 'pure' art working, offering artwork that meets standards of 'bourgeois' taste and consecration and offering other artwork to the general public representing the "mass audience".

Her early exhibited work in response to the horrors of war at one point was deeply political and feeds into Greg Sholette's definitions of activist artists, but she has progressively developed work that is more mainstream with no political overtones that is purely market driven for the creative economy

Bella struggled through Covid with no work, ill health and her art teaching workshops in Tuscany were cancelled.

Government Support – how cultural policy has impacted the artists

Bella moved to Dumfries because of the supportive dynamic arts environment there, which is centred around the Dumfries and Galloway local authority arts officer based in Gracefields Art Centre in Dumfries. Through offering her services and volunteering to be part of a 'visual arts focus group' she developed a new creative network. By volunteering and offering free time in an area where nobody knew her and through networking at monthly meetings, she was given the opportunity to bounce her own ideas off other practicing artists and this helped grow Bella's connections. This focus group was responsible for the development of the Spring Fling, a very successful, artist led initiative which is still going on sixteen years later. She found opportunities through all of this to also connect with gallerists, which also expanded her network more broadly.

She has built up a support network within the arts community in Dumfriesshire and resources targeting the creative artistic community by the local authority has been very valuable, and is supported and funded by the cultural policy of the Scottish government.

Shona Barr

<http://www.shonabarr.com>

Fig 8. Artist: Shona Barr, Title: Towards Jura, Medium: oil on canvas, Dimensions: 71x92cm, Date: 2011 (Collection of the Glasgow Art Club). The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Shona studied at Glasgow School of Art and chose to specialise in fine art, focussing on painting. A lot of her time was spent working down at the GSA hostel at Culzean in Ayrshire and she was inspired by the coastal landscapes there. Her early artwork used the landscape detail to create abstract works. In her fourth year show she sold many of her landscapes and life drawings in watercolour and was included in the Compass gallery's graduate show in Glasgow.

One of her works was chosen in the Hunting Group competition which was exhibited in a gallery in London. After that, an opportunity to access a foreign scholarship from the British Council came up and she applied and was invited to the Norwegian Embassy in London where she was offered a student residence and scholarship with a place at the Statens Kunstakademi in Oslo for an academic year starting after she graduated.

On her return from Oslo, she settled into the Wasp studios in Denniston, and used the Enterprise Allowance Scheme that gave basic benefits and the ability to develop her own business for a year. After her return from Norway she exhibited work produced during her stay there in Edinburgh at the Flying Colours gallery. After a successful show there, the gallery owner arranged for her to exhibit in a collaborative show down in London at Gallery Ten. Again, her artworks sold well, but to a different audiences' taste down there. She then exhibited

back at the Glasgow Art school's Newberry gallery in another collaborative show with some other students who had also been on travelling bursaries.

Two years on from graduating, her ex tutor at GSA contacted her about the development of a new Masters course in European Fine Art at Winchester School of Art, which was based in Barcelona for nine months and then three months back in Winchester. She applied and was accepted and received a grant from the Scottish Education department to support her there. The course was not very well run in Barcelona and she was not very inspired whilst she was out there and the majority of her MA show was of landscapes in rural Hampshire painted on her return.

The following January, the Edinburgh based Flying Colours gallery took a big stand at the London contemporary art fair and she was given a one woman show which was mostly of her Barcelona work, and again they sold well enough for both her and the gallery to be happy with it.

Jean Houldsworth who founded Flying Colours Gallery in Edinburgh and latterly in London has been a mentor in Shona's career, offering her the first shows in Edinburgh and then acting as her main gallerist to show her work in London, and has continued to support her though out her career.

Shona applied to the Scottish Arts Council for funding to help support her frame a new exhibition in the Lillie public art gallery in Milngavie, but was not given any funding. A month later a previous client of hers brought his brother to her studio who had just been given a golden handshake from retiring from his work and wanted some new paintings for his house, and bought five big paintings. So, she had a large sum of money just at the right time, to fund the show at the Lillie gallery,

More recently due to Covid, Creative Scotland were offering grants for personal development projects. Shona put in an application and with great effort, submitted it and again didn't get anything. Her bid was considered to be fundable, but did not get passed the next round and no feedback was given regarding its failure.

She has also been nominated by the GSA to apply for an art travel grant through the AEH Salvesen's Trust on several occasions but failed in her bids. She finds it a bit demoralising to apply for funding and not be successful, but is aware of others who have been successful in developing stained glass art and knows a musician who collaborated with a dancer being funded.

Shona hasn't collaborated with anyone creatively, but has worked as a group member in organising exhibitions. One project was located at the Briggait in Glasgow where the decanted Wasps artists put on a show and Shona loved the collaborative energy involved in making it happen.

Critical Reviews; at Shona's degree show, Jonathan Brown, who was writing for a magazine called Sports, a listings magazine for the Scotsman, wrote a review of the four Scottish art schools degree shows and said the best painter by far was Shona. Also, in the 90s, Clare Henry who was the arts critic of the Glasgow Herald and very influential at the time wrote about Shona's exhibition at the Roger Billcliff Gallery. Robin Hume, a GSA tutor who worked at Culzean had introduced Shona to the Billcliff gallery owner and he suggested the gallery

might have a look at Shona's work, as she had just had a show in Edinburgh and showed Roger Billcliff the list of artworks with all the wee sold red dots on them which made his eyes light up.

She's had reviews in the Scotsman for the show in Edinburgh and also had reviews of two or three shows early on in her career. She was in a group show at the Lillie gallery, which Emilio Coia wrote a lovely piece about her. She was really touched and then also got introduced to him, again through Robin Hume at the Glasgow Art club. Shona thinks fondly of him. A wee online Scottish Art Scene magazine did a feature on Shona, three or four years ago, with a wee blurb and some nice pictures.

Shona has an official website, and it has been of significant value for her in allowing clients to find her, although her online sale are a minor part of her income. Shona values the relationships she has with the galleries and doesn't allow the website to interfere with that relationship as they are her main source of income. Shona has a Facebook account and Instagram, which she hasn't ever posted any work. She also has a twitter account and has failed to tweet anything.

She now has the system set up so that she can do an Instagram post that also tweets and posts it on Facebook. But Covid lockdown has made her think about using online social media rather than just going along in the same way as she's always done.

With Covid's shutdown, a number of galleries have successfully used online media to continue operating, but some have been very slow to respond and some have just stopped trading. Exhibition openings at galleries haven't been so important in recent years. People now see the work online and perhaps arrange to view it and sometimes they buy it unseen. There's a trend of people wanting to buy directly from artists and are no longer seeing the value brought by galleries in the process.

Shona hasn't considered running prints of her artworks as her work is very tactile and could not be easily reproduced. The idea of creating a paper copy of a big oil painting just doesn't appeal to her. Her galleries have advised against it as they believe the clientele would be unhappy about it. The artworks are unique and her clients' value that. She once did do a design of a Christmas card for UNESCO which was for a charity.

When Shona was starting out, institutions like the Royal Scottish Academy had big open submission exhibitions. These were really an important public place to be seen and if you were accepted, lots of galleries saw you and you quite often received a couple of different inquiries from galleries. Times are changing and some galleries are struggling to survive, and they're all working online as well, which is a different process than exhibiting the paintings.

Shona doesn't have any initials after her name and has not been invited to join any of the arts organisations. She submits regularly and has had work accepted by the Royal Society of Scottish Painters in Watercolour and also has work accepted from the Glasgow Institute of Fine Arts. Several institutions invite applications whereas others run in a very old school traditional way, where you have to wait till a member invited you to apply and then go through an application process to join them.

There is an issue of rejection too in applying to join one of these institutions and what if you fail to be invited to join? Shona thinks you need to be thick skinned and young artists should put themselves out there and apply for everything. They should apply for open shows, and put their work out in public. Shona's advice to them is don't compromise and try and do something that's just going to fit, and just really try and keep to your vision and there will be someone somewhere who will want your thing.

Shona believes her work is not political and just shares her work that she hopes people will enjoy, one of the attributes that Csikszentmihalyi (1994) deems a creative act. It's just her escape. There was one thing Shona did in 1990, when Glasgow Zoo's contribution to the year of culture was to borrow a white tiger. She went and painted it because she liked tigers ... but tigers in a zoo? They're never going to be happy. So, she did a painting which had this tiger in it but it had big bars across the painting just to highlight, this was a caged tiger. And the tiger was big enough to fill the whole painting, so it was showing that it was a cramped, caged tiger. But that's as political as she's got.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

Bourdieu developed a language which helped define the power dynamics that support, validate and legitimise certain types of art practice over others, and identified aspects of cultural working that are core elements in the production of creative goods, (Bourdieu, 1996, p. 58). Shona Barr meets that criteria and has the identity of being a visual arts practitioner, and brings a lot of habitus and symbolic value with her, winning awards and scholarships whilst studying as a student. She has had a successful full time career painting landscapes and exhibiting regularly at galleries in both Scotland, London and internationally in Oslo, Barcelona and Hong Kong. Critics have written about her with high regard, one even commenting on her being the best graduate of her year across all the Scottish art schools.

As Shona develops her creative work she relies on the cultural power system to formally recognize her artworks' worth. The critical narrative and historical discourses developed to support the value of her artwork legitimizes it and at the same time reaffirms the power hierarchy that bestows that legitimacy upon it. Shona's work is clearly niche output and 'consecrated' through its appeal to a bourgeois audience. Her legitimacy comes from being autonomous and self-sufficient and for corresponding to that 'bourgeois' taste. Jean Houldsworth, the gallerist at Flying Colours was the mentor who discovered her and opened doors to Shona's recognition as an artist of note, as identified by Csikszentmihalyi (1997). Critical discourse around her artwork legitimizes both the artwork and the appointed critics, such as Jonathan Brown of the Scotsman and Clare Henry, the arts critic of the Glasgow Herald.

Becker (1974) highlights the artwork is produced through 'collective action' which also includes support and involvement of curators, critics, gallery owners, publishers and media organisations who locate the placing of that work within a cultural context and define its meaning and value and Shona clearly fits with that position.

She is also highly qualified in her field with a Masters in in European Fine Art, but yet after thirty years of practice she has not been invited to join any of the prestigious and privileged Scottish arts academies. She has

not been overly keen on applying to those who accept direct applications as she worries that she might be rejected by them also, so therefore she has limited her institutional capital in that area.

Bourdieu highlights the systems in place where old-school gatekeepers have been defining who becomes celebrity artists and what successful art practice should be like (Bourdieu & Nice, 1980, Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). Shona possibly lacks cultural capital and may not have developed the required networks and engagement within a contemporary art setting to merit an invitation? Maybe her recent profile may not be modern or dynamic enough in that context? Perhaps she is being squeezed out by up and coming artists with new perspectives, as the dominant art scene declines as new names introduce 'discontinuity, difference and revolution' in their new work and seek to displace the old order. Or is this an example of 'symbolic violence' where those in power create structural institutions such as the Royal Scottish Academy solely for their own aggrandisement, and through them, manage and have control of the arts, culture and aspects of the marketplace.

Shona produces work that is solely meaningful for her, although on occasion takes commissions from known clients who may give her a broad brief to create a landscape in a special area for them, so she bridges the heteronomous and autonomous principles to some degree, although primarily taking the heteronomous position (Bourdieu, 1983, p. 321).

Covid and the online market place

With regard to Covid and the shifting of gallery spaces online, Shona has deferred to the gallery owners as her major facilitators and 'cultural bankers' who have invested a lot in her career and she has not taken advantage of alternate ways of connecting with clients in respect to them (Bourdieu, 1996). She has a lifetime of working for clients and has built a network of connections and her history of being popular and successful, allows her the freedom to move into that space on her own because she has a reputation, has credibility and she's a known artist. If she was, an up and coming artists with no gallery experience, it would be quite a different situation. She wouldn't have that creative and cultural capital of being attached and supported by a specific gallery. If the galleries aren't able to sell on her behalf, then she would need to step outside that support. The dealers drive their own and their artists profiles, enhancing their values through the catalogues of exhibitions or in gallery spaces. Without them she would have needed to solely rely on the marketplace to make value and aesthetic judgements about her work (Bourdieu & Nice, 1980).

Shona recognises that there requires a lot of administrative work in supporting an online presence and struggles at present to motivate herself to do it all.

Her work is non-political and has no resonance with Gregg Sholette's theories, with the exception of her painting of the visiting caged tiger in Glasgow zoo.

Scottish Government support – how cultural policy has impacted the artists

Shona had access to the Wasp studios in Denniston, Glasgow and used the government's 'Enterprise Allowance Scheme' that gave basic benefits and the ability to develop her own business for a year when she was starting out.

She received a grant from the Scottish Education department to support her on a new Masters course in European Fine Art at Winchester School of Art, which was based in Barcelona for nine months and then three months back in Winchester.

Shona applied to the Scottish Arts Council for funding to support her frame a new exhibition in the Lillie public art gallery in Milngavie, but was not given any support. More recently due to Covid, Creative Scotland was offering grants for personal development projects. Shona put in an application and with great effort, submitted it and again was unsuccessful. The bid was considered to be fundable, but still failed! Shona has also been nominated by the Glasgow School of Art to apply for an art travel grant through AEH Salvesen's Trust on several occasions but also failed in her bids.

So, she has had very little support from the Scottish government during her art career, and applications require a great effort to complete and she finds it a bit demoralising to apply for funding and then not be successful, however she is aware of others who have been successful.

Inge Smith

<http://www.ingebjorgsmith.co.uk/1st%20Frameset.htm>

Fig 9, Artist: Inge Smith, Title: Birchwood Barn Owl, Medium: Gouache on paper, Dimensions: 19x36cm, Date: 2019. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Inge Smith graduated from Glasgow School of Art 1982 and was employed as a freelance illustrator for the BBC on children's TV until 2007 which brought in a chunk of her income each year. She also was employed as a part time lecturer at Glasgow School of Art, in addition to selling her paintings and exhibiting at a number of galleries across the UK. Currently she runs her own gallery, which is more profitable, as the commission take by other galleries is very high.

When Inge moved up north to Taine from Glasgow she was supported by the local council arts & exhibition sector officers would invite her down to exhibit at the Glasgow Art Fair each year. Lack of funding stopped that.

She also was employed to teach creative workshops with both children and adults in the early 90's for a few years and then that funding dried up too. She also did workshops at schools from a separate budget. The council also offered her advice on website development and helped to build one for her through Taine and District Development Trust.

Exhibiting at Art fairs developed Inge's network of contacts, and as well as in Glasgow she attended Edinburgh, Cambridge and Battersea Art Fairs. People would see her at the art fairs and then contact her through her website. She noticed a slump in enquiries and sales since Brexit was announced. Inge's work is quite affordable and has an awful lot of repeat customers but she thinks people were buying higher ticket items, possibly as investments.

Based on her artwork, she offers paintings, calendars, place mats, coasters, cards, tin mugs, notebooks and is currently working on handmade clocks with a clock face design and detail on the hands. When producing these items there is a risk in the choice of artwork to put on them as if you get it wrong you have invested a lot in work that people won't buy. She sells her work to people who can't afford to buy high priced artwork at the fairs but want to get something nice whilst they are there.

Inge has collaborated in having a stand to exhibit at the art fairs as the cost is quite high. She thinks there are now too many art fairs, after a number of new ones opened at the same time the art market nose-dived and stagnated around Brexit and the Scottish referendum.

Inge has exhibited internationally in Holland in 1996 and in the Shanghai Art Fair, where she collaborated with other artists who she met at the Cambridge Art Fair. There were cultural issues in selling in China where the right number of elements is an auspicious thing there, so for example the numbers of birds in a painting are important. She has not been too successful abroad and her work sells more locally, particularly in Edinburgh.

Online, Inge utilises her website and Facebook. She should be using Instagram, Etsy and Twitter as well, but they all need to be fed and time is limited. She has heard of artists setting up sites to help other artists during Covid but she isn't interested.

She was able to access government 'furlough' money through having her gallery and twenty years of accounts.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power

After graduating and building up freelancing and part time teaching employment in Glasgow, Inge moved up to the north east of Scotland to live. She has needed to have multiple revenue streams to support herself (Sholette, 2011). In addition to her art practice she opened her own gallery space, rented accommodation to other artists and continued to teach, offering workshops to differing age groups on behalf of the council and education authorities in Taine.

Inge was given support by Taine's local authority arts officers to attend the art fair in Glasgow and networked into the art scene through attending other art fairs across the UK. That initial support was helpful, where a

connection to a mentor opens doors to successful recognition of the artist by the creative field (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). Gallery curators were exposed to her work through the art fairs and offers of exhibitions followed as her network expanded. The curators support the creative production process but also create added value to the artistic endeavor through their contribution (Becker, 1974), however the percentage charges they make for that appear onerous for a struggling artist and in Inge's case, she takes a different route to sell her work if possible.

Her work is defined as 'affordable' so although she has exhibited extensively her work has not appreciated in value. She treats her art production as a commercial enterprise. Her artistic practice sits in a grey area of being both attractive to gallery owners for exhibition but failing to capitalise on that exposure is worthy of unpacking. Her work is attractive and sells and she promotes it through art fairs, with gallery owners making good commission from her sales. She has a website service supporting her (Becker, 1974), but her recognition and reputation has failed to grow. She is missing critical judgement perhaps, as the art world embraced newer, much more philosophical and conceptual art practices (Sholette, 2011, p. 30) and being a gifted individual is no longer enough to succeed (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997) or the gallery owners maybe are not high enough status themselves in the market place to elevate her artwork perhaps (Bourdieu & Nice, 1980, p. 265)?

Bourdieu noted that the production of artifacts within a cultural economy was surrounded by a range of contextual markers which are core to the generation and maximisation of their economic value. In this case, Inge's habitus brings high levels of artistic skill but is limited perhaps in recognition or reputation. She is not a member of any institution or academy and graduated from Glasgow School of Art in a design discipline, not in fine art, so she has some institutional capital. Her work does not appear to resonate with these markers which would elevate her artwork to a higher value and over time she has progressively commoditised her output to that of 'merchandise' subordinate to market demands meeting the interests or aesthetic values of the dominant classes.

Inge's work attracts a principle of legitimacy through the broader 'mass audience' due to its visual appeal and she prices herself where ordinary consumers were able to purchase her artwork. She also uses economies of scale by printing up her artworks onto consumer products, which devalues and restricts her from the field of 'high end' production and the possibility of the 'consecration' of her artwork. As a cultural worker, her artwork is clearly defined as lowlier industrial art through its popularity with a broader audience. Did she have any other option but to engage in the art market in this way to survive?

Inge does not produce or engage in political acts so her work has little resonance to Gregg Sholette's views, although he highlights the development of inexpensive digital communications technologies which facilitate artists like Inge and help support her connect with clients and galleries in an outlying area of rural Scotland.

Inge's role as an informal gallery curator not only gives her opportunities to exhibit her own work but she informally promotes and sells other artist's work too, and bridges the role of artist and curator.

Inge had assistance from the local council when she moved up to Taine, both through promoting her work at the Glasgow Art Fair and by supporting her by offering her work running workshops and developing projects at local schools. This stopped during the Conservative governments years of austerity.

Support given in the development of her website was funded by the local authority

She has never applied for any funding support through any government routes, but did get 'furlough' money through her gallery to help her during the Covid outbreak.

Louise Ritchie

<https://louiseritchie.com>

Artist: Louise Ritchie, Title: Between the Bronze and the Perspex, Medium: bronze casts, lithography & screenprint on Perspex, Dimensions: installation detail, approx. 1x1x1.5m. (full installation size - 5x5x6m.) Year: 2018. The artwork has been reproduced with permission from the copyright holder.

Louise Ritchie, is an Honours, Post Graduate and a Master of Fine Art graduate at Duncan of Jordanstone college of Art and Design in Dundee (DJCAD). She is also currently a lecturer on the BA (Hons) Contemporary Art Practice Programme at City of Glasgow College and is a former President of the Society of Scottish Artists (SSA). She has exhibited internationally, with her work being held in several major collections including The Mirror Group, London, University of Dundee, Dundee City Council and City of Glasgow College Art

Foundation. She has co-created projects for Angus Council as an Artist in Residence and is currently undertaking a practice-led PhD in Contemporary Art Practice at DJCAD.

After graduating, Louise briefly travelled to Spain with her partner and returned to stay in East Kilbride, then Glasgow. She sees challenges in making work in a supportive environment and in finding a tribe who understand your work with a shared consciousness about what you do. She found a job at the CCA in Glasgow working in the cafe and the galleries and built up her network with lots of people there. She found a studio and began making large scale abstract, 'colour field' type of paintings, which was work that had a performance of quality, felt environmental, felt physical, combined with her background in dance as well. So, these big giant paintings felt like she could do performance pieces and with that scale the spatial quality was really important.

She had shown in the Compass Gallery quite regularly in graduate and Christmas shows and then managed to get a big solo show with Cyril Gerber in 1996. So, she'd been out of college at that point for five years, which was a huge break for her selling everything there and it led her into being taken regularly to the big art fairs and smaller shows and dealers would come in and buy. So, there was a hot spot of sales for a good few years which was lovely, but within about two, three years of that she was starting to feel a little bit claustrophobic about how that was operating, because there was then almost an expectation that she would keep producing that same work that was highly saleable at that point, but she found that quite difficult. Also, if she wanted her work to evolve, develop and change, there would be resistance to that from the gallery dealers. She had a dealer in London who would phone from her yacht, every so often and ask Louise to just 'knock up' a duplicate red painting for her. So, she became very, very aware she was being commodified in that way and there was this kind of tacit pressure for her to stay the same.

Thing changed when she got married, and became pregnant, and that completely changed everything, because she could no longer work with oil paint and turps. Once she'd had her firstborn, that completely changed her sense of self and the work and all of those things that come with motherhood and new priorities. Then during the years bringing up her children, she was continuously at work teaching at the College of Building and Printing in the art department and continued to make work in the studios. She was aware that the work that she wanted to do was shifting further and further away from the work that galleries wanted and was becoming less bankable. Those connections were allowed to drift and she had three years of going right back under the radar again. So that when she started to make work more proactively once her youngest was approaching school-age and she felt like she wanted a bit of reinvention, this allowed her to not be defined by all that previous work. Gone are the days where you would get a gallery that would support you regardless of what your creative progression was because they can't afford to now, which is another thing about how they're funded. Compass Gallery used to receive a subsidy every year from Glasgow City Council which allowed them to put on shows every year that were in support of the artists who existed for the truthfulness of the art and who weren't commercial. They cut all that funding, so suddenly, artists were now going to have to be completely commercially supported. That changes everything because no longer can that gallery host work that it really wants to show, it can only host work that they'd get some sense of certainty that they're going to make some money from it.

Louise studied on the MFA in Art and Humanities at DJCAD as she was interested in philosophy and literature, which might sit alongside the work that she was making and so another reinvention came as she started creating bronze casts and giant screen prints on Perspex. This was completely unexpected for her and what is interesting, because when she went into art college all those years ago, she thought she was going to do sculpture, and found herself enjoying painting. So there seems to be a coming back to that three dimensional process, which was through a completely different sort of lens. She wanted to place herself right back in that academic art based context that she'd been away from and wanted access to have artistic conversations. That's a hard thing to have when it's just you in your studio, sometimes not seeing anybody for days on end, because that's the nature of an art studio, you know, you're not around people all the time. So, she wanted that wider dialogue to really open back up again, and it was a really amazing course. It's not an easy thing to do a full time Master's Course and still teach two days in Glasgow.

At the MA show she didn't have to think about putting a price on a wall as there was no commodification at all, as it was purely about the work and how she wanted that to translate and be viewed.

“if you're able to support your life, have a studio, contribute to the mortgage, buy foods and be part of a family, and you can do that and make the work that you want to make, that's a pretty good definition of success.” (Ritchie, 2020)

Because nobody controls what she is doing, there isn't an agenda behind it, and she doesn't need to think about what a gallery might want, She was really sick of putting work in exhibitions where it's all about selling, and the sense of failure if you sent five pieces of work to an art fair somewhere in Bristol, didn't sell any of them and then being met with a desperately disappointed tone that she was given from the gallery who gave an impression she'd somehow failed. Really, who needs that, and so not only was she making work that she was not entirely fully believing in anymore, it still wasn't selling.

In 1986, Louise was working two and half days in the College of Commerce and the College of Building and Printing at that point. From that time on she was completely self-funded, but certainly during that first five year period, she lived on dole money and the Enterprise Allowance scheme.

She had a Wasps studio in the East End of Glasgow for a long time, in three different art spaces. Then she had her first child with her partner, whilst living in a flat in Shawlands with no proper back court and needed a house. So, the trade-off was to give up the studio, and create a studio in a big double garage at the new house, and it sounds really idyllic, but she struggled to work from home. For about three to four years, she had a garden studio and she kept things ticking along and was still exhibiting, teaching and the whole shebang.

In 2005 her family moved over to Broughty Ferry, so the boys could have a much nicer childhood and primary experience and here partner Andy didn't have to commute to work, but she then travelled back to Glasgow to teach twice a week.

At that point she gave up the job and just went off doing lots of different things over the next few years, being involved in different kinds of projects and using different funding pots and very much having the life of a freelancer. She had funding from Creative Scotland, Artwork Scotland, Ginkgo Projects and worked with the

Paul Hamlyn Foundation, and used all sorts of different funds. She also worked for Angus council with artists, project artists and residencies for about five years as well, so lots of different things.

The art of how to fill in a proposal, funding application skills

She got an opportunity to do a creative facilitation role with Ginkgo Projects, a really interesting organization, run by director Tom Littlewood. He commissions a lot of artists, designers and architects to create big public artworks and architectural projects. They had advertised for a creative facilitator to come and do a job working with three little primary schools in the Glens up into Perthshire, who were all closing down and being put into one big community school. She had a job helping design glass and Perspex panels for the primary school and through a contact worked with another three artists, employed for about five months on that project, and to create various artistic works supported by Creative Scotland and Angus Council. So, from that she then got offered freelance work with Angus Council on a more permanent basis, still there as a freelancer but it just kept continuing, as the boss just kept finding new pots of money. They'd get separate grants through Creative Scotland to support them. She applied with one of the other artists in residence for Creative Scotland funding, Paul Hamlyn Foundation and Artwork Scotland for Art in Participatory Settings funding. They had that for about three and a half years or so and that was an amazing project which was about bringing together five different networks in Scotland; TRIGGER Network, Dundee; SPAN, Scottish Prison Network, Glasgow PATTERN Theatre Group, Edinburgh and Aberdeen Artist Collective. They were brought together periodically all the way through, for training and sharing research knowledge that lasted for a long time.

Louise was working as an artist in residence alongside that at the same time. That ran from 2009 up until about 2013 and at the same time as doing that she became President of the Society of Scottish Artists. She'd been involved with the SSA for many, many years, and was on its council long before she had kids. She went back into it because she wanted to be part of that creative network allowing her to reconnect and speak to artists directly. When she was on the SSA Council, Professor Elaine Shemilt, a researcher and printmaker from DJCAD was President at that point, and they had discovered that they were massively in debt, and like many other arts organisations they were entirely self-funded. Louise managed to get six thousand pounds worth of funding from the Alliance Trust in Dundee and that big chunk of money brought the organisation back into life again, and gave them money to be able to completely redo their social media platform and just drag it from the past into this period, where they could rationalize the membership and so she became a businesswoman for a while. They managed to access several Creative Scotland pots of funding to support very specific projects for it. When she was on council, when it was Elaine's time to stand down. Christopher Wood then stood up as President and asked Louise if she wanted to be Vice-President and then when he came to the end of his time she was asked to do it. It's a fantastic organization and it's a brilliant way to be involved as an artist, and it's entirely artist led. It doesn't have any agendas. It's not beholden to anybody. It has nothing to do with the hierarchy of aristocracy, for example, which is just so tightly connected with class and arts patronage.

"The Royal Scottish Academy has always been traditionally associated with the establishment or hierarchy and even now at official functions Academicians wear ceremonial velvet plus-fours - very much a male domain - the Scottish Society of Artists began as the more rebellious, non-establishment younger sibling in opposition to that and remains that way to a large extent now" (Ritchie, 2021)

The SSA had always been the opposite of that. She did that for about five years, and within that was involved with projects in Slovakia, and Belgium where they had to get public funding, so applied for grants and got money from Creative Scotland again and brought three artists over to host them for a week and got money from Creative Scotland to support that also. She did all of that at one time and then just got really tired of not really knowing where money was coming from and that constant scramble to find the next pot. She felt the need to extend her knowledge a bit more as she wanted to be back in education really, and it just happened that at that point she was invited to be the external for one of the professional bodies, as part of the validation process for UWS with their Creative Arts Practice course in Glasgow. And then about a year later, one staff member had gone on maternity cover so she was brought in to cover for them, then somebody left and she got the job and that's kind of how it grew from there.

Regarding Creative Scotland funding she thinks there's a dance to be done when applying for funding. You just have to make sure that that funding application absolutely ticks those boxes, and if you get a flavour for what they're prepared to fund, that helps. She thinks a lot of people apply for things that are really not applicable for them, and they get pissed off when they are not successful because the application doesn't really make sense. She thinks she was just a bit lucky, being in the right place, at the right time and having the right connections, that's probably part of it. There were plenty of things she went for and didn't get, and getting knocked back is part of your armour as an artist, as there are some years when it hurts more than others.

Being back in education as a part-time lecturer, as her main source of income, she's less 'tuned-in' perhaps what they probably want now, but it's a constant process of applying for different pots. She put in a really big proposal with two colleagues for a GI exhibition last year, and just got a straight no, and there was no feedback to it as they had been promised. It was based on the 'pedagogy of the oppressed' as a provocation, about education and about how so many of us in the arts who teach, don't see teaching as just a means to make money, it's part of who we are as artists, that we learn from students. Students are hardwired in the way that we are not, so we learn all the time and it's even just tips on things and they'll find some good resources. "I just found this dude who makes.....", "did you see this" etc, magical, and so she and two colleagues thought of creating an exhibition that used 'pedagogy of the oppressed' as a really interesting premise for an exhibition. GI just knocked it back, after having put a lot of time into drafting it and following their guidelines and all that time and effort that was spend drafting and there's nothing back on that at all. But then having been on the other end of that at the SSA looking at applications for projects or for whatever, is there time in a voluntary organisation to write hand-written feedback to every single prospective candidate, probably not. We artists have all got spectacular egos, but have very little self-esteem so it is quite a powerful combination.

When she worked at the CCA between 1992-1995, there was a definite lack of transparency around who was getting the funding, more from the old Scottish Arts Councils that was then, and it was the same people year on year, who were getting the awards. The Scottish Arts Council were probably frightened to give it to anybody that they couldn't guarantee some kind of cool outcome from and you see certain names come up again and again. Now, these are people who are absolutely, firmly in the establishment and who are the names in Glasgow in particular. But really, they got there because they had so much help at a formative point in their career. At that point when there's so much validation that comes with it, not just the money, it's the validation. Grayson

Perry talks about the process of validation, that because one person says you're good, the next person will, and the next person will.

When Graham Fagan got the Creative Scotland in Venice gig, he stated that the first thing everyone said was, "how did you get that? how did you work that one?" And that's what happens, people think how do you get in there? Who are the connections that you have to make over the lifespan of a career, whether it's in Visual Arts, or theatre, or music, any of those things? How do you make the network that is prepared to take a punt on you or give you that level of validation? Part of her learning at the Scottish Society of Art was understanding what it was like on the other side and just being able to learn how to write a decent application, or learn how to write an artist statement example or prepare your work for an exhibit, all that kind of stuff, the bread-and-butter things of life that you don't get taught at art college.

Engage UK and the big gallery organizations have a leadership project every year, and Louise got a place on that about three/four years ago, called 'Extend' and because it's UK wide it was funded by Creative Scotland, Arts Council England, the Paul Hamlyn Foundation and AHRC. She worked with artists and theatre makers and museum folks from all over the country. And there were a lot of discussions around the hierarchies and how these different institutions work in terms of leadership but also in terms of creative thinking and how they supported the arts. It's easy to expose the inner workings of all these things, such as artist receiving public funds to create projects whilst still working for institutions already financed with state funds. Everyone knows it happens but they do not expose it.

Louise feels strongly that institutional sexism and exploitation, issues of class, inequalities regarding childcare and career breaks that adversely affecting women are still of concern. She believes things are improving, with a majority of art students being female, and many senior arts roles are now being filled by women. There are growing numbers of mature female students and more women in advanced areas of study such as PhDs. It's mostly women who sit on art organisations boards now and there is a growing number chairing those boards.

Covid pandemic

For those who are highly motivated, disciplined, organized and established in their careers, it's been hard just on a psychological level, maintaining focus, let alone facing the perils of the money and she's got friends around her that don't have the benefit of having established part time contracts to be able to fall back on. They are relying on the Bridging Bursary and subsequent Creative Scotland funding. Louise applied for a Bridging Bursary from Creative Scotland in March, partly because she had just put together an exhibition at the Briggait Gallery in Glasgow with another artist and it had cost a fortune to do it. It was literally open for about six days before it got shut down due to lockdown. So, all the opportunities that was going to open up, how that was going to feed into their careers and possible sales etc. just went completely out the window. Both artists successfully applied for a Bridging Bursary to just cover those materials, so at least they weren't out of pocket, which was fair enough. She had a real ethical, moral dilemma with herself as she was in a job, and should she be taking this money to cover costs that you've put out there potentially for something that's never going to happen.

She knows a few people who've made some money out of 'The Artists Support Pledge', which is such a lovely idea and she knows people that it's been a lifeline for them actually. She has friends that are in very precarious positions right now. They're not the ones who are furloughed, they're the ones that have just been relying on the Bridging Bursaries, because their entire freelance career has just gone up in smoke. It's been tricky this year for them and they had to get a couple of big grants to support them through that because they're not making an income.

Analysis - How do the artists' lives represent key theories of art and power?

Louise has built up her academic profile over her career, building on her habitus and cultural capital during that time. She matches Bourdieu's model of cultural working where she is validated and given symbolic capital through her connection to Cyril Gerber and the Compass gallery, where she was given a show to herself, which was financially very successful. Following that, her work was promoted at big art fairs and other shows which brought her success for a number of years. Being promoted by an eminent gallerist elevated her work and its economic value and through it increased demand and 'signification' of her work.

When Bourdieu discusses the impact of new art movements coming to market, he does not consider that change can also come from those consecrated artists themselves already in the field and the consequences of that can be disruptive to the market and status quo. Gallerists promote artists and their unique personalised cultural artifacts. Bourdieu believes that these gatekeepers utilise a range of cultural rules to keep control over what artworks are acceptable. Becker (1974) recognises that the creation of art is through consensual negotiation. There needs to be stability within the artworld. Louise discovered this as she looked to change the direction of her creative work which was met with disapproval by gallerists who act as symbolic and cultural bankers. It was particularly problematic as her new work wasn't selling. Within the collective action there is an implicit pressure on artists to make work that gallerists continue to sell and to offer the bourgeois market what it wants to buy and collect. There is a disconnect between the buyers looking for a particular piece of merchandise and the artists motivation, ability and desire to create it, as in the client's request for another 'red painting, like the original', produced by Louise, shows. Groys (2008) recognises that the artists ultimately have control over their art production and its creative direction, not the gallerists, as Louise has shown when she stepped away from the market and began producing self-funded pure, avant-garde 'autonomous' artwork solely for herself

Louise took time out to have a family and worked in education and in a freelance capacity till her children were more independent, and then felt a need to reinvent herself. She went back to do a Masters at DJCAD, and at the MA show declined to commodify her work.

Her next artistic direction was to develop a career in community based arts working on collaborative projects which were funded through different grants from a range of public and private funders such as Creative Scotland, Artwork Scotland and the Paul Hamlyn Foundation.

Becker believes that only the most gifted artists' careers are supported by organisations such as guilds and academies, demanding long apprenticeships for the chosen ones. Louise joined the Society of Scottish Artists to network with fellow artists, not to develop cultural capital through it. She utilised her experience of accessing

funding to make the organisation viable again, and was invited to be President of the SSA after several years of supporting and managing it. She has enhanced institutional capital with both qualifications and status through her membership of the SSA.

Louise may challenge Csikszentmihalyi's simplified model of creativity. Perhaps artists do not need their artwork to be judged in a fluid world where they move in and out of their association with the art market. The process of judgement is also fluid, as academic judgements are made through academia, clients assessment of the quality of community based creative work supports the supply of grant funding, but avant-garde working purely for yourself has nothing but personal validation supporting it on a creative journey.

Csikszentmihalyi sees that there is value in being where artists interact around creative activity in universities, art schools and centres of artistic practice such as the SSA. Louise is well placed to identify opportunities within this domain. She also had the learning experience of being part of an esteemed group, sitting on a funding board reviewing others creative applications for funding, many which were not suited to the criteria of the funding applied for.

Louise does not support the hierarchy of aristocracy embedded in the Royal Scottish Academy, which is enmeshed with class and arts patronage in Scotland but is not politically active directly through her work. She regards the Society of Scottish Artists as being agenda free, and nor beholding to anyone. Sholette does not make mention directly of class as part of the power structure he writes about in the US, and perhaps it is more important in a UK setting.

She also has issues with gender discrimination through her career, believing that institutional sexism still exists, where there is still abuse of academic power and exploitation of young students. Class is never kind to women especially those not from a middle class background and inequalities regarding childcare and career breaks during parenthood almost always adversely affects the mothers most. Single mothers who are artists struggle terribly, and Louise has a few friends in that position.

“It's mostly women who sit on art organisations boards and a growing number chairing those boards. So things are changing - apart from motherhood, childcare & all the headaches emotional & practical associated with that. I suspect that may always be the case...” (Ritchie, 2021)

She's now back in teaching part time on an arts course, producing 'bare' art for herself and not really engaging with government funding schemes and understanding of their new requirements. She was aware of the favouritism of awarding bodies towards certain artists, but believes it is done through the bureaucratic funders playing safe and backing an artist who is guaranteed to create a cool, successful outcome.

Louise has moved between the world of success and then returning to produce avant-garde artworks for her own satisfaction and personal development.

Scottish Government support – how cultural policy has impacted the artists' lives

In certain phases of Louise's career, she has relied extensively on government funding support. She gained access to the artist network in Glasgow through the Centre for Contemporary Art whilst working there.

She saw local authority funding support of galleries being diminished due to austerity measures and directly impacting the ability of galleries to support exhibitions of non-commercial artists.

Once she settled down to have a family, she left part time teaching and was involved in a range of projects funded by Creative Scotland, Artwork Scotland and Angus Council in different ways. These included working with Ginkgo Projects and as an artist in residences. She also was chosen to be involved with Engage UK.

She was quite successful in accessing funding from Creative Scotland and felt she understood what they were looking for in her application.

She was certainly aware in her time at the CCA that certain artists were privileged in receiving multiple funding bids and there was a lack of transparency around where resources were being allocated.

With Covid, she knows a number of artists who are relying on the Bridging Bursary and subsequent Creative Scotland funds as their freelance careers have stopped dead. Louise managed to get support through this route to offset exhibition costs impacted by the virus appearing just after she had opened a show at the Briggait Gallery in Glasgow.

Findings: What common themes surround these visual artists' practice in Scotland

In addition to the analysis generated by the literature review of theoretical positions exploring the nature of art together with the Scottish government cultural policy developments, the interviews with practicing artists provided some valuable insights into the nature of artistic living, survival and success in Scotland. With the understanding that this is a small group of interviewees who are not necessarily representative of the broader artistic community, these interviews never the less illustrate the personal challenges that visual artists in Scotland face at a time of great change. Their stories describe the personal resilience they have built up throughout their careers and highlight the resourcing and coping strategies that have supported them in sustaining their arts practice throughout their lives, living and working in Scotland.

Key points of learning from the research conducted for this PhD are:

Cultural funding is set within a political landscape that that is designed to meet the political aims of government

The key funders who support the artists in Scotland are driven by the political landscape through the devolved Scottish parliament, and there are distinct challenges in distribution of resources. The Scottish Government is primarily funded by the UK Westminster government block grant in addition to raising its own revenue from taxation. Resources flow from Scottish Government mainly through Creative Scotland and its Local Authorities. The Scottish government has ring fenced funding which directly supports the cultural and artistic infrastructure of national museums, galleries and theatres but this does not apply to cultural expenditure delivered at local authority level.

Comparative research shows this funding support to the creative industries is significantly lower in the UK than in comparable EU countries, and it is set within the constraints of an austere funding regime imposed by the UK Westminster government (Drew Wylie Projects Ltd. 2019, p. 7).

The Scottish Government gave Local Authorities £575m in funding for 2018-19 and they have a responsibility for delivering a tailored cultural agenda to local communities. The most recently published cultural policy document in March 2020 will be implemented by Local Authority Cultural Convenors, Culture trusts and Creative communities, supported by regional arts officers who are being reintroduced again after austerity cuts had removed that layer of specialist arts officers from local councils. These had been very supportive of several of the artists interviewed in their early careers.

Creative Scotland was funded by the Scottish Government through grants of £66m in 2018-19 and also by the National Lottery who contribute £28m. It distributes that funding and supports the arts in Scotland which includes arts organisations, individual artists, dance & theatre companies and the film industry. Their own branded creative outputs include full length feature films and documentaries in addition to funding creative activities.

Local authorities' cultural budget is vastly bigger than Creative Scotland's, and has supported artists through a range of employment and the funding of special projects. Local authority's utilisation of ALEO's to deliver arts

and cultural funding has a potential to be problematic and has been marked by instances of mismanagement and lack of oversight (Gordon-Nesbitt, 2009, 2011). Often there is also a primary focus on the use of cultural activities in the delivery of economic benefits, such as cultural tourism and collaborative regeneration projects utilising arts and culture to generate the ‘Richard Florida effect’ in depressed neighbourhoods. This appears to be often at the expense of local communities.

The Scottish Government uses Creative Scotland as a supposed ‘arms-length organisation’ to manage funding support for the creative sector. Local Authorities use a similar mechanism in their use of ALEOs who deliver arts and cultural activities on their behalf in their regions. This arms-length approach to both national and regional governments’ subcontracting out of the management of arts and cultural funding to separate funding organisations has potential problems, as could be seen with recent Creative Scotland’s funding process failures which ultimately had to be resolved through Scottish government interventions. Detailed data around the management of cultural funding in local authority ALEOs is difficult to disaggregate as they are not held to the same compliance standards as required by local authorities (Audit Scotland, 2018). The ALEOs have no direct strategic visibility within the local council’s organisational hierarchy and therefore support for the arts is potentially disadvantaged through this position.

The Arts & Culture Support Map (Figure 1) visually highlights the key funders and their relationships with over sixty five art support organisations in Scotland. They offer access to networks, use of facilities, grants, financial assistance, training, and business support. Many are funded through the Scottish Government and Creative Scotland. There are also a number of organisations who act as a voice for artists in Scotland such as the Scottish Artists Union and Applied Art Scotland.

Additional funds no longer come directly from the European Union, since the introduction of Brexit. These substantial packages of support were managed by both the Scottish Government and Creative Europe, administered through Creative Scotland. Issues around this loss of EU funding support for the arts have not been addressed either by UK or Scottish governments, particularly with regard to the European Regional Development Fund’s £23m of support which has been of major importance to those depressed areas of Scotland and in particular the highlands and isles.

Of the interviewees, the majority have been impacted by Scottish cultural policy, through support and funding programmes. However, Bryan and Shona have had no support during their careers from these organisations. Karen has also had no relationship directly with any of the Scottish government’s cultural policy initiatives.

Differing support given by Creative Scotland and Local Authorities to the Artists

Cultural policy supports the ‘quality artists’ identified by Creative Scotland, who has no interest in supporting the majority of artists of a ‘poorer’ quality, which is defined solely by them and there appears to be a lack of transparency around their choices of the funding of these types of candidates. Their agenda is to build the creative brand of Scotland, making it a global creative centre of excellence and in doing so, supporting the economic growth of the creative industries within Scotland. Whereas, artistic support is given more broadly by

local authority funded cultural activities which have been significant in supporting over half of the interviewed artists.

The majority of the visual artist interviewed have had no support from Creative Scotland. Alison, Louise and Kate have received grants through Creative Scotland, but Shona, has failed in all her funding bids, even though she has high social capital and her project proposal was deemed fundable. There was a whole range of experiences of the artists interviewed from those who were able to engage with the funders and access resources on a regular basis, those who has no success in accessing any funding and those who did not engage at all with the system.

There were issues around Creative Scotland's funding bids raised by the interviewees within the selection criteria for funding support which to them needs to be more open, transparent and less arduous to apply. Of the three interviewed participants engaging with the funding application process, Louise was particularly successful. Alison also was well supported but recently spent a month of her time on the labour of submitting a bid to Creative Scotland which successfully progressed through two funding rounds with extensive feedback which was incorporated into her bids but was then rejected at the final stage due to lack of funds to support all the bids submitted. Kate needed to have a grant writer to support her application and the submission was successful. A supposedly 'transparent system' such as this, which has no real transparency around criteria for final decisions is problematic. Does the application process choose bids as a matter of bureaucratic decision making, which is most likely to be influenced by a range of criteria including social and cultural capital of the artists involved, their relationship to the arts market place and the cultural and economic return? Should Creative Scotland submit to open scrutiny of its final decisions with a clear rational and rubric for those decisions? The Scottish government recognises that there needs to be a simpler process to navigate, as it has been recognised as overly difficult.

We can see that the local authority arts officers had a powerful impact on the lives of Alison, Bella, David, Inge and Louise, enabling them to pursue their artistic careers and helped in fulfilling their potential. Alison was supported by her crafts officer, and Bella was able to access a creative community centred around Gracefield Arts Centre in Dumfries. David's career was solely down to being discovered by the local arts officers in Irvine and has certainly been a recipient of a high degree of support with his success being primarily down to him being championed by his local authority. Inge was supported by her local arts officers in Highland council to exhibit in the Glasgow art fair and Louise was supported on a number of projects, including being an artist in residence supported by Angus local authority. The austerity of the Tory Westminster years progressively slashed grant funding and the arts support services were heavily hit, removing this fundamental support function for up and coming artists. The new Scottish Government Cultural Policy seeks to reinstate a version of this with support at Local Authority level through Cultural Convenors and support workers which is a positive step forward.

With regard to the interviewees, artistic success does not require government cultural policy support and there are alternate paths through the gallery system and other funding support received from other avenues such as social media and online sales. Shona was given bursary help from the Norwegian government, and then from the Scottish education department to fund her Barcelona based, Masters qualification. Kate looks for funded

projects from anywhere, including international collaborative partners and other national governments including China. Bryan is developing more fully his online relationship with clients particularly through Covid. He has had early career support through his involvement with the Wasps studios and current use of the Print Studio in Glasgow.

Despite corrections in addressing past weaknesses, the new and revised Government cultural policy still does not fully meet the needs of the Scottish arts sector according to Kate. The government's use of Creative Scotland acting as an agent and buffer in developing the arts and other creative areas and in distributing resources through open funding support has been problematic, resulting in the recent resignation of the chief executive. The new government cultural strategy seeks to correct past issues and aims to put artists at the centre of Creative Scotland's funding review. Creative Scotland's role in deciding who are the artists of quality to be supported is not transparent, and wastes so much valuable time and emotional resource of the artists interviewed in the process. Its limited budget cannot meet the high demand for its resources. The Scottish government review had some radical ideas in it, including considering a citizens basic income for artists, quick proposal decisions before any investment in time was made by applicants and fair payment for actual artists time spent on a project. This goes some way to addressing Kate's issues with how psychologically negative the whole funding process is for artists and these would be positive steps forward in supporting artists in their creative practice. The issues of who is chosen, what funding is allocated and by whom has been contentious and there is a need for fairness and particularly transparency in Creative Scotland's funding decisions.

The stories told by the artists interviewed in their dealings with Creative Scotland are mixed. There is a distrust of the organisation by several of the interviewees, in that it appears no longer interested in the quality of creative ideas but focussed more on meeting targets, quotas and ticking boxes. It is felt that it is high risk with minimum reward and needs a certain writing skillset to access any funding support from Creative Scotland. Kate at one point hired a grant writer to help her get funding as she didn't feel she had the required writing skillset. Spending a month of time to write a proposal which falls at the last hurdle must be demoralising, and to only know, as Alison did, that there ultimately wasn't enough funding to cover all the applicants bids isn't much consolation. This isn't an acceptable system, which wastes so much of artists time for such little returns, as Bryan mentions. There also seems to be a message that the artists projects are good enough to fund, as Shona's submission was rated, but that it wasn't going to be progressed, just seems strange that she clearly either isn't good enough to be funded or she is. So, the artist is being misled or there may be a problematic lack of decisiveness in the process.

The artists experience of accessing government funding through Creative Scotland is varied; Alison and Louise have been able to successfully navigated the application process, Kate, who needed to be assisted in writing her bids was also successful, Shona has applied but even though her bid was fundable she failed to access any money, Bryan sees applying as high risk for low returns and it needs a special skillset that he doesn't have or as in Karen's case, her just not attempting to access or needing funding. Inge, and Bella have both been given support through both their local authorities. Alison and Louise had experience of judging funding applications and this appears to have been very useful to them both in understanding what was required when they applied for funding themselves.

In addition to Local Authorities employing 'artists in residence' to support local communities, such as in Alison's, Inge's and Louise's cases or with Glasgow Council's recent use of artists to work on community projects, the need to teach and educate the community to celebrate and generate their own cultural outputs and creativity has been supported through the proposed Creative Communities programme. There is possibly a need for additional gallery spaces to show and give opportunities to celebrate local artists' work such as in Karen's need, although this could be a regional issue as Glasgow has invested a lot in developing artist spaces in its recent development strategy. Karen is looking to share and connect through her artwork and David's positive experience in developing "Well kent faces" shows how elevating art can impact a community in so many different valuable ways.

Definitions of Artistic Success

Success is defined by interviewees in different terms. It is rarely financial, occasionally through a need for recognition or connection with other artists, but primarily having the ability to be an artist full time or just the ability to have free time to support continuing art practice?

"if you're able to support your life, have a studio, contribute to the mortgage, buy foods and be part of a family, and you can do that and make the work that you want to make, that's a pretty good definition of success." (Ritchie, 2020)

All the artists interviewed had unique stories to tell of their experiences as artists in Scotland.

Kate, Shona, Inge and Bryan have been able to sustain themselves as full time artists all of their lives

Alison taught in education to support her practice for part of her life, then ran her own workshop gallery selling her own artworks, before returning to be a full time artist. She then taught in higher education to support her practice whilst completing a PhD. Bella worked in education and industry to support her practice for the early part of her life and now is a full time artist who includes some summer teaching of art in Tuscany. Karen works in education to support her practice. David had a range of careers prior to exhibiting his work and now teaches in education, in addition to having a renewed focus on his art practice. Louise developed a full time artistic career, successfully serving the bourgeois arts market but she stepped out to raise a family before returning to work on more community based art projects. Like Alison, she has developed an academic career and is studying again to gain a PhD, whilst working on her own avant-garde creative artwork, being now more independent and disconnected from the art market. Inge runs her own gallery in addition having a full time artistic career. Her early years included illustrating for the BBC and teaching at GSA and local schools.

Support by the Gallerist network

All of the artists, with the exception of Karen, have all worked with galleries to sell their work. Online sales have increased during Covid, having an impact on the artists long term relationship with those off-line galleries. Shona values and respects her life long relationship to her gallerists and choses to minimise her online activities.

Bella, Shona, Louise and Inge have successfully utilised art fairs to sell and promote their work. One new business model mentioned by Bella being tried out by some galleries is the use of art fairs as promotional points of contact with their existing and future clients and then moving selling activities through online sites without the costs of offline bricks and mortar galleries.

Academic theories are useful in understanding the challenges in artists' careers in Scotland and highlight issues around recognition, legitimacy and innovation, but also do not fully encompass the reality of the artists experience in Scotland.

Bourdieu's theories help explain why many full time artists struggle to achieve financial success.

The power dynamics in Scotland may hold the key as there is clearly an elite who make decisions in Creative Scotland and in art institutions who decide which artists will be elevated and who do not meet their standards. Both the Scottish Government and Creative Scotland made statements that make clear they are only interested in supporting 'excellent' and more recently have added 'experimental' creative work to their criteria, and have little interest in working with or developing those defined as poorer quality artists at that level. This is a weakness of the system in identifying artists of quality, as Kate Downie stated, 'there are artists out there who if financially supported, instead of being forced to mirror the art market, could produce amazing work' (2020).

Bourdieu recognises that those with economic capital do not have to be subordinate to the market place and have social capital that gives them a competitive advantage in recognising new trends and they have the ability to push boundaries with limited risk. They are also able to stay working in the avant-garde for longer as they have financial support which increases their ability to eventually extract social capital from this process. The majority of Scottish artists chose to stay in the avant-garde and fund their practice through secondary work, which is often teaching. He also believes the art establishments in Scotland, such as the Royal Scottish Academy and the Royal Scottish Society of Painters in Watercolour, are likely to have influence on who is deemed an artist of renown and what is defined as 'high art', but a separate research project would be required to understand fully the organisations' impact on the process.

Kate is a member of the Royal Scottish Academy and is chair of the Friends of the RSA of which Prince Philip was the patron. She has artwork in Her Majesty's collection. The Royal Society of Scottish Painters in Watercolours patron is now King Charles. Louise is anti-establishment and believes the Scottish Society of Artists is a counter to that tradition and more politically independent. Both Kate and Louise have been presidents of the SSA, which enhances their habitus and cultural capital. Alison is a Fellow of the Royal College of Art which also raises her cultural capital. Bella has been a professional member of Visual Arts Scotland for twenty years. Karen is also a member of VAS.

The Royal Society of Scottish Painters in Watercolours needs the proposal from two members for a nomination to proceed. Visual Arts Scotland's professional membership needs two nominations to apply. The Society of Scottish Artists needs work accepted for their annual exhibition two years running to apply. So, all have a vetting process and their own relative status as an arts organisation in Scotland.

Some of the artwork produced by the artists interviewed has become elevated to becoming symbolic goods that can have 'signification' and symbolic value as opposed to their artwork being treated as 'merchandise', which only has market value. Kate has achieved some level of symbolic output but thinks for the effort she has put in, feels it should be greater. Louise also achieved 'signification' in her early artistic career. Shona's career ticks so many quality boxes giving her signification and value, but she is not a member of any art society or institution which may put her at a disadvantage. Alison who is a member of the Royal Academy of Arts, only uses it to

enhance her CV and has no other engagement with that institution. She has been creating her artwork for the last ten years embedded in academia, solely for its own sake with no interest in the art market and all for personal growth, so currently has a limited external profile and limited signification. She recently applied for funding and has the cultural and institutional capital to be a contender for grant funding resources.

Bourdieu and the other theorists' models are too simplistic to accommodate the variety of creative strategies being employed by the Scottish artists interviewed, particularly by the artists who have flexible careers, both in full time working and in their relationship to the marketplace, appearing to extract capital from it when they needed it and disregarding it when they chose not to.

Importantly, Bourdieu splits the artists into those who are elevated, those serving the art market or being in the avant-garde. These positions are fluid and incomplete when defining the interviewees, as the artists have greater ownership of this space and are not often subordinate to the marketplace (Groys, 2008, p. 43). The reverse of Bourdieu's theories appears to be playing out here. The artists utilise the art market for their own purposes. They produce avant-garde artwork that they want to personally develop, and the majority of interviewees see the market as secondary to their choices of artistic direction. Perhaps these artists are not in the elite super successful group precisely because they chose to do what they want and are not part of the duality the theorists espouse between those who are symbolic producers or those pandering to the market's demands. Several interviewees utilise careers particularly in education to fund their practice until for some, their work potentially grows enough social and cultural capital to allow them to live solely off it and become full time artists. Sholette misses this point as his focus is on the politics of those who are elevated and those who aren't recognised. He sees a conflict and power struggle between the two, and doesn't recognise the fluidity that moves artists between both positions, and with the exception of Bella's anti-war images and Louise anti-RSA establishment views, have very little political agendas.

Inge and Bryan, who are the most entrepreneurial and market focussed artists, capitalise on market successes and optimise their offerings accordingly. However, for the majority interviewed, the markets appear to serve the artists not the other way around.

Alison and Inge both have created their own galleries as part of their income generation strategies which makes them both creators and intermediaries in the sales process.

David and Bryan, the two artists who have issues with being defined as 'artists', see themselves as painters, as both produce work that is subordinate to the art market place and they recognise their positions in it.

Kate also discussed the elevation of the new Glasgow Boys, who graduated from the Glasgow School of Art in 1982 at the same time as her. She recognised that those artists were doing similar creative work to others across Scotland at that time, but that they were chosen to have 'signification'. It would be interesting to understand how that narrative was developed and attached to them and hear what those specific artists' personal experiences were at that time, and the process of how they were chosen and elevated to become symbolic 'high art' producers. Louise also discussed the signification of Graham Fagan by Creative Scotland through their

choice of him for the Venice Biennale and the mystery of how that happened, to even those who were close to him.

Documentary based elements of the interviews

As part of the outputs of this thesis exploring key aspects of mature artists ability to sustain their creative practice, a series of documentary clips were produced highlighting findings in the research process. The themes of the documentaries aligned with three key areas of interest; Bourdieu's theories around successful navigation of funding resources in relationship to power hierarchies, Csikszentmihalyi's theories around the success of creative artists increasing through connections to mentors who open doors to successful recognition by the creative field and Bourdieu's theories around the use of symbolic violence being utilised against disempowered groups.

Successful navigation of funding resources

The first set of documentaries explore the experiences of three artists who have successfully navigated funding resources and accessed Government cultural funding and support networks and of one artist who has chosen a completely opposite strategy to resource his practice.

Each of the first three artists interviewed has had positive experiences of accessing funding for their artistic practice. Louise, Kate and Alison were the three artists of the group who positively engaged and supported Scottish artistic and cultural institutions during their careers and all were beneficiaries of a range of institutional grant funding in support of their art practice. By participating in the managing and processing of grant funding applications, both Alison and Louise gained an understanding of what was required in a grant application to meet the criteria for a successful bid. Meeting the specific requirements laid down in the funding process was critical to an application, as many artists failed to do this when making a submission for support. Louise's expertise in accessing grant funding from Creative Scotland, Artwork Scotland, Ginkgo Projects and working with the Paul Hamlyn Foundation and others gave her valuable expertise in the creative community and it contributed to her being offered President of the Society of Scottish Artists as she had the skills to be able to support them in becoming more financially stable.

The fourth documentary shows an alternative pathway to supporting an artistic practice. In contrast to the three who actively engaged and supported Scottish artistic and cultural institutions, Bryan chooses to focus solely on the marketplace, and generates income by offering a range of artworks through a number of different sales channels. He has never been a member of any arts guilds or institutions nor has he applied for any funding grants throughout his career as he perceives them as high risk and low return. He solely derives income through the sales of artwork via galleries, sales to framers and more recently has progressively grown his online presence selling directly to his customers.

The following four documentaries look at artists who have successfully navigated funding resources.

Louise Ritchie - Funding & Support Networks 12:48 <https://youtu.be/avFIsWUIKTI>

Louise talks about her wide ranging arts funding support from a variety of government and private sources in Scotland. She also speaks about her support of the Society of Scottish Artists where she became its president.

Alison Bell - Funding & Support Networks 25:09 <https://youtu.be/-gIsXC4Wqxs>

Alison discusses how her involvement with a local authority crafts officer was critical in developing her profile which allowed her to be invited onto several prestigious government arts bodies This helped her in accessing funding support throughout her career. Alison is a fellow of The Royal Society of Arts but is not an active member.

Kate Downie - Funding & Support Networks 13:03 <https://youtu.be/Dn1hdTtUoJM>

Kate has accessed funding support from a variety of sources in Scotland and abroad. She has employed a grant writer to support one of her Creative Scotland bids. She was President of the Society of Scottish Artist from 2004 to 2006 and is a member of the Royal Scottish Academy in 2008

Bryan Evans - Funding & Support Networks 14:34 <https://youtu.be/TFONW4ckOiQ>

Brian has sold his artworks directly to the marketplace through a range of intermediaries. He has avoided engaging with any artistic and cultural institutions and has taken a more business-like, entrepreneurial approach to making a living as an artist.

One of the Csikszentmihalyi's most relevant theories is that the success of creative artists is often determined by chance events, where a connection to a mentor opens doors to successful recognition of the artist by the creative field.

Four short documentaries were created exploring Csikszentmihalyi's theories connecting cultural mentors to increased artistic success.

David Reid – Mentors Open Doors 15:47 <https://youtu.be/1oru3yjf-0>

David's raw artistic skills were 'discovered' by the North Ayrshire local arts officers whilst they were engaging with the general public through art exhibitions held in Irvine. This happened during Davids regular visits to a community based gallery in Irvine, and through him building rapport with the curators he was offered an exhibition space for his work. They promoted and brought him into the arts market place through offers of two gallery exhibitions and actively supported him in finding portrait commissions that elevated his status in the art market. They also found him work opportunities as a community artist and teacher to help fund his art practice.

Alison Bell – Mentor Opens Doors 3:42. <https://youtu.be/IvYdvgMZ3dU>

Alison was massively helped by her introduction to North Ayrshire's local authority Crafts Development Officer who promoted her work in London and helped her grow her international profile through support of her attendance at conferences in the USA and Netherlands. This was valuable capital in supporting her application to be on the board of Craft Scotland and in becoming a special advisor for the Scottish Arts Council in support of their selection panels and funding decisions.

Shona Barr – Mentor Opens Doors, 5:47 <https://youtu.be/GwDyxZMDXqs>

This interview explores Shona's ongoing relationship and promotion throughout her career by her mentor, Jean Houldsworth, the gallerist at Flying Colours gallery, in Edinburgh & in London. After her showing successfully in Edinburgh, the gallerist arranged for her to exhibit in London at Gallery Ten which also was successful. This was the start of a career long relationship in support for her practice.

Inge Smith – Mentors Open Doors 8:15 <https://youtu.be/r14YcmO7IK8>

This interview again highlights the value of mentors in opening up opportunities for artists. Inge was given support by Taine's local authority arts officers who were very supportive of her practice and offered her exhibition space at the art fair in Glasgow with them. She also was offered a number of teaching opportunities around her art practice in the local community. Through this support, Inge built the confidence to exhibit collectively with other artists including family members at art fairs across Scotland and the UK, leading to opportunities for her to exhibit her work further field and internationally in China.

One of Bella's art class student helped opened doors for her with the submission of an article promoting her work which was published in the Glasgow Herald and also the gifting of one of her works to the Woman's Library in Glasgow. The student's partner also created an opportunity for her to teach in Tuscany through personal connections, which helped financially supported her practice. Louise was elevated through her one woman show by Cyril Gerber and his Compass gallery and follow on art fairs. So, it can be clearly seen that mentors can really open doors for artists, particularly in their early years. These could be through government arts officers, as seen with Alison, Inge and David or through gallerists offering a first major show as in the case of Louise or Shona.

Bourdieu's concept of Symbolic violence

The majority of women interviewed feel that there are structural impediments to them being successful as artists. Women are impacted by institutional sexism, misogyny and are at risk of exploitation particularly in their early years. They have also to deal with issues of class, inequalities regarding childcare and a need for carer breaks and caring roles which adversely affect their career development.

Scotland has a majority of female artists relative to the rest of the UK and females lead the majority of creative sector positions, but are paid less than the men.

Bourdieu's concept of Symbolic violence is highlighted by four of the Scottish women artists interviewed. Bella, Kate, Louise and Karen felt as females they were devalued within the art industry. They have experienced differing types of sexism and misogyny during their careers.

“But in actuality, as we know, in the arts as in a hundred other areas, things remain stultifying, oppressive, and dis-couraging to all those - women included - who did not have the good fortune to be born white, preferably middle class and, above all, male. (Nochlin, 1971, p. 6)

Csikszentmihalyi also believes that strongly socialised gender stereotypes inhibit creativity as it constrains personality development. Bella agrees with that.

“If a child is too strongly socialized to act in terms of a strict gender stereotype, his or her creativity is likely to be inhibited. In other words, the traits that distinguish a complex personality are likely to add a higher statistical probability of creative expression.” (Csikszentmihalyi, 2007, p. 336)

The Guardian published an article on a recent report revealing 'disgraceful' gender inequality in the arts' (Tuckett, 2021, p. 21) highlighting that women in the arts are under-represented and face serious challenges that need to be addressed. Issues around attitudes towards women and transparency of decisions around allocation of resources need to be improved. Gatekeepers need to view the system through a gendered lens with regard to policy direction and much needed arts organisational change. So, this shows that the interviewees experiences are set within a broader framework of gender discrimination, which is a UK wide issue that needs to be addressed.

The following three documentaries explore Bourdieu's theories of 'symbolic violence

The following three interviewees expand on Bourdieu's theories around 'symbolic violence' and its relationship to gender-based discrimination.

Kate Downie – Symbolic Violence 3:09. <https://youtu.be/IB7oTmF4YEEY> highlights systemic sexist policies towards working mothers through UK taxation policies around child care and in workplace sexism and misogyny, where females are disadvantaged around promotion and recruitment practices. She also felt there were sexist attitudes shown by gallerists around what art movements and artists should be sanctified, such as the elevation of the New Glasgow Boys in the early 1980's.

Karen Monaghan – Symbolic Violence 0:58. <https://youtu.be/oOdTTArTw7Y> discusses how in the past educational institutions, which were very patriarchal communities, created discriminatory narratives around the legitimacy of who would be eligible to be a member of the Scottish art world and laid down rules which disadvantaged women and other minority groups from participating. Karen encountered sexist views at art school and bought into the narrative of the inadequacies of 'sunday painters' who were deemed by the gatekeepers as to not be legitimate artists and their having no right to define themselves as such, nor being allowed to be part of the system of art production if they were not available to develop a full time artistic career with no allowance for caring roles or child rearing.

Bella Green – Symbolic Violence 3:10. <https://youtu.be/EHmFxsDpneU> has life experiences of subtle sexism in the art world particularly early in her career. The gender bias was certainly cultural in expectations of women not being too assertive and clear cases of sexist attitudes particularly towards young women artists were observed. Also, there was the Scottish cultural thing about people not promoting themselves too much and where bragging about your successes was discouraged. It has been difficult for Bella to identify whether the barriers to success were based on issues of gender discrimination since they were often very subtle, but after a lifetime developing an artistic career she believes it has been so.

Louise has also witnessed a range of sexist behaviors throughout her career which are still ongoing today and also identified the caring and parenting issues that predominately impacted female artists careers.

The stories recounted by four of the female artists interviewed highlight gender issues across a range of issues affecting employment opportunities, taxation issues around child rearing, discriminatory narratives that were designed to be non-inclusive and sexist behaviour particularly involving younger female artists. Bella highlighted that there was also a sense that things were just not right in the art world but that it was very difficult to pinpoint it and call it out, but as an older female artist she was more able to deal with it.

Collective production of the artworks

Becker recognises that the consumers, audiences and buyers of the artistic work are part of the creation of that artwork (1974, p. 767). The visual artist is the central player within the radiating network of supporting personnel who support and also create added value to the creative artistic process. Kate's family have roles in supporting her practice and she recognises the value of the additional supporting cast, particularly from the multiple canvas and stretcher suppliers. David's portraiture projects of local people are so contextually relevant to the local community and are so much more than the individual parts. Before he was supported by the arts officers he had little understanding of any of the processes involved in painting, such as where to get the paints, the canvas and other materials. Becker does not subscribe any unique status to any of the artist he defines as cultural workers. Bryan, Kate Shona and Louise's work could be ascribed as having particular unique symbolic status. Inge works collaboratively with other artists in sharing exhibition spaces at art fairs which are very expensive for individuals to access, competing directly with gallerists and also promoting their work to the broader art market place.

Sholette identifies the vast numbers of artists who do not achieve any status of high art production and the tensions that exist in the system of production, but none of the artists interviewed are really political or subversive, so they are not trying to undermine the systems of power in the art world.

The artists value their networks both emotional and financial

Networks are paramount to the interviewees artistic success in Scotland. Bella moved to Dumfries and Galloway specifically to successfully connect with the large artistic community there, helped by the arts officer based at Gracefields in Dumfries. Kate has built an internationally extensive network through her art practice, and her involvement in several arts organisations. Alison's connections with local authorities, arts organisations and academia sustained her full time arts career. Louise was involved in the Scottish Society of Arts, helping her to network and connect with other artists. Karen struggles in building a network of artists and gallerists since she moved over to the east coast of Scotland and has had difficulty in making connections there.

The majority of artists have built up relationships with gallerists who promote their work. Bryan has developed his online relationships directly with clients in addition to support from gallerists and has become more self-sufficient as his online art sales have grown during Covid. He has noticed that things have changed over the last eight months as virtually all his income has been through online sales, and he thinks it will totally change how his paintings will sell. He sold a painting online recently and swapped messages with the buyer who said, it's so great that we've cut out the galleries, and because that reduces his sales costs, ordinary people can now afford to buy his work and he's been selling quite a lot, whereas Bella and Shona understand the value on an online presence, but just don't have time, expertise or the inclination to develop their websites and social media any further.

The key power dynamics between artists, gatekeepers and the art marketplace

There is recognition by Bryan, Louise, Shona, and Kate that gallerists support artists in developing their careers, and add value and capital to their work, but none of the theorists acknowledges the price that is paid by the artists for this support. The artwork increases in value through the dealer acting as the symbolic banker, but the artists only get a percentage, often less than half of the value of their work at that point. This cost disproportionately affects those artists who are struggling to make a living. Louise identifies the tensions that can arise between the gallerists and artists over what the market is looking for versus the direction that the artist wants to take. This is particularly acute when sales are affected by that transition. This pressure can stunt the creative growth of the artist in a similar way to Kate's understanding of the damage that funding applications have on their creative processes.

The statistic around the sixty percent of artists who cannot financially sustain a full time art practice fails to articulate that artist career are not solely focussing full time on serving the art market place. Karen, David and Louise are currently working in education to sustain their art practice from income generated.

Alison now has a private income from her pension and highlights the precariousness of being a 'retired' practicing artist who has lived her life on a very low income which does not allow for an enhanced pension provision. Most artists will continue to practice independently or on the fringe of the marketplace and will continue to combine both creative working and other revenue generating activities to support their practice.

The heteronomous and autonomous principles can be seen clearly in the work of the artists. Six of the artists Bella, Alison, Kate, Shona, Karen and Louise all produce work for themselves with little regard for the marketplace. They are well aware of the market and its requirements but do not pander to its needs. Three artists, Bryan, David and Inge focus the types of artwork they produce on market interest and demand. Bryan and Inge are particularly entrepreneurial, utilising their artwork to maximise income from the marketplace though original work in galleries and additional sales of reproductions. Alison ran her own studio gallery for a period and sold artwork to a summer tourist market and Inge currently runs her own gallery in Taine.

Kate, Shona, Inge and Bryan have been full time artists all their lives. Alison taught in education to support her practice for part of her life, ran her own studio gallery and was a full time artist. Bella worked in education and industry to support her practice for the early part of her career and is now working full-time. Karen works in

education to support her practice. David had mixed careers prior to becoming a painter, then education became his primary occupation. Louise had a full time career as an artist until she had her family, then returned to work in more community based art practice before balancing her career with part time lecturing.

The majority of artists; Bella, Alison, Karen, David and Inge have all had careers as creative art teachers in addition to being art practitioners. This work supplemented their income and gave them financial stability which allowed them to develop their own personal art practice.

The impact of Brexit and the COVID-19 pandemic

While some artists found online approaches to mitigating the impact of the Covid pandemic on their artistic practice, and in Bryan's case actually benefitted from it, many failed to adapt nor get appropriate governmental support, as had been made available to protect other industries. The Covid pandemic coupled with Brexit has brought shifts to funding of the arts sector, to networking and specifically to a sustainable practice for artists in Scotland due primarily to the loss of EU Regional Development funding, although none of the artists interviewed with the exception of Inge had been noticeably affected by those changes.

Traditional artistic sales networks collapsed during Covid as Galleries shut down, with many not having the capacity to transfer their business online. Several of the theorists' models need updating, as the use of social media and online networks has not been incorporated. Bourdieu's theories of symbolic capital still hold for the elite artists, but his model does not include the online social media opportunities for artists to bypass galleries and build their own client base, as Bryan has been doing, particularly if the artists have been supported by the galleries to develop their personal brand and social and cultural capital prior to their online development. Sholette recognises the opportunities for artists to utilise online communications systems to access the art market and clients directly, bypassing the gatekeepers who manage definitions of quality and who have membership of the club.

An interesting addition to Becker's concept of artists being at the centre of a process of artistic development, could focus on how networks shift, such as with the impact of the global pandemic. As one pathway or route of the art market network is damaged then other pathways to it are found and developed, such as through the neural networks and structures of the internet.

The Scottish government's new cultural policy March 2020

The Scottish government's new cultural policy been updated to help the art sector and deal with a range of issues affecting the lives of artists. Unfortunately, it was launched in March 2020, just as Covid's impact hit and it did not get the visibility it deserved. Their plans to investigate the feasibility of a 'Citizen's Basic Income' for artists was a radical one. They also wished to bring artists to the centre of Creative Scotland's open funding policies again after the problems encountered in the previous funding round. They are going to reintroduce cultural convenors and arts officers at local authority level which is a really positive step.

Creative Scotland was offering a £2m Bridging Bursaries fund to help freelance artists in March 2020. A second round of funding was opened up in April 2020 with a further £2m allocated. Eighty percent of 2831 applicants were given support. Most of the interview group did not accessed the funding. Costs of Louise's curtailed exhibition was helped with funding support and Shona applied but she wasn't successful. Inge did get 'furlough' money from central government through her business as a gallerist. Louise has freelance artist friends who were solely dependent on the Bridging Bursaries for income as all other routes were closed off.

The consequences of Brexit and the Covid pandemic will potentially make Scottish artists' lives much harder and much more difficult for them to sustain any substantive artistic career due to loss of income. With a package of arts funding in Scotland coming directly from the EU being at risk and there being no plans for it to being replaced by neither the Scottish nor UK, Westminster governments overall arts funding will be reduced (Creative Scotland, 2019, p. 4). This is particularly a problem as EU support to disadvantaged communities has been gained through the EU Structural Fund, which the arts and creative industries in the north west of Scotland have been particularly successful in accessing.

Yet, artists are doing a lot to help themselves. Bryan's online sales increased through Covid, reducing further any dependency he had on galleries as intermediaries and he utilised the 'Artist Support Pledge' website which was very successful. Karen chose not to apply for the 'pledge' as she had income through another job. There is another artist pledge online group, called 'Patreon – Artist Pledge' that only Karen was aware of. Inge knew of the Artist Pledge but wasn't really interested in it or its aims.

Covid gave David time for reflection about the focus and future direction of his art practice and a reconnection to painting. Alison also had time for introspection of her art practice. Kate found Covid brought a time of compassion into her life, as she supported her elderly mother and worked jointly with her on an art project together. Bella had no income during Covid and had been hoping to set up a Pop-Up Shop to sell her jewellery for Christmas. Louise accessed the Bridging Bursary to cover expenses for her ill-timed gallery exhibition that had only been open days before Covid shut everything down.

The visual art world v's the cultural industries

The UK government has absorbed the artworld into its broader overarching definition of the creative and cultural industries, but is this appropriate? The visual art world looks like it fits within that grouping and at first glance it appears to have similar issues regarding employment precarity and challenging working conditions with sporadic income and the need for flexibility and multiple jobs to survive. All groups need to constantly promote themselves to sustain their careers and often work individually and have opportunities to collaborate in creative collectives.

However, a career as an artist has qualities that are quite different to those employed in the creative industries in many regards. The creations of the art world still hold the illusion of mystery and awe with an elite art market sitting behind it. Artworks need to be distinctive, novel and authentic and lose their appeal and value if turned

into mass produced commodities. It is also imperative that artists never pander to the art market or they will lose their unique position in society

Creative industries freelancers often design low brow, mass produced, commercial projects within the world of creative design. There is little mystery or spirituality surrounding their work to commodify and supply mass produced popular culture to a global audience, working to a budget, meeting the client's briefs and the market's needs.

However, it could be argued that those working in the creative industries have their own equivalent unique high art worlds and institutions set within their own disciplines, who bestow their own special marks of approval, making judgements on their work and are responsible for defining their status in each discipline as can be seen in high fashion, art house films, music, design and even architecture.

Conclusions

Artists pathways to funding and support

The title of this thesis is 'The Scottish Art Scene: Shrinking Resources, Growing Networks', as it examines the particular challenges that are faced by mature Scottish visual artists in developing a sustainable art practice following the austerity years of a Tory Westminster government, Brexit and a global pandemic. It explores the difficulties that artists have in accessing funding and support from the Scottish government, Creative Scotland, local authorities and others in helping sustain their creative practice and looks at alternate support and resourcing structures that are being utilised.

The research revealed a variety of experiences, both positive and negative in the interviews carried out with these mature visual artists and their evolving strategies developed to cope with the broader issues of income generation and social networking responding to adversity due to the current financial climate and the recent Covid pandemic. It seems that these visual artists have been inoculated and have built up a resilience to the stresses of the pandemic that is borne out of their historically difficult working conditions prior to the pandemic, where they often created work in isolation, set with precarious lifestyles and little financial stability that has prepared and sustained them through the Covid lockdown. In a way it could be seen that their careers have always depended on them adjusting to a hazardous environment created by the politics of the UK government's austerity years that has progressively cut and privatized previously subsidized cultural provision where now only an instrumentalised, economic case for support would be considered. These visual artists' self-reliance is part of an 'individuated' way of working, where individuals take on all the risks of being self-employed in an unstructured and fluid state which has no government social support and no social benefits if there is an inability to find avenues of income, or through ill health (Bauman, 1999, 2000) so their lives are always enmeshed in risk.

These mature artists utilise diverse portfolios to generate income and have developed creative reputations pre-pandemic that they have been able to build upon and utilise their cultural capital to sustain online and some limited gallery sales. New networks of contacts need to be developed facing outwards towards Europe and more internationally again to seek new funding opportunities as income generation within Scotland is likely to become progressively more difficult as funding support is cut through major losses post Brexit of EU funding (Creative Scotland, 2019, p. 4).

Use of Academic Theoretical Models

The research also explored academic theoretical models of artistic practice in the art world and its criteria for success and how these have informed and structured this thesis. It also identifies where potential opportunities to develop and grow additional networks of support could be found, including those in online social media where artists interact directly with clients and other artists, diminishing reliance on governmental funding and traditional structures such as through the traditional gallerist network to support them.

The insights of the four theorists chosen have helped illuminate the broad structures and relationships embedded in the workings of the art market. The Scottish artists careers are fluid and don't align with the theorists' models, particularly around definitions of careers and static life-long models of interaction with the art market. The theorists have not considered forms of gender bias or the class and privilege of artists having any impact on artistic success in their thinking, but most of the female artists interviewed believe they do. The majority of the interviewed artists create avant-garde artwork for themselves, but chose to engage with those in power or the art markets only whenever they have need of financial resources. The art markets are actually there to serve the majority of the interviewed artists in this context, not the other way around as suggested by the key theorists.

Those artists who engage with key art institutions such as the Royal Scottish Academy, Royal Society of Scottish Painters in Watercolour, Society of Scottish Artists and Visual Arts Scotland and are active members in art communities are more likely to be successful in accessing funding than those who do not. Having recognition for their commitment to the arts landscape of Scotland increases the likelihood of them building enough cultural capital to be taken seriously and be rewarded for it too. Having a profile and being known in the art world will always increase opportunities, but as Alison Bell noted, "as doors open you must also be able to deliver what funders are looking for too".

Networks of resource

The artists interviewed have all developed strategies to navigate the networks of resources available which allow them to both emotionally and financially support their artistic practice and sustain a viable career within the visual arts. In identifying the key milestones in their careers, these Scottish artists identified the significance of mentors and sponsors in supporting their artistic development and the fluid and inconsistent self-serving relationships they have with the formal art market. This has been of particular note at local authority level where its criteria for support and involvement with local artists is radically different to that of Creative Scotland which is primarily interested in 'excellent' artistic output are clearly seen in the case studies presented.

The sector is inadequately funded relative to comparable countries and given the current lack of funding supporting artists in Scotland, access to resources will certainly deteriorate in the post-Brexit era with loss of EU funded support (Creative Scotland, 2019).

Female artists often face symbolic violence and gender discrimination challenges whilst trying to sustain a full-time career, which is magnified for those with caring and parenting responsibilities. Louise thinks that gender issues could be reduced as female participation in the arts are increasing in Scotland and at managerial levels, but are still unfortunately there (Visual Arts in Scotland, 2015, p. 31).

Creative Scotland's open funding process has issues particularly around transparency in its decisions to support artists and issues of it defining what it regards as work of 'excellence'. It has demanded quite onerous time expenditure in its funding process which is costly and of high risk to visual artists and there is a perception that the bureaucrats play safe when committing funding to projects and have little interest in the value of the creative ideas at the centre of application bids. There are also serious issues around their apparently having no real understanding of the nature of artistic creativity and the damage caused to it and the artists by their current

funding processes. Policy makers need to understand more fully how the creative process that artists go through is impacted by their current funding requirements. There is also a need for debate around the inherent value of cultural activities that go beyond a solely instrumentalised approach to awards. A bidding war between competing artists and organisations trying to access funding is so counter to what artistic endeavour should be about and is also corrupting of the artists and artistic outputs which serve it.

Government policy issues

There are positive things to note in the current art sector environment. Government policy doesn't only focus on the marketability of excellent artists in a global setting, it gives substantial resources to local authorities, helping meet the unique cultural needs of local communities and supports artistic projects at lower levels. The Scottish government is looking to develop a new strategy, where they put culture at the centre of their policy decisions. Their arm-length approach to artistic support through Creative Scotland and the Local Authorities use of ALEO's weakens organisational control over these areas and a more integrated approach should be considered. Also, Creative Scotland and Local Authorities should also have a closer working relationship around common goals of artistic and cultural support. Perhaps local authorities could take on the role of growing and nurturing artistic talent through a career development focus and Creative Scotland takes those they deem best suited and promote their excellence internationally. Proposals by the Scottish government to introduce a National Cultural Observatory which would monitor cultural activity and collect data in support of their policy decisions would help address issues of lack of useful relevant unpacked data around the arts.

However, the research also highlighted the challenges that the Scottish government has in delivering its cultural policies as there are clear disconnections between it and with the independence of local authorities utilising funding for cultural activities in any way that meets their own specific needs. Creative Scotland does not fund all regions of Scotland and some Local authorities do not seek any funding support from them. Currently there is surprisingly no available data source to understand where local authority funding resources for culture are actually being spent (Scottish Government, 2019).

One reason why Local Authorities resources are so important to the artist economy is that their culture budget is five times that of Creative Scotland, although there is limited data on its specific support for artists which is not clear, particularly if under ALEO's reporting mechanisms. Local authorities appear to drive their own cultural agenda which is independent of the Scottish governments but there appears to be no clear signposting for artists to access support for their own projects and in accessing funding directly from them.

There would be benefits to an integrated cultural policy solution that combines the resources of Creative Scotland with Local Authorities to forge an integrated package of support and commitment to the creative arts sector as a whole. It should be one that recognises the full scope and potential of artistic practice here in Scotland, growing the skills and confidence of artists to make more of them creators of excellence, and not just for the selected few. It also needs to be more flexible to accommodate the needs of artists who are more fluid in their careers, such as those who have caring responsibilities or those who step out to recharge their batteries or even take time out to lead a normal life with a steady income and holidays abroad for a period of time. Clear policies within Creative Scotland which actively seek to remove any discrimination around gender, ethnicity or

class within the funding process need to be articulated and actions taken to enhance them. Those who produce radical avant-garde artwork shouldn't be penalised for it, but should have it celebrated.

The new government cultural policy has now been set at the heart of its broader policy making. Creative Scotland has been instructed to refocus on artists and new ways of funding and supporting them have been proposed. A 'Citizen's Basic Income' is being investigated, which would be a positive step to really help artists. Creative Scotland and Local authorities are looking at having tentative discussions around them building closer ties in working together which should be encouraged.

The Covid pandemic

The Covid pandemic has also been a time for reflection, compassion and for developing self-reliance and challenging the relationships between artists and galleries. It also has highlighted the flexibility of the capitalist system in re-routing and optimizing suppliers' channels to market, as some galleries having shut down due to their lacking an online infrastructure and artists have needed to build direct routes to their customers. This is only likely to work effectively where artists have already built up symbolic and cultural capital through the system already and it will be more problematic with new entrants coming to the art marketplace who have built up little capital through these traditional routes. With no cultural bankers in place, they will struggle to build up any symbolic capital around their work. Further research into the impact on the creative community is needed around this specific subject area.

Even though the majority of artists interviewed have had little government support during the Covid pandemic, a large number of the arts community who applied for Creative Scotland's Bridging Bursaries did receive small grants from Creative Scotland. Creative Scotland's Bridging Bursaries and newly positioned 'Open Fund for Individuals' provided some very limited relief for the artists struggling to financially survive during Covid. Support, for the many freelancers in the creative arts sector has been overlooked by the current UK Government's overarching support packages as independent freelancers, who make up a large proportion of the creative sector, were not covered by its 'furlough' scheme (Banks & O'Connor, 2021).

The Scottish government's supporting interventions were limited within the context of the scale of impact of the pandemic and had to follow in part the UK government's strategy for dealing with differing industry support measures. The visual artists interviewed primarily had to fend for themselves with limited access to any support. Several artists were able to access broader UK 'furlough' support whilst others who were self-employed received no state support at all. Most of the artists interviewed utilised online technologies to help support themselves, either through online sales and social media engagement or through collective artists' mutual support networks such as the online Artist Pledge commitment. Those artists who were unwilling or unable to transfer their engagement online really financially struggled.

While some artists found online approaches to mitigating the impact of the Covid pandemic on their artistic practice, and in one case actually benefitted from it, many failed to adapt nor get appropriate governmental support, as had been made available to protect other industries. The Covid pandemic coupled with Brexit has

brought significant shifts to funding of the arts sector, to networking and specifically to a sustainable practice for artists in Scotland.

Educational Value of the Research

Educators who are helping graduating Higher Education art students enter and survive in this uncertain market need to explain the critical theories around how the sector works, together with an understanding of the routes to sustaining successful careers, accessing funding opportunities and facing the challenges they will encounter on the way. The interviewees give useful advice on navigating their careers in times of austerity.

The Scottish Arts & Culture Support Map (December 2020) is available to artists in Scotland, highlighting key organisations who can offer support, networking and funding opportunities. It also explains the resourcing flow from government to organisations in Scotland. It highlights those lost EU funding streams too and awaits a government response to those losses.

The documentary clips will be used to stimulate discussion and debate with Higher Education students around academic theories connecting cultural mentors to artistic success, the relationship between Government cultural policy and the experiences of artists accessing funding and support networks and finally around the use of ‘symbolic violence’ and its relationship to discrimination and gender-based issues.

Further research will be carried out through the use of these materials in workshops with students, to get them to engage with the themes and content of the thesis to see what is valued and what resonates with them and will be used to identify future directions of research.

This research could be useful for graduating students, policymakers and other Scottish artists, offering a road map to successfully engaging with the sector from both a theoretical and an applied position.

Bibliography

- Acker, J. (2006) Inequality regimes: gender, class and race in organizations. *Gender and Society* 20(4): 441–64.
- Althusser, L. (1971) *Letter on Art in Lenin and Philosophy and other essays* trans. Ben Brewster, London: New Left Books, Originally published in *La Nouvelle Critique*, 1966
- Althusser, L. (2014) *On the Reproduction of Capitalism*. London/ New York: Verso. p. 243.
- Alizadeh A, (2017) Marx and Art: Use, Value, Poetry, in *Continental Thought & Theory: A Journal of Intellectual Freedom*, Volume 1, Issue 4: 150 years of Capital, p587-615
- Anderson R.L. (1990) *Calliope's Sisters: A Comparative Study of Philosophies of Art*, Pearson
- Audit Scotland (2018) 'Councils' use of arm's-length organisations' Available at: https://www.audit-scotland.gov.uk/uploads/docs/report/2018/nr_180518_councils_aleos.pdf (Accessed: 25 February 2021)
- Banks M. & Hesmondhalgh D. (2009) Looking for work in creative industries policy, *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 15:4, 415-430,
- Banks M & O'Connor J (2009) After the creative industries. *International Journal of Cultural Policy* Volume 15, 2009 – Issue 4. Pages 365-373
- Banks M (2010) Craft labour and creative industries. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 16:3, 305-321
- Banks, M. Gill R. Taylor, S. (eds) (2013) *Theorizing Cultural Work: Labour, Continuity and Change, in the Cultural and Creative Industries*, London: Routledge,
- Banks M, Ebrey J & Toynbee J. (2014) *Working Lives in Black British Jazz; A Report and Survey*
- Banks, M. & Oakley, K. (2016) The dance goes on forever? Art schools, class and UK higher education, in the *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 22:1, 41-57
- Banks, M. (2020) The work of culture and C-19, in the *European Journal of Cultural Studies* 2020, Vol. 23(4) 648–654
- Barker, C. (2004) *Making sense of cultural studies: Central problems and Critical Debates*, London: SAGE.
- Barker, C. (2004) *The SAGE dictionary of cultural studies*, London: SAGE

- Barrett, T. (1997) Modernism and Postmodernism: an overview with art examples, in Hutchens J W & Stevens Suggs M. *Art Education Content and Practice in a Post Modern Era*, Virginia, NAEA
- Bauman, Z. (1999) *Liquid Modernity*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Bauman, Z. (2000) *The Individualised Society*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- BBC. (2012) In full: Open letter to Creative Scotland. Available at: <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-19880680> (Accessed: October 9, 2012)
- Beardsley M C, (1981) *Aesthetics: Problems in the Philosophy of Criticism*, 2nd ed. Indianapolis: Hackett Publishing Company, Inc.,
- Beardsley M C. (1976) Is Art Essentially Institutional? In Lars Aagaard-Mogensen, ed., *Culture and Art*. Atlantic Highlands, NJ: Humanities Press
- Becker, H. S. (1974) Art as collective action. *American Sociological Review* 39 (6) pp767-776.
- Becker, H.S. (1976) Art worlds and social types. *American Behavioral Scientist* 19 (6): pp703-719.
- Becker, H. S. (1984) 'Art Worlds', London: University of California Press
- Belfiore, E. (2002) Art as a Means of Alleviating Social Exclusion: Does It Really Work? in *A Critique of Instrumental Cultural Policies and Social Impact Studies in the UK*, *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, vol.8, no.1, pp.91-106
- Belfiore, E. & Bennett, O. (2006) *Rethinking the Social Impact of the Arts: A Critical-Historical Review*, Centre for Cultural Policy Studies, University of Warwick, Research Paper no. 9 Series eds. Bennett, O. & Ahearne, J.
- Belfiore E (2020) Whose cultural value? Representation, power and creative industries, *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 26:3, 383-397,
- Bell, C. (1914). *Art*. London: Chatto & Windus.
- F Bianchini, M Parkinson (ed) (1993) *Cultural Policy and Urban Regeneration: The West European Experience* Manchester: Manchester University Press
- F. Bianchini (1993) *Remaking European Cities: the role of cultural policies*, in F. Bianchini and M. Parkinson, eds. (1993) *Cultural Policy and Urban Regeneration: the West European Experience*, Manchester: Manchester University Press

Blain N & D. Hutchinson D (Eds.) (2013) *The Media in Scotland*, Wilts: Edinburgh University Press.

Blanche R. (2015) *Mapping the Visual Arts in Scotland - Survey of Individuals Working in the Visual Arts Sector in Scotland, A Report of Key Findings*. Available at:

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/36483/Survey-of-Individuals.pdf

(Accessed: 5 October 2020)

Blanche R. (2015) *What we learned about Visual Arts in Scotland*, , P3

part of: *Mapping the Visual Arts in Scotland* (SCAN & Creative Scotland. Available at

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0008/36485/What-we-learned-SCAN.pdf

(Accessed: 10 October 2020)

Blanche, R. (2015) *Mapping the Visual Arts in Scotland, Survey of Individuals Working in the Visual Arts Sector in Scotland* Creative Scotland Visual Arts Sector Review October 2016. Available at

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0004/36481/Visual-Arts-Sector-Review-Final-Report.pdf (Accessed: 10 October 2020)

Blanche, R. (2015) *Scottish Contemporary Art Network (SCAN) On behalf of Creative Scotland A Report of Key Findings*. Available at:

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/36483/Survey-of-Individuals.pdf

(Accessed: 16 October 2020)

Blizek W. (1974) *An institutional theory of art*, *The British Journal of Aesthetics*, Volume 14, Issue 2, SPRING 1974, Pages 142–150

Bonnar, A. (2014) *What does culture mean to you? The practice and process of consultation on cultural policy in Scotland since devolution*, *Cultural Trends*, 23:3, pp 136-147, Routledge. Available at

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2014.925278> (Accessed: 23 December 2020)

Bonnar & Keenlyside. (2000) *A national cultural strategy for Scotland. Report of consultation*. Retrieved May 12, 2014, Available at: <http://annebonnar.files.wordpress.com/2012/10/a-national-cultural-strategy-for-scotland-2000-consultation-report.pdf>

Bourdieu P & Nice R. (1980) *The production of belief: contribution to an economy of symbolic goods*, *Media, Culture & Society*, vol. 2, 3: pp. 261-293

Bourdieu, P. (1983) *The Forms of Capital*. In J. G. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education* (pp. 241-258). New York: Greenwood Press.

Bourdieu, P. (1985) *The social space and the genesis of groups*, in *Social Science Information* Vol. 24, No. 2: pp. 195–220

- Bourdieu, P. (1986) 'The forms of Capital', in Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education, Richardson, J (Ed.), London: Greenwood Press, pp241-258.
- Bourdieu P, (1994) *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press
- Bourdieu, P. Haacke, H. (1995) *Free Exchange*. Stanford Calif: Stanford University Press
- Bourdieu, P. (1996) *Rules of Art: Genesis and Structure of the Literary Field*. USA: Stanford University Press,
- Bourdieu, P. (1993) *The Field of Cultural Production: Essays on Art and Literature*. New York: Columbia University Press
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology* 3, 77–101.
- British Council, (2016), *Scottish Enlightenment*, Available at: <https://www.britishcouncil.org/research-policy-insight/insight-articles/scottish-enlightenment> (Accessed: 18 July 2020)
- Burkett, Paul (2001) Book Review: *Social Capital versus Social Theory: Political Economy and Social Science at the Turn of the Millennium* by Ben Fine, London: Routledge, *Historical Materialism*, Vol. 12, No. 1, pp. 233-246.
- Caves, R. (2000) *Creative industries: contracts between art and commerce*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press
- Chin-tao Wu, (2003) *Privatizing Culture: Corporate Art Intervention Since the 1980s*, Verso
- Clark, K. (1990) *Civilisation: A Personal View*, HarperCollins
- Collingwood, R.G. (1971) *The Principles of Art*, Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Comunian, R. et al., (2010) Unrewarded careers in the creative class: the strange case of bohemian graduates. In *Regional Science*, 89 (2), 389–410.
- Conor B., Gill R., Taylor S. (2015) Gender and creative labour, in *The Sociological Review*, 63: S1, pp. 1–22, Oxford, John Wiley & Sons
- Cote, M. and Pybus, J. (2011), 'Learning to immaterial labour 2.0: Facebook and social networks', in M.A. Peters and E. Bulut (eds), *Cognitive Capitalism, Education and Digital Labour*, 169–193, New York: Peter Lang.

Cox, G. (2005) Cox review of creativity in business: building on the UK's strengths. London: HMSO.

Creative Scotland (2015) 'Visual Arts in Scotland, 2015', Available at:

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0008/36485/What-we-learned-SCAN.pdf (Accessed: 23 March 2020)

Creative Scotland (2016) 'Report on the Consultation – Visual Arts Sector Review, October 2016' in Creative Scotland 2016 Visual Arts Sector Review Final Report. Available at:

<https://www.creativescotland.com/resources/our-publications/sector-reviews/visual-arts-sector-review> (Accessed: 08 October 2020)

Creative Scotland (2019) Creative Scotland Annual Budget 2018/19. Available at:

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0004/57487/Annual-Budget-2018_v2.pdf (Accessed: 8 October 2020)

Creative Scotland (2019) Creative Scotland Annual Plan, 2019, Available at:

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0010/82378/Annual-Plan-2019-FINAL.pdf (Accessed: 5 October 2020)

Creative Scotland (2019) Letter to CTE&EAC, 14 June 2019 Available at:

https://www.parliament.scot/S5_European/General%20Documents/CTEEA_2019.06.14_CreativeScotland_FollowUp.pdf. (Accessed: 26 October 2020)

Creative Scotland (2019) 'Creative Scotland to Finance and Constitution Committee, Funding of EU Structural Fund Priorities in Scotland, Post-Brexit Submission', Available at:

https://www.parliament.scot/S5_Finance/Inquiries/22.2_Creative_Scotland.pdf (Accessed: 27 October 2020)

Creative Scotland (2021) 'Creative Scotland, Regular Funding 2018-21: The Network' Available at:

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0008/47627/RFO-Overview-2018.pdf (Accessed: 16 October 2020)

Creative Scotland (2020) 'Creative Scotland Annual Plan 2019/2020'. Available at:

https://www.creativescotland.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0010/82378/Annual-Plan-2019-FINAL.pdf (Accessed: 23 October 2020)

Creative Scotland (2019) 'Letter to CTE&EAC from Creative Scotland', Available at:

https://www.parliament.scot/S5_European/General%20Documents/CTEEA_2019.06.14_CreativeScotland_FollowUp.pdf. (Accessed: 28 October 2020)

Croce, B. (1967) Aesthetic, London: Peter Owen - Vision Press

Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1988) 'Society, Culture and Person: A Systems View of Creativity', in R. Sternberg (ed.) *The Nature of Creativity* (Cambridge University Press), pp. 325–38.

Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1990) 'The Domain of Creativity', in M. A. Runco and R. S. Albert (eds) *Theories of Creativity* (London: Sage), pp. 190–212.

Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1994) 'The Domain of Creativity', in Feldman D. H., Csikszentmihalyi M. and Gardner H. (eds.) *Changing the World: A Framework for the Study of Creativity* (Westport, CT: Praeger), pp. 135–58.

Csikszentmihalyi, M. (2007) '*Creativity; Flow and the Psychology of Discovery and Invention*' HarperCollins e-books

Culture, Tourism, Europe and External Affairs Committee (2019) *Putting Artists In The Picture: A Sustainable Arts Funding System For Scotland*, 5th Report, (Session 5) (Accessed: 20 October 2020)

Culture, Tourism, Europe and External Affairs Committee. (2019) Official Report, 21 November 2019, Col 8. See: Local Government and Regeneration Committee. 7th Report, 2016, Session 4, *Inquiry into arm's length external organisations* (SP Paper 941).

Culture Counts (2012) *Culture counts*, Available at: <http://culturecounts.wordpress.com/home/> (Accessed: Jan 2022)

Currey, M. (2019) *Daily Rituals Women at Work*, New York: Picador

Danto A, (1964) *The Artworld*, in *The Journal of Philosophy*, Vol. 61, No. 19, American Philosophical Association Eastern Division Sixty-First Annual Meeting. (Oct. 15, 1964), pp. 571-584

Danto, A.C. (1992) '*Beyond the Brillo Box: The Visual Arts in Post-historical Perspective*', CA: University of California Press

Duncan, C. (1983) 'Who Rules the Art World?', in *The Aesthetics of Power: Essays in Critical Art History*, Cambridge University Press, 172–80.

Dunlop, S., Galloway, S., Hamilton, C., & Scullion, A. (2004) *The economic impact of the cultural sector in Scotland*. Retrieved March 4, 2015, from: <http://christinehamiltonconsulting.com/wpcontent/uploads/2011/10/Economic-Impact-Report.pdf>.

DCMS (2008) *Creative Britain: new talents for the new economy*. London: DCMS

Dent T. (2020) Devalued women, valued men: motherhood, class and neoliberal feminism in the creative media industries. *Media, Culture & Society*.;42(4):537-553.

Dewey J, (1934) *Art as Experience*, New York : Minton, Balch & company

G. Dickie G (1976) *What is Art?* in *Culture and Art: An Anthology*. Ed. Lars Aagaard-Mogensen. Atlantic Highlands, NJ: Humanities Press, 21-32.

Dickie, George (1993) "What is art? An institutional analysis" [an excerpt of *Art and the Aesthetic* (1974)], in John W. Bender and H. Gene Blocker, (eds), (1993), *Contemporary Philosophy of Art: Readings in Analytic Aesthetics*, Prentice-Hall, pp. 171–82

Diffey, T. J. (1969) *The Republic of Art*. in *British Journal of Aesthetics* 19: 145–156

Dissanayake, E. (1991) 'Art as a human behavior: toward an ethological view of art' [1980 article in *JAAC*], reprinted in Howard Smagula (ed.), *Re-Visions: New Perspectives of Art Criticism*, Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, pp. 124-137.

Docampo, M. (2005) 'Tango Queer', accessed Havmoeller, B, Batchelor R & Aramo O (Ed), 2015, *The Queer Tango Book*, Ideas, Images and Inspiration in the 21st Century, accessed <http://www.queertangobook.org>

Drew Wylie Projects Ltd. (2019) *Scottish Parliament – Arts Funding Inquiry Comparative Analysis*. Available at: [Arts Funding Inquiry comparative analysis - Scottish Parliament](#) (Accessed: 15 Jan 2020)

Eagleton, T. (1990) *The ideology of the aesthetic*. Oxford: Blackwell

Eikhof, D. & Warhurst, C., (2013). *The promised land? Why social inequalities are systemic in the creative industries*. In *Employee Relations*, 35 (5), 495–508.

Escotregen, (2005) 'Planning Creativity, in *The Hidden Glasgow Forums*', Available at: <http://www.hiddenglasgow.com/forums/viewtopic.php?f=25&t=1919> (Accessed: 29 December 20)

FashionUnited, (2016) *UK fashion industry statistics*. Available at: <https://fashionunited.uk/uk-fashion-industry-statistics> (Accessed: 10 May 2019)

Fernie (1995) *Art History and Its Methods*, London; Phaidon Press

Fischer E.P. (1963) *The Necessity of Art: a Marxist approach*: Baltimore, Pelican

Franks, S. (1999) *Having none of it: Women, Men and the Future of Work*. London: Granta

Foucault, M. (1980) 'Truth and Power', in *Power/Knowledge*, New York: Pantheon Books.

Florida, R. (2003) *Rise of the Creative Class: And How It's Transforming Work, Leisure, Community and Everyday Life*, Basic Books, Available at:

<http://www.hiddenglasgow.com/forums/viewtopic.php?f=25&t=1919> (Accessed: 9 November 2020)

Frankel, E. (2020) I get censored four or five times a year, Paul McCarthy, art's virtuoso of vile, *Guardian*, Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2020/aug/04/paul-mccarthy-artist-america-alpine-stories> (Accessed: 4 August 2020)

Fulton J., Paton E. (2016) *The Systems Model of Creativity*, in: McIntyre P., Fulton J., Paton E. (eds) *The Creative System in Action*. Palgrave Macmillan: London

Freud S. (2010) 'The interpretation of Dreams', translated by Strachey J., Philadelphia, Hogarth Press

Frith, S. and Horne, H., 1987. *Art into pop*. London: Methuen.

Galloway, S. (2004) *Public funding on the arts within the UK (CCPR Briefing Paper)*, Glasgow: CCPR, University of Glasgow.

Galloway S. & Jones H.D. (2010) *The Scottish dimension of British arts government: a historical perspective*, *Cultural Trends*, 19:1-2, 27-40,

Galvin, J. et al (2015) 'Mental health nursing students' experiences of stress during training: a thematic analysis of qualitative interviews' in the *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*, Vol 22 Issue 10

Gardiner, M. (2005), *Modern Scottish culture*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press

Gavin F. (2020) 'Francesca Gavin interviews Phoebe Saatchi Yates'. *Financial Times* 3rd October 2020,

Gill R (2007) *Technobohemians or the new Cybertariat? Network Notebooks 01: New Media Work in Amsterdam a Decade after the Web*

Glaser, B. & Strauss, A. (1967) *The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research*. Mill Valley, CA: Sociology Press

Glasgow City Council (2007), *The Merchant City Townscape Heritage Initiative (THI)*. Available at: <https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/article/18301/Merchant-City-Initiative> (Accessed: 15 August 2020)

Glasgow School of Art (2020) 'Turner Prize' Available at: <http://www.gsa.ac.uk/about-gsa/key-information/our-structure/school-of-fine-art/turner-prize/> (Accessed: 10 December 2020)

Glasgow City Council (2007) *Glasgow City Council's Five Year Action Plan (2007-12)*

- Glasgow City Council (2019) Glasgow Draft Culture Plan. Available at: <https://www.glasgowcultureplan.com/>
(Accessed: 13 May 2022)
- Glasgow Life, (2021) Glasgow Life's Artists in Residence. Available at:
<https://www.glasgowlife.org.uk/arts-music-and-cultural-venues/festivals/glasgow-lifes-artists-in-residence>
(Accessed: 9 May 2022)
- Gordon-Nesbitt, R. (2011) The New Bohemia, Variant 32
- Gordon-Nesbitt, R. (2011) Glasgow Life or Death, Variant 41
- Gordon-Nesbitt, R. (2009) The Culture of Capital, Critique Vol. 37, No. 4, November 2009, pp. 553_564
- Goodman, N. (1969) Languages of Art : An Approach to a Theory of Symbols, London: Oxford University Press
- Graham, G. (1997) The Marxist Theory of Art, British Journal of Aesthetics 37
- Gray, N. (2009) 'Glasgow's Merchant City: An Artist Led Property Strategy' Available at:
<https://romulusstudio.com/variant/pdfs/issue34/merchant34.pdf> (Accessed: 8 December 2020)
- Greenberg, C. (1939) Avant-garde and Kitch, Partisan Review, Available at:
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Avant-Garde-and-KitschGreenberg/c2bf2bb12e8789c82e6e40db6efa1715ffc8e51d> (Accessed 26 April 22)
- Greenberg C. (1961) Art & Culture, Beacon Press: Boston
- Groys, B. (2008) 'Art Power'. The MIT Press: Cambridge
- Hagberg, G.L. (2002) The Institutional Theory of Art: Theory and Anti theory, in Smith P, Wilde, C. A Companion to Art Theory, Blackwell Publishers Ltd pp. 487-504
- Hannula, M. (2004) 'The Responsibility and Freedom of Interpretation', in Miles M (Ed), 2004, New Practices, New pedagogies, London: Taylor & Francis Group
- Hassan G & Mitchel J, (2013) After Independence: The State of the Scottish Nation Debate, Birlinn Ltd
- Hefferon J & Gil-Rodriguez E. (2011) Methods: Interpretative phenomenological analysis, The psychologist vol 24 No 10, Available at: <https://thepsychologist.bps.org.uk/volume-24/edition-10/methods-interpretative-phenomenological-analysis> (accessed 02 Jan 2021)
- Hegel, G. (1975) Aesthetics. Lectures on Fine Art, trans. T.M. Knox, 2 vols., Oxford: Clarendon Press

Hesmondhalgh, D. (2007) *The Cultural Industries*, London: Sage.

Hesmondhalgh, D. & Baker, S., (2011), *Creative labour: Media work in Three Cultural Industries*, Abingdon: Routledge.

Hesmondhalgh, D., Oakley, K., Lee, D., & Nesbitt, M. (2015). *Culture, economy and politics: The case of New Labour*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Hesmondhalgh D. (2006) Bourdieu, the media and cultural production. In *Media, Culture & Society*.;28(2):211-231

Hewison, R. (1995) *Culture and consensus: England, art and politics since 1940*, London: Methuen.

Higher Education Statistics Authority, (2020) Available at: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis/students/what-study> (Accessed: 12 October 2020)

Hoare Q., & Nowell Smith G. eds., (1971) *Selections from the Prison Notebooks of Antonio Gramsci*

Hobbs, J. A. (1997) 'The Interaction between Art Education and Theories of Art' in Hutchens J W & Stevens Suggs M., *Art Education Content and Practice in a Post Modern Era*, Virginia: NAEA

Holden, J. (2004) *Capturing Cultural Value, How culture has become a tool of government policy*, Demos

Holden, J. (2006) *Cultural value and the crisis of legitimacy*, London: Demos.

Holden, J. (2008) *Democratic culture; opening up the arts to everyone*, Demos

Holden, J. (2011) *Cultural Diplomacy talk, Jersey*. Available at: <https://www.gov.je/sitecollectiondocuments/leisure%20and%20entertainment/r%20culturaldiplomacytalk%200111126.pdf> (Accessed 27 April 2022)

Holgate, J. & McKay S. (2009) Equal opportunities policies: how effective are they in increasing diversity in the audio-visual industries' freelance labour market? In *Media, Culture & Society*.;31(1):151-163

Horkheimer, M. & Adorno, T.W. (2002) 'The culture industry: Enlightenment as mass deception', in Gunzelin Schmid Noerr (ed.), *Dialectic of Enlightenment: Philosophical Fragments*, pp. 94–136. Translated by Jephcott E. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press

Hume, D. (1910) *Of the Standard of Taste*. In C. W. Eliott (Ed.), *English Essays from Sir Philip Sidney to Macaulay* (pp. 215–236). P F Collier & Son. (Original work published 1757)

- Hursthouse, R. (1992) Truth and Representation, in *Philosophical Aesthetics*. Edited by Hanfling O., 239–296. Oxford: Blackwell
- Hyer, E. A. & Billingsley, D. (no date) Art & Politics in Mao’s China, Available at: <https://kennedy.byu.edu/art-politics-in-maos-china/> (Accessed 2 May 2022)
- Hyslop, F. (2013) Past, present and future: Culture and heritage in an independent Scotland. Speech, 5 June. Edinburgh: Talbot Rice Gallery. Retrieved May 12, 2014, Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/News/Speeches/Culture-Heritage05062013> (Accessed 3 May 2022)
- Jensen, R. (1994) *Marketing Modernism in Fin-de-siècle Europe*, Princeton University Press
- Jones, R.L. (1997) ‘Modern and Postmodern Questioning Contemporary Pedagogy in the Visual Arts’, in Hutchens J W & Stevens Suggs M. *Art Education Content and Practice in a Post Modern Era*, Virginia: NAEA
- Jordan, G., & Weedon C. (1995) *Cultural Politics: Class, Gender, Race and the Postmodern World*. Oxford: Blackwell
- Kant, I. (1951) *Critique of Judgement*, trans. Bernard J.H. New York: Hafner Press
- Kawashima, N. (2006) Audience development and social inclusion in Britain. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 13(1): 56–70.
- Kearney, R. (1988) ‘The wake of imagination: Ideas of creativity in Western culture’, Hutchinson
- Kent, T. (1993) *Paralogic Rhetoric: A Theory of Communicative Interaction*, Cranbury, NJ: Associated University Presses.
- Khaleeli H. (2014) Britain's ethnic minorities need better access to the TV and film industry. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2014/jan/24/britain-ethnic-minorities-access-tv-film> (Accessed 12 April 22)
- Kymlicka, W. (1996) *Multicultural Citizenship: A Liberal Theory of Minority Rights*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Landry, C. Greene, L. Matarosso, F. & Bianchini, F. (1996) *The Art of Regeneration: Urban renewal through cultural activity*, Stroud: Comedia
- Langer, S.K., (1957), *Problems of Art*, New York: Scribners

- Latham, S. & Rogers, G. (2015) *Modernism: Evolution of an Idea*, London: Bloomsbury
- Leadbeater, C. and Oakley, K. (1999) *The independents*, London: Demos.
- Leitch, S. (2006) *Prosperity for all in the global economy – world class skills*. London: Her Majesty's Stationery Office.
- Lenard, P. T. (2020) Culture, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2020 Edition), Zalta E.N. (ed.). Available at: <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2020/entries/culture/> (Accessed: 20 Jan 2022)
- LeWitt, S. (1967) Paragraphs on Conceptual Art, in *Artforum* Vol.5, no. 10,
- Lippard, L. (1973) *Six Years: The Dematerialization of the Art Object From 1966 to 1972*, NY: Praeger Publishers
- Litowitz, D. (2000) *Gramsci, Hegemony, and the Law*, 2000 *BYU L. Rev.* 515. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol2000/iss2/1> (Accessed: 5 Feb 2022)
- Lukacs, G. (1970) *Writer and Critic and Other Essays*, trans. A Kahn, London: Merlin Press, pp.137, 146
- McConnell, J. (2003). *St Andrew's day speech*. Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/News/Releases/2003/11/4641> (Accessed: 12 May 2020)
- Macdonald, M. (2007) *The Scottish Enlightenment: A Visual Culture*, Available at: <https://mapmagazine.co.uk/the-scottish-enlightenment-a> (Accessed: 6 May 2020)
- McAndrew, C. (2017) *The Art Market*. Available at: https://d33ipftjqr91.cloudfront.net/asset/cms/Art_Basel_and_UBS_The_Art_Market_2017.pdf (Accessed: 18 November 2020)
- McCall, V. and Playford, C. (2012) *Culture and the Scottish household survey*. *Cultural Trends*, 21(2): 149–172.
- McCarthy, P. (2020) *I get censored four or five times a year': Paul McCarthy, art's virtuoso of vile*, Available at: https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2020/aug/04/paul-mccarthy-artist-america-alpine-stories?CMP=Share_iOSApp_Other (Accessed: 4 August 2020)
- McDonald, D. (2019), *'Glasgow announces 23 Artists beginning residencies across the city*, in *Glasgow Life*. Available at:

<https://www.glasgowlife.org.uk/news/glasgow-announces-23-artists-beginning-residencies-across-the-city>

(Accessed: 19 December 2020)

MacDonald, M. (2007) *The Scottish Enlightenment: A Visual Culture*. Available at:

<https://mapmagazine.co.uk/the-scottish-enlightenment-a> (Accessed: 9 March 2020)

McGuigan, J. (1996) *Culture and the Public Sphere*, London: Routledge

McIntyre, P. Fulton, J. Paton, E. (Ed) (2016), *The Creative System in Action: Understanding Cultural Production and Practice*, UK: Palgrave Mcmillan

McMillan, J. (2010) *Arts budget hardly deserves to “share the pain” of country’s cuts*, Scotsman 23 July.

Available at: <http://www.scotsman.com/lifestyle/culture/joyce-mcmillan-arts-budget-hardly-deserves-to-share-the-pain-of-country-s-cuts-1-818526> (Accessed: 15 March 2022)

McMaster, B. (2008) *Supporting Excellence in the Arts, From Measurement to Judgement*,

Department for Culture, Media and Sport, London, Cabinet Office, James Purnell, Secretary of State for Culture, Media and Sport cited in McMaster, (2008), p.4

McRobbie, A. (2002) *Clubs to Companies: Notes on the decline of political culture in speeded up creative worlds*, in *Cultural Studies* 16:4, 516-531

McRobbie, A. (2016) *Be Creative: Making a Living in the New Culture Industries*. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press

Madden, C. (2009) *The independence of government art funding: A review*, in *D'Art Topics in Art Policy* No.9,

Sydney: International Federation of Arts Councils and Cultural Agencies. Available at:

[http://media.ifacca.org/files/Dart9independencereport\(1\).pdf](http://media.ifacca.org/files/Dart9independencereport(1).pdf) (Accessed: 8 April 2022)

Mangset, P. (2020) *The end of cultural policy?* in *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 26:3, 398-411

Marcuse, P. (1989) *Dual City: Muddy Metaphor for a Quartered City*, *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 13: 697-708

Matarasso, F. (1997) *Use or Ornament? The Social Impact of Participation in the Arts*. Available at:

<https://www.artshealthresources.org.uk/docs/use-or-ornament-the-social-impact-of-participation-in-the-arts/>

(Accessed: 5 June 2022)

Matarasso, F. (2003) *Smoke and Mirrors: A Response to Paola Merli’s “Evaluating the Social Impact of Participation*. In *Arts Activities*”, *IJCP*, 2002, vol.8, no.1, *International Journal of Cultural Policy* vol.9, no.3, pp.337-346

Maxwell, L. (2011) *The Crisis in Art History: Ten Problems, Ten Solutions*, Anderson

- Miles, A. & Gibson, L. (2016) *Everyday participation and cultural value*, *Cultural Trends*, 25:3, 151-157
- Miller, T. & Yudice, G. (2002) *Cultural Policy*, London, Sage
- Moore, M. (1999) *Beyond the Cultural Argument for Liberal Nationalism*, *Critical Review of International Social and Political Philosophy*, 2(3): 26–47
- Morrissey, L. (2005) *Pierre Bourdieu (1930–2002)* from “The Field of Cultural Production, Or: The Economic World Reversed,” (1983). In: Morrissey L. (eds) *Debating the Canon: A Reader from Addison to Nafisi*, New York: Palgrave Macmillan
- Morrison, T. (2020) *Mouth Full of Blood*, UK; Vintage
- Morgan, G. & Nelligan, P. (2018) *The Creativity Hoax: Precarious Work and the Gig Economy*, London: Anthem Press
- Mulgan, G. (1986) *Saturday Night or Sunday Morning? From Arts to Industry* in *New Forms of Cultural Policy* Stroud: Comedia
- Myerscough, J. (1988b) *The Economic Importance of the Arts in Glasgow*, London: Policy Studies Institute
- Myerscough, J. (1988) *The Economic Importance of the Arts in Britain*, London: Policy Studies Institute
- Nance, K. (2008) *The Spirit and the Strength: A Profile of Toni Morrison*. Available at: https://www.pw.org/content/the_spirit_and_the_strength_a_profile_of_toni_morrison (Accessed: 6 June 2019)
- Nash, R. (1999) *Bourdieu, ‘Habitus’, and Educational Research: Is it all Worth the Candle?*, *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, Vol. 20, No. 2, pp. 175-187.
- National Records of Scotland (2019) *Mid-2017 population estimates Scotland and Question S5W-22384*: Angela Constance, Almond Valley, Scottish National Party, Date Lodged: 27/03/2019 Answered by Fiona Hyslop (10/04/2019).
- Neff, G., Wissinger, E., & Zukin, S. (2005) *Entrepreneurial labor among cultural producers: “Cool” jobs in “hot” industries*. *Social Semiotics*, 15(3), 307–334.
- Nochlin, L. (1971) *Why Have There Been No Great Women Artists?* ARTnews
- Netzer, D. (1978) *The Subsidized Muse*, New York: Cambridge University Press
- O’Hagan, J. (1998) *The State and the Arts: An Analysis of Key Economic Policy Issues in Europe and the United States*, Cheltenham: Edward Elgar

O'Neill, M. (ed.) (1998) *The People's Palace Book of Glasgow*, Edinburgh: Mainstream Publishing

Outset Scotland (No date) Available at: <https://outset.org.uk> (Accessed: 6 June 2019)

Parvin, P. (2008) What's Special About Culture? Identity, Autonomy, and Public Reason, *Critical Review of International Social and Political Philosophy*, 11(3): 315–233.

Patten, A. (2014) *Equal Recognition: The Moral Foundations of Minority Rights*, Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.

Pearse, H. (1997) *Doing Otherwise: Art Education Praxis in a Post Paradigmatic World*, in Hutchens J W & Stevens Suggs M. 1997, *Art Education Content and Practice in a Post Modern Era*, Virginia: NAEA

Pearce, M. (2022) *The Art of Propaganda: Kitsch and Avant-Garde*, in *Mutual Art*. Available at: https://www.mutualart.com/Article/The-Art-of-Propaganda--Kitsch-and-Avant-/FCAD40322CD4AC51?utm_source=MutualArt+Subscribers&utm_campaign=390f706a38-EMAIL_CAMPAIGN_Magazine_COPY_01&utm_medium=email&utm_term=0_0a9ce6ca24-390f706a38-448454856 (Accessed: 26/04/22)

Peck, J. (2007) *The Creativity Fix*, Eurozine. Available at: <https://www.eurozine.com/the-creativity-fix/> (Accessed: 8 April 2022)

Peillon, M. (1998) Bourdieu's Field and the Sociology of Welfare, *Journal of Social Policy*, Vol. 27, No. 2, pp. 213-229.

Pollock, G. (2015) *Vision and Difference; Feminism, Femininity and the Histories of Art*, London: Routledge

Randle, K. Forson, C. Calveley, M. (2015) Towards a Bourdieusian analysis of the social composition of the UK film and television workforce. *Work, Employment & Society* 29(4): 590–606.

Reid, K. Flowers, P. Larkin, M. (2005) Exploring lived experience. *The Psychologist* 18, pp. 20-23

Robinson, H. (2015) *Feminism-Art-Theory; An anthology 1968-2014*, Wiley: Blackwell

Royal Scottish Academy (2020) 'Royal Scottish Academicians'. Available at: <https://www.royalscottishacademy.org/royal-scottish-academicians/> (Accessed: 9 December 2020)

SCAN (2016) *What we learned about Visual Arts in Scotland, 2015*. Available at: <https://sca-net.org/downloads/5807417db7f79-scanmappingthevisualartsresearch.pdf> (Accessed: 5 February 2020)

Schlesinger, P. (2009) The SNP, cultural policy and the idea of the “creative economy. In *The modern SNP: From protest to power*, Edited by: Hassan, G. 135–146. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

Scotsman (2016) Glasgow’s SSE Hydro named third busiest venue in the world - 1st Feb 2016. Available at: <http://www.scotsman.com/lifestyle/culture/music/glasgow-s-sse-hydro-named-third-busiest-venue-in-the-world-1-4017567> (Accessed: 25 March 2022)

Scottish Artists Union (2018) Scottish Artists Union’s Membership Survey Results, 2017. Available at: <https://d3n8a8pro7vhmx.cloudfront.net/artistsunionscot/pages/450/attachments/original/1559738229/scottish-artists-union--members-report-2017.pdf?1559738229> (Accessed: 11 May 2020)

Scottish Executive (2000) *Creating our Future... Minding our Past: Scotland’s National cultural strategy* Edinburgh: Scottish Executive

Scottish Government. (2007a) Draft culture (Scotland) bill consultation: Report of responses. Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2007/08/16120452/0> (Accessed: 10 February 2022)

Scottish Government (2020) ‘A Culture Strategy for Scotland 2020’, Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2020/02/culture-strategy-scotland/documents/culture-strategy-scotland/culture-strategy-scotland/govscot%3Adocument/culture-strategy-scotland.pdf?forceDownload=true> (Accessed: 13 December 2020)

Scottish Government. (2020) Scottish Local Government Finance Statistics (SLGFS) 2018-19. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-local-government-finance-statistics-slgfs-2018-19/> (Accessed: January 1, 2021)

Scottish Government. (2020) Scottish Budget 2019-20 – amendments following passage of the Budget (Scotland) (No.3) Bill 2021. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-budget-2019-20---amendments-following-passage-of-the-budget-scotland-no.3-bill/> (Accessed January 1 2021)

Scottish Government (2019) *Putting Artists in the Picture: A Sustainable Arts Funding System for Scotland*. Available at: [‘Putting Artists In The Picture: A Sustainable Arts Funding System For Scotland’](#). (Accessed: 15 October 2020)

Scottish Government (2019) *A Culture Strategy for Scotland*, Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/strategy-plan/2020/02/culture-strategy-scotland/documents/culture-strategy-scotland/culture-strategy-scotland/govscot%3Adocument/culture-strategy-scotland.pdf?forceDownload=true> (Accessed: 2 October 2020)

Scottish Parliament (2008) SPICe briefing: Creative Scotland bill, Edinburgh

- Schiller, H.I. (1991) *Culture, Inc: The Corporate Takeover of Public Expression*. New York: Oxford University Press
- Shaw, R. (Secretary-General, ACGB) to Mason T. (Director, SAC), 21 April 1981 NAS ED61/1.
- Sholette, G. (2011) *Dark Matter: Art and Politics in the Age of Enterprise Culture*, London: Pluto Press
- Sholette, G. (2016) 'Untangling Art's relationship with Capitalism'. Available at: <https://www.plutobooks.com/blog/art-and-capitalism/> (Accessed: 20 September 2020)
- Sholette, G. Charnley, K. (2017) 'Delirium and Resistance; Activist Art and the Crisis of Capitalism'. London: Pluto Press
- Siisiäinen, M. (2000) Two concepts of social capital: Bourdieu vs. Putnam. *International Journal of Contemporary Sociology*. 40. 183-204.
- Smith, A. (1776) *The Wealth of Nations*.
- Smith, J. A. Flowers, P. Larkin, M. (2009) *Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: Theory, Method and Research*. London: Sage
- Smith, J. A. (1996) 'Beyond the divide between cognition and discourse: Using interpretative phenomenological analysis in health psychology', *Psychology and Health*, 11(2), 261-271.
- Stalker, L. H. & Burnett, K. (2016) Good work? Scottish cultural workers' narratives about working and living on islands, In *Island Studies Journal* 11, 1, p. 193-208 16 p.
- Stallabrass, J. (2002) *Art Incorporated: The Story of Contemporary Art*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Sternberg, R. J. (ed), (1999) 'Handbook of Creativity'. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Stevenson, D. (2013) What's the problem again? The problematisation of cultural participation in Scottish cultural policy. *Cultural Trends*, 22(2)
- Stevenson, D. (2008) *Taking part in Scotland: Full report on survey findings*, Edinburgh: Scottish Arts Council
- Talfan Davies, G. (2007) *At arm's length*, Bridgend: Seren
- Taylor, A. (1997) Arm's length but hands on: Mapping the new governance: The Department of Heritage and cultural politics in Britain. *Public Administration*, 75(3): 441–466.

Taylor, M. (2016). Nonparticipation or different styles of participation? Alternative interpretations from Taking Part. *Cultural Trends*.

The City of Edinburgh Council (2019) Citywide Culture Plan Update 2018-19. Available at: <https://cultureedinburgh.com/resources-reports/citywide-culture-plan-update-2018-19> (Accessed 13/05/2022)

The United Nations Organisation for Education, Science and Culture (UNESCO) (2002) Universal declaration on cultural diversity. *Records of the General Conference, Paris, October 15– November 3, 2001*, p. 71. Retrieved June 4, 2014, Available at: <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001246/124687e.pdf> [Google Scholar] (Accessed: 12 April 2022)

Thompson, N. & Sholette, G. (eds) (2004) *The Interventionists: Users' Manual for the Creative Disruption of Everyday Life*, Mass: MoCA/MIT Press,

Thornton, S. (2009) *Seven Days in the Art World*, London: Grants Books

Throsby, D. (2001) *Economics and culture*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

Thurley, S. (2019) *Crown, Country & the Struggle for Cultural Supremacy*. Available at: https://s3-eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/content.gresham.ac.uk/data/binary/3043/2019-04-03_SimonThurley_CulturalSupremacy-T.pdf (Accessed: 9 July 2020)

Timothy, D. (2011) *Cultural heritage and tourism: an introduction*, Bristol: Channel View

Tolstoy, L. (1899) *What is Art?* trans. A. Maude. London: Walter Scott

Travers, T. (1989) The Threat to the autonomy of elected local government, in Crouch and Marquand (eds) (1989)

Tuckett, J. (2021) 'Women in Theatre Forum Report, Part 1, Developing strategies to improve gender equality in the arts', Available at: <https://sphinxtheatre.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Women-in-Theatre-Forum-Report-11121.pdf> (Accessed: 20 January 2021)

Tully, J. (1995) *Strange Multiplicity: Constitutionalism in the Age of Diversity*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

UCLID (2017) *Annual Report 2017*. Available at: <https://m.euclid.int/annual-report-2017/> (Accessed 08 July 2020)

Ursell, G. (2000) *Television production: issues of exploitation, commodification and subjectivity in UK television labour markets*. *Media, culture & society*, 22, 805–825.

- Vasary, G. (1568) *The Lives of the Most Eminent Sculptors, Painters, and Architects*, trans J C Bondanella, J. C, Bondanella, P. in Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Velthuis, O. (2005) *Talking Prices: Symbolic Meanings of Prices on the Market for Contemporary Art*. Princeton NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Voltaire (1764) *Gazette littéraire de l'Europe*, quoted in Lounsbury, T.R. (1902) *Shakespeare and Voltaire* vol. 2
- Weitz, M. (1956) *The Role of Theory in Aesthetics*. In *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 14: 27–35
- Wittel, A. (2001) *Toward a Network Sociality*. *Theory, Culture & Society*. 18(6):51-76.
- Wölfflin, H. (1948) *Classic Art. An Introduction to the Italian Renaissance*. Translated from the 8th German Edition (Benno Schwabe & Co, Basle 1948) by Murray P. & Murray L. (1952) London: Phaidon Press, 2nd Edn. 1953
- Wölfflin, H. (1929) *Principles of Art History. The Problem of the Development of Style in Later Art*, Translated from 7th German Edition (1929) into English by M.D. Hottinger (1932) New York: Dover Publications
- Work Foundation (2007) *Staying ahead: the economic performance of the UK's creative industries*. London: Work Foundation.
- Wright, S. (2008) *Behind Police Lines: Art Visible and Invisible*, in *Art & Research: A Journal of Ideas, Contexts, and Methods*, vol. 2, no. 1, Summer 2008. Available at: www.artandresearch.org.uk (Accessed: 9 March 2020)
- UK Government (2018) *UK government's Brexit White Paper 'The future relationship between the United Kingdom and the European Union'*, Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/786626/The_Future_Relationship_between_the_United_Kingdom_and_the_European_Union_120319.pdf (Accessed: 9 September 2020)
- Zedong, M. (1942) *Talks at the Yen'an Forum on Literature and Art*. Selected Works, Vol. III
- Zedong, M. (1966) Mao Zedong, Culture and Art, Originally published in: *Quotations from Chairman Mao Tse-tung*. Peking: Foreign Languages Press, p. 299-303.
- Zimmer, A. & Toepler, S. (1999) *The Subsidized Muse: Government and the Arts in Western Europe*. in *Journal of Cultural Economics*, Springer; The Association for Cultural Economics International, vol. 23(1), pages 33-49, March.